

GELILA INTERNATIONAL SEMINARY

**THE EFFECT OF HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGEMENT POLICY ON
EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE IN THE CASE OF ADDIS ABABA POLICE
COMMISSION HEAD OFFICE**

**A DISSERTATION SUBMITTED TO GELILA INTERNATIONAL SEMINARY
IN PARTIAL FULFILLMENT FOR THE REQUIREMENTS FOR THE
DEGREE OF DOCTOR OF PHILOSOPHY IN MANAGEMENT AND
LEADERSHIP**

BY: ELIAS EBESO

ADVISOR: DR GOFERE ADISHO

FEBRUARY, 2024

ADDIS ABABA, ETHIOPIA

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This is to certify that the dissertation is prepared by Elias Ebeso, entitled: “The effect of human resource management policy on employee performance in the case of addis ababa police commission head office” and submitted in partial fulfillment of the requirement for the degree of doctor of philosophy in management and leadership complies with the regulation of the Gelila International Seminary and meets the accepted standards with respect to originality and quality.

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External Examiner _____ Signature _____ Date _____

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DECLARATION

The dissertation has not been previously accepted for any degree and is not being concurrently submitted in candidature for any degree in any academic institution.

I declare that the dissertation is a result of my own investigation, except where otherwise stated. I have undertaken the study independently with the guidance and support of any research advisor. Other sources are acknowledged by citations giving explicit reference. A list of reference is appended.

Signature _____

Elias Ebeso

This dissertation has been submitted for examination with my approval as an advisor.

Advisor's Signature _____

Dr. Gofere Adisho

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS	1
LIST OF TABLES	6
ABBREVIATION	8
ABSTRACT	9
CHAPTER ONE	10
1 INTRODUCTION	10
1.1 Background of the Study	10
1.2 Statement of the Problem	14
1.3 Objectives of the Study.....	17
1.3.1 General Objective.....	17
1.3.2 Specific Objectives.....	17
1.4 Research Question	18
1.5 Scope and delimitation of the Study.....	18
1.6 Limitations of the Study	20
1.7 Significance of the Study.....	21
1.8 Definition of Terms	22
1.9 Organisation of the Study	22
1.10 Summary.....	23
CHAPTER TWO	24
2 REVIEW OF LITERATURE	24
INTRODUCTION	24
2.1 The Concept of the effect of human resource management policy	24
2.1.1 Effect Human Resource Management (EHRM)	25
2.1.2 Human Resource management policy and practice	26

2.1.3	Human resource management policy	28
2.1.4	Human Resources Management Practices	36
2.1.5	Employee’s performance.....	58
2.1.6	Relationship between HRMPP with Employee’s performance	59
2.2	Empirical Review of Literature	61
2.2.1	Empirical evidencen on HRM In the global studies	61
2.2.2	Empirical evidence on HRM in Ethiopia	63
2.3	Conceptual Frame work.....	73
2.4	Summary.....	74
CHAPTER THREE		75
RESEARCH DESIGN AND METHODOLOGY.....		75
3.1	Research Design	75
3.2	Research Approach.....	76
3.2.1	Quantitative research approach	76
3.2.2.	Qualitative research approach	76
3.2.3.	Mixed research approach	77
3.3	Target Population, Sampling Technique, and Sample Size.....	78
3.3.1	Target Population	78
3.3.2	Sampling Technique.....	78
3.3.3	Sample Size	79
3.4	Data source and collection methods	82
3.4.1	Sources of Data	82
3.5	Data Collection Instruments	82
3.5.1	Quantitative Methods	82
3.5.2	Qualitative Methods	83

3.6	Data Collection Procedure	84
3.7	Data Analysis.....	85
3.8	Ethical Considerations	87
3.9	Insuring the Quality of Data	88
3.9.1	Validity Test	88
3.9.2	Reliability	89
2.5	Summary.....	91
CHAPTER FOUR.....		92
4.	DATA PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS, AND INTERPRETATION	92
4.1	Demographic characteristics of the respondents	93
4.1.1	The human resource management policy and practices of the Addis Ababa Police Commission.....	93
4.2	Descriptive Statistical Analysis	98
4.2.1	The effect HRMP on the Addis Ababa Police Commission	99
4.2.2	The extent of HRMPP affect the employee’s performance	102
4.3	Result of Inferential Statistics.....	106
4.3.1	Correlation Analysis.....	106
4.3.2	The Relationship between HRMPP and employee performance.	107
4.4	Diagnosis Test	113
4.4.1	Linearity Test	113
4.4.2	Normality Test.....	114
4.4.3	Multicollinearity Test.....	115
4.4.4	Regression Analysis	116
4.4.5	The combinastion of HRMPP & Employee performance for the Development.....	117
4.5	Discussions of Major Findings	125

4.6	Discussions of Interview Results.....	129
2.6	Summary.....	132
CHAPTER FIVE.....		133
5. SUMMARY OF MAJOR FINDINGS, CONCLUSIONS, AND RECOMMENDATIONS		133
5.1	Summary of the Major Findings.....	133
5.2	Conclusions	136
5.3	Recommendations	137
5.4	Recommendations for Further Research	138
REFERENCE.....		140
APPENDIX		162
መጠይቅ		171

LIST OF TABLES

Table 3-1 Staff Data with Sample Size	80
Table 3-2: Cronbach's alpha internal consistency rule of thumb.....	90
Table 3-3 Reliability test	91
Table 4-1 Background of the Respondent.....	93
Table 4-2 Descriptive effect human resource management policy	99
Table 4-3 HRMPP affect the employee's performance	102
Table 4-4 Correlations between HRM Practice and employees' performance	107
Table 4-5 Collinearity Statistics	115
Table 4-6 Model Summaries	117
Table 4-7 ANOVAa Model Summary	118
Table 4-8 Coefficientsa	119
Table 4-9 Model Summaries	121
Table 4-10 Coefficientsa of recrutement on training and development.....	121
Table 4-11 Model Summary of PA on reward &compensation management	122
Table 4-12 the Coefficientsa of performance appraisal on reward, and compensation management	123
Table 4-13 Model Summary effect of Performance management on Training and development	124
Table 4-14 Coefficientsa	124
Table 4-15 Summaries of Results	125

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 2-1 conceptual framework of the study	74
Figure 4-1 Normal Point Plot Standardized Residual	113
Figure 4-2 Frequency Distribution of Standardized Residual.....	115

ABBREVIATION

AI	Artificial intelligence
AMO	Ability, Motivation and Opportunity)
CEO	Center for Effective Organizations'
HR	Human Resource
HRD	Human Resource Development
HRMHuman Resource Management
HRMP	Human Resource Management Practice
KSAs	Knowledge, Skills, and Attitudes
PA	Performance Appraisal
VRIN	Valuable, Rare, Imperfectly Imitable and Non- substitutable

ABSTRACT

Human resource policies are continuing guidelines on the approach an organization intends to adopt in managing its people on various matters concerning employment and state the intent of the organization on different aspects of human resource management. The main objective of this study was to assess the effect of human resource management policy on employee performance in the case of Addis Ababa police commission head office. The study adopted a descriptive survey, which is both quantitative and qualitative non-experimental research. Data production in quantitative form is a component of the quantitative approach. There are 5240 participants in the study overall, including police officers and civil servants. To choose a sample size of 372 people from the population, stratified random sampling is the sampling technique used. Both primary and secondary sources of data were used to reach the study's ultimate goals. There were three areas of study that required inferential statistics, depending on the type of gap or problem. Examining the effects of the last area that required inferential analyses was to determine examining how the confined factors affected the status of the human resource management policies and practices on employee performance was the final area that required inferential analysis. The study found that the inefficient use of affirmative action during prerequisites and selection is a contributing factor to the high turnover rate among police officers. It has been demonstrated that there is a significant relationship between HRM practices and employee performance, with practices including work-life policy, salary, benefits, and training and development having a positive effect on employee performance. The study makes recommendations for improving the Addis Ababa Police Commission's human resource management policy and practice, such as implementing affirmative action during requirements and selection, updating performance management policies, laying out clear expectations during performance evaluations, and linking reward mechanisms with other HR practices.

Key words: Human resource management, policy and employee performance

CHAPTER ONE

1 INTRODUCTION

The study aims at assessing effects of the effect of human resource management policy on employee performance in the case of Addis Ababa police commission head office with due emphasis effects on Recruitment and Selection, Training and Development, Compensation & Reward and Performance Appraisal. This chapter specifically provides an introductory part that includes background of the study, statement of the problem, research question, objective of study, significance of the study, scope of the study, limitation of the study definition of terms and lastly gives an overview of the organization of the study

1.1 Background of the Study

Human resource management (HRM) is the strategic approach to the effective and efficient management of people in a company or organization so that they help their business gain a competitive advantage. It is designed to maximize employee performance in service of an employer's strategic objectives (Johnason, 2009). Human resource management is primarily concerned with the management of people within organizations, focusing on policies and systems (Collings & Wood, 2009).

Human resource policies are continuing guidelines on the approach an organization intends to adopt in managing its people (Michael A. , 2001). They represent specific guidelines to HR managers on various matters concerning employment and state the intent of the organization on different aspects of human resource management, such as recruitment, promotion, compensation, training, selections, etc. (Pravin, 2010). They,

therefore, serve as a reference point when human resources management practices are being developed or when decisions are being made about an organization's workforce.

A good HR policy provides generalized guidance on the approach adopted by the organization, and therefore its employees, concerning various aspects of employment.

A procedure spells out precisely what action should be taken in line with the policies.

Each organization has a different set of circumstances and so develops an individual set of human resource policies (Resource, 2014.). The location and organization's operations will also dictate the content of its policies.

Human Resource Management (HRM) practices are defined as a unique but interrelated set of activities, functions, and processes designed to attract, develop, and sustain a company's human resources (Tangthong et al., 2014). HRM practice is a broad term that includes related but different activities, functions, and processes for the entire human resources of the company. According to Tan and Nasurdin (2011), HRM practices are a system to attract, develop, motivate, and retain employees to ensure the effective implementation and sustainability of the company and its members. In addition, HRM practices are also conceptualized as a set of consistent policies and practices designed to ensure that the company's human capital contributes to the achievement of its business goals (Hee & Jing, 2018; Tan & Nasurdin, 2011). HRM practices are implemented to evaluate employee performance. In this highly competitive era, improving HRM practices can improve employee performance (Caliskan, 2010; Bowra et al., 2012). Ahmad and Shahzad (2011) argued that employee performance expresses the entire faith of an employee in their actions and commitment to achieving the organization's goals and mission. They also mentioned that payroll practices, performance appraisals, and practices related to promotion and staffing are

benchmarks of employee performance. Alagaraja and Shuck (2015) reveal that employee performance can be measured through regular training and improvement. Khan (2010) adopted five HRM practices to investigate the impact of HRM practices on the performance of Pakistani workers and organizations. Recruitment and selection, performance appraisal, training and development, employee relations, and compensation and rewards were the five HRM practices. This study also cover except employee relations all four HRM factors such as Recruitment and Selection, Training and development, Performance appraisal and Reward and Compensation and there impact on Employee's performance.

Performance management (PM) is a goal-oriented process directed toward ensuring that organizational processes are in place to maximize the productivity of employees, teams, and ultimately, the organization. It is a major player in accomplishing organizational strategy in that it involves measuring and improving the value of the workforce. PM includes incentive goals and the corresponding incentive values so that the relationship can be clearly understood and communicated. There is a close relationship between incentives and performance (David & Giannetto, 2009).

Employee performance is considered to be what an employee does and doesn't do. Employee performance involves quality and quantity of output, presence at work, accommodative and helpful nature, and timeliness of output. According to the results of the study conducted, the individual performance showed that the performance of the individuals cannot be verified. Similarly, he asserts that organizations can use direct bonuses and rewards based on individual performance if employee performance is noticeable (Yang, 2008).

Ethiopian human resource management practices differ from those in the West due to differences in cultural factors, economic systems, political systems, and legal and industrial relations. Hence, the importance of human resource management is not uniformly understood at all the case-study companies. Although multinational companies based in Ethiopia see their human resources as the companies' most important asset, the local companies generally do not. Ethiopia's limited experience in industrialization might explain why human resource management in Ethiopia is rudimentary and still has a long way to go (Dirk , J. van Wasbeek, 2004).

The human resource management practices of selection, training, and career development have been found vital to employees and indeed influence turnover intention. To improve employees' turnover intention, the organization should examine the effectiveness of its selection process and conduct a better remuneration reward and recognition scheme, and the training and career development practices of the organization need to be re-established for the employees Esayas, (2019). Training providers design and deliver training so as to make employees motivated, committed, productive, and well-performing. Alemayehu, (2017). Non-financial compensation and rewards were found to be more motivational than financial rewards. Therefore, competitive and effective compensation and rewards should be developed to motivate employees' performance (Begashaw, (2017).

The aim of this study to asses the effect of human resource management policy on employee performance in the case of Addis Ababa police commission head office since from recent years many employees of the organization are not satisfied on their works and the others enter to some crimes such as violastion of human rights and corruption problems. Those problems may be come from proper implements of human resource

management polices in the human resource management departments. Those issues are inciated the researcher to see detail from scholar's perspect views and adress those proplems.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Human resource management refers to the procedures, methods, and systems used by businesses to hire, train, and motivate staff members while also influencing their attitudes, performance, and behavior to further the objectives of the business (Stone, 2008). There were different problems identified in each practice of human resource management, like recruitment and selection mechanisms not properly using strategic human resource plans, performance management systems not being implemented based on employees' agreements, reward management not being linked to performance management systems, etc. These practices were poorly perceived by their employees as helping their performance. The researcher concluded that the practices of HRM in the organisation under study had been implementing different problems in their processes (Assefa , 2019).

The major challenges of human resource management practices vis-à-vis organizational performance were a lack of sufficient budget, an absence of accountability and transparency, technological resistance, an uncomfortable working environment, insufficient managerial capacity building, and a lack of employee inspiration. (Daniel , Tadesse Tulu, 2020).

The recruitment and selection process of HRM practice is not transparent and objective; the organization does not have a standard salary and benefit package and lacks a training and development policy, but relatively has a better staff performance

evaluation system. The study also showed that employees lack awareness of HRM practices, which is one of the main challenges of HRM in the organization, in addition to the lack of commitment of administrators and the compensation system. (Fisseha , 2019).

The results of the HR Rapid Assessment were consistent across the regions, regardless of individual regional characteristics. In all cases, the lack of trained HRM staff was at the top, followed by a lack of budget for HRM activities (aside from compensation and recurrent costs) and a lack of HR planning. All regions identified the lack of a computerized system to gather information on staff and staffing needs on a consistent basis as a priority, seeing HR data as an essential ingredient to improving planning and management (MSH, 2013).

An organization's competitive edge in the corporate world can be created and developed through the use of human resources management as a long-term strategy. As employees enhance their performance, they also provide value to their organizations, which is another area of interest for HRM. (Richard & Johnson, 2001). The activities that affect the rank and file in their organizations focus for HR managers to increase effectiveness and efficiency. The effectiveness of HRM plays a crucial role in fostering an organization's overall performance by providing a long-lasting competitive advantage (Richard and Johnson, 2001). A company's effectiveness and efficiency can be increased by identifying each employee's knowledge, skills, and attitudes (KSAs), motivating them to apply their KSAs, and placing them in the proper roles (Lajara, Lillo, & Sempere, 2003). The manager's efforts to develop and implement the organizational strategy are what drive all HR actions (Wei & Lau, 2005). In the police department, HRM is crucial because police officers interact with community members

as an outward representation of the state. According to Rajendran, each organization's success ultimately rests greatly on the caliber of its human resources (Rajendran, 2005).

The study conducted in Ethiopia (Ashenafi, 2018) stated that teacher's motivation most of the time does not owe to extrinsic factors. Yet, the study conducted by Awoke in 2015 indicates that the key factor in the poor motivation of teachers was a repellent salary. Teachers sensed that the salary and incentives were very low. His studies also discovered that the opposite reason, in addition to salary and benefits, for the low motivation of teachers was the low emphasis given by society, student misbehavior, and therefore the inability of the varsity management and administration to effectively address the teachers' demands for supportive and fair leadership.

Moreover, in Hawassa, Getachew and Abebe (2019) conducted a study on work motivation and its effects on organizational performance among public and private hospital nurses. The finding indicated that the majority of nurses were motivated by receiving prospective encouragement, recognition, and financial incentives. These were the most common descriptions given to motivation by the nurses. Increased work performance, job satisfaction, good solidarity, patient satisfaction, and job attachment were the reported effects of nurses' motivation. On the other hand, there is not much research made regarding the impact of motivation on performance (Dinler, 2008). Studies on employee motivation have been carried out in different disciplines in Ethiopia. And also, different researchers were interested in briefly talking about studies of motivation within private institutions. This brings about a great gap that needs to be filled with scientific research because employees in different environments may attain the same level of motivation.

There has been a great challenge for Addis Ababa Police in determining how exactly they can attain human resource management policy for their police employees, whom they believe would go a very long way towards improving organizational performance. Many organizations have tried to attain the motivation of their employees by trying several methods. But methods that were successful in other areas of Ethiopia would be useless in a police organization unless they were supported by scientific evidence. For this reason, the goal of this study is to examine the effect of human resource management policies and practices (person-organization fit, compensation, reward, and recognition, training and career development, challenging employment assignments, and career opportunities) as a means of enhancing the performance of both civil servants and the police force at the Addis Ababa Police Commission's Head Office.

1.3 Objectives of the Study

1.3.1 General Objective

The general objective of this research is to assess the effect of human resource management policy on employee performance in the case of Addis Ababa police commission head office.

1.3.2 Specific Objectives

The specific objectives of this study are:

- To assess the human resource management policy and practices of the Addis Ababa Police Commission.
- To assessing the effect human resource management policy and practices on employee's performance at the Addis Ababa Police Commission look like.

- To examine to what extent human resource management policy and practice affect the employee's performance in the Addis Ababa Police Commission
- To assess the relationship between human resource management policy and practice and employee performance.
- To unify human resource management policy with employee performance for the development of the Addis Ababa Police Commission.

1.4 Research Question

1. How does the human resource policy and practice of the Addis Ababa Police Commission influence the effect of the performance of the human resources department?
2. How does human resource management policy affect employee's performance at the Addis Ababa Police Commission look like?
3. To what extent do human resource management policies and practices affect the employee's performance at the Addis Ababa Police Commission?
4. What is the relationship between human resource management policy and practice and employee performance?
5. What does an employee perceive to unify human resource management policy with employee performance for the development of the Addis Ababa Police Commission?

1.5 Scope and delimitation of the Study

Delimitation [scope] addresses how a study is narrowed in scope, that is, how it is bounded. Limit your delimitations to the things that a reader might reasonably expect

you to do but that you, for clearly explained reasons, have decided not to do (Dawson, 2007).

Even though there are many issues that need research in the Addis Ababa Police Commission, the researcher is selected to investigate the effect of human resource management policy on employee performance because many problems seen in the organization employees are on the human resource management policy problems.

There has been a great challenge for Addis Ababa Police in determining how exactly they can attain human resource management policy for their police employees, whom they believe would go a very long way towards improving organizational performance. Many organizations have tried to attain the motivation of their employees by trying several methods. But methods that were successful in other areas of Ethiopia would be useless in a police organization unless they were supported by scientific evidence. For this reason, the goal of this study is to examine the effect of human resource management policies and practices (person-organization fit, compensation, reward, and recognition, training and career development, challenging employment assignments, and career opportunities) as a means of enhancing the performance of both civil servants and the police force at the Addis Ababa Police Commission's Head Office.

It is practically impossible to address various issues or concepts in the geographical setting of this study. Therefore, this study is defined in terms of concept, time, place, and data. In terms of concept, it focused on the impact of human resource management policy and practice on employee performance. Regarding space and place, this study focuses on the Addis Ababa Police Commission head office. The researcher believes that focusing on a specific area fosters accuracy and better quality of data collection work, considering the accessibility of relevant data and information from the study

area. The time-dimension cross-sectional design was used, which helped the researcher gather data at a particular point in time. This research study has independent variables such as HRM policy and practice (recruitment and selection); training and development; compensation and reward; performance appraisal; and employee performance (as dependent variables). The reasons for the study, as supposed, were to discover the relationship between independent variables and a dependent variable. Finally, the study assessed the practical activities performed from 2010–2015 E.C. by the Addis Ababa Police Commission head office.

1.6 Limitations of the Study

There are many problems with those who tried to constrain the study. Nonetheless, only the major challenges and strategies for coping with them were reported in this dissertation, as indicated below.

Although the research is believed to reach its aims, it has some restrictions; this research is conducted on a small size of population. Therefore, the result may not be applicable to all staff in the organization including branch offices. Furthermore, since a written questionnaire was used to collect information from the respondents willingness of the respondent to fill the questioner and busyness of senior management staff for interview limit the researcher from probing response.

Obtaining key informants who readily showed their willingness to give their time was very tiresome. To solve those problems the reserchers repeated communication (so as to convince them) demanded extra resources (money, time, and energy) during data collection to solve these problems. Moreover, since almost all of the interviewees were leaders, getting their minds out and obtaining genuine information from them still required extreme patience, which made the researcher suffer a lot. To solve those

problems by communicating with human resource management directors and the director gives direct command to other leaders to give time for interview to solve the problems. Some of them refused to participate in a face-to-face interview and asked me to give a written response. In this case the reserche show for them the written letter that written from college to the organization of the study and the organization recive and distiributed for departments of the organization. Still, convincing these individuals also delayed the study time. Actually, a similar problem was faced by a related study (Shahin, 2011) conducted on evaluating the effectiveness of SP in the public sector of Dubai. In this study, after repeated calls by the researcher, all managers (except one) refused the interview. Finally, Shahin reported:

One of the managers who refused to conduct the interview stated over the phone that I cannot share strategic planning information with external entities or individuals since this may reveal information that could affect our chances of winning the Dubai Government Excellence Award. Also I used these methods to solve for those refused to participate in a face-to-face interview and asked me to give a written response.

1.7 Significance of the Study

The study was to investigate the effect of human resource management policy on employee performance, identify its current situation, and recommend the organization based on the findings of its outcomes. For that the benfit of result of this study

For organization it gives a chance to look at their human resource policies and practices in an appropriate style. It also helps the management of the organization in general to identify some of the strengths on the current HRM practice and build up on them while looking also on the gaps to improve them and even members of the human resource

management department in particular to take corrective measures to improve the use of human resource management policies and practices towards achieving their objectives.

For researchers the study will help the researcher to acquire knowledge and practical experience on the subject under study.

For stakeholders the finding of this study is believed to add valuable insights to the existing body of knowledge on the attitude of HRM policy and its practice in organization.

For other researchers this study will serve as a reference material for further investigation for interested researchers and they will get a fresh reference to precede with similar studies in local police organizations.

1.8 Definition of Terms

Effectiveness: getting the desired outcome within defined resources (Malik, Ghafoor, & Naseer, 2011)

Organizational effectiveness is the measure of how successfully organizations achieve their missions through their core strategies (Jamrog, 2005).

Performance is everything about the performance of employees in a firm or a company or an organization (Elnaga & Imran, 2013).

Training: Training refers to bridging the gap between the current performance and the standard desired performance (Garavan T. , 1997)

1.9 Organisation of the Study

This study is organized into five chapters. The first chapter consists of an introduction. This includes the background of the study, the statement of the problem, the objective

of the study, the significance of the study, and the scope of the study. The second chapter presents the theoretical framework, an empirical review of the literature, and the conceptual framework. The third chapter consists of the research methodology and design that were used in the study. It describes the type and design of the research; the population and sampling techniques of the study; the data collection instruments and procedures used to collect data; and the methods of data analysis. The fourth chapter contained data analysis, presentation, and interpretation. Finally, the fifth chapter contained a summary of the findings, a Conclusion, and a recommendation.

1.10 Summary

CHAPTER TWO

2 REVIEW OF LITERATURE

INTRODUCTION

This chapter consists of review of literature on concept of human resource management policy on employee performance. The literature review considered in theoretical and empirical reviews. It focused on the themes of the study which covers the practices of recruitment and selection, performance management, training and development and reward management and their influences on employees' performance.

2.1 The Concept of the effect of human resource management policy

Human resource management (HRM) includes all management decisions and practices that affect the employee of an organization (Bhatt & Reddy, 2011). There have been many definitions of human resource management used by different scholars (Daud, 2006). Defined HRM as a system, policy, and practices that can affect folks that work in an organization, while (Hussain & Ahmad, 2012) considered HRM to be a system that attempts to realize an active balance between the personal interests of people and their economic added value, lastly (Burma, 2014). Viewed HRM is a strategic and clear approach for the organization's most valued assets behind on the employees.

Human resources management is considered to be the most important factor that helps the organization to achieve a competitive advantage. This is due to the fact that managers in both public and private organizations consider human resources to be the main source of sustaining competitive advantage; this is done by having the "best of the best" human resource systems for recruiting, selecting, motivating, and efficiently managing their people Schuler and Jackson (Schuler & Jackson, 2020).

2.1.1 Effect Human Resource Management (EHRM)

The effect is the capability of producing a desired result or the ability to produce desired output. When something is deemed effective, it means it has an intended or expected outcome, or produces a deep, vivid impression (Dictionary.com, 2011).

Effective Human Resource Management is the Center for Effective Organizations' (CEO) sixth report of a fifteen-year study of HR management in today's organizations. The only long-term analysis of its kind, this book compares the findings from CEO's earlier studies to new data collected in 2010. Edward E. Lawler III and John W. Boudreau measure how HR management is changing, paying particular attention to what creates a successful HR function one that contributes to a strategic partnership and overall organizational effectiveness. Moreover, the book identifies best practices in areas such as the design of the HR organization and HR metrics. It clearly points out how the HR function can and should change to meet the future demands of a global and dynamic labor market (Edward & John , 2012).

Organizational effectiveness is a concept organizations use to gauge how effective they are at reaching intended outcomes (Etzioni, 1964) Organizational effectiveness is both a powerful and problematic term. The strength of it is that it may be used to critically evaluate and improve organisational activities.

It's problematic since it means various things to different individuals. And there are other alternative methods for measuring organizational performance (Forbes, 1998). Organizational effectiveness embodies the degree to which firms achieve the goals they have decided upon, a question that draws on several different factors (AIHR, 2022). Among those are talent management, leadership development, organization design and structure, design of measurements and scorecards, implementation of change and

transformation, deploying smart processes and smart technology to manage the firms' human capital and the formulation of the broader Human Resources agenda.

Effectively supporting HR functional and operational contributions showed decreasing associations with overall HR effectiveness between 2004 and 2016, while effectively supporting strategy contributions either held constant at high levels or increased. Notably, effectiveness in every measurement outcome is consistently associated with HR function effectiveness, so it's important to emphasize that more effective measurement supporting HR functional and operational contributions does distinguish effective HR organizations. Still, the notable increase in many of the items reflecting effectiveness of strategy and decision support suggests that HR effectiveness will increasingly associate with these categories (Edward & John , 2012).

2.1.2 Human Resource management policy and practice

Business growth introduction society is increasingly advanced and increases the competitive advantage of every company organization. Companies are expected to increase their productivity so that they can compete with each other nationally and international, and continue to follow the dynamics of changes that occur in society in order to continue to exist in the current market (Mohammadi, 2017). (Aydogan & Arslan, 2021)

So that organizations in the 21st century accelerate the company's innovation, besides that it becomes necessary to analyze the performance of human resource management in the success of a corporate. In some companies, there are often failures in the application of management to employees, the main reason being that they have not been able to implement comprehensive human resource management to achieve organizational goals. This shows that HR management is important in the

sustainability of the organization (Hadji, 2022). Human Resources (HR) is the most important component in a company or organization to run the business it does. Organization must have a goal to be achieved by the organizational members (Niati, Siregar, & Prayoga, 2021). Development is a change towards improvement. Changes towards improvement require the mobilization of all human resources and reason to realize what is aspired (Shah M. M., 2020). The development of human resources is a process of changing the human resources who belong to an organization, from one situation to another, which is better to prepare a future responsibility in achieving organizational goals (Werdhiastutie, 2020).

With the current condition of the organization, it is more dynamic and flexible in which companies not only generate profits but also shape company branding and employee relations in the workplace. Therefore, it is necessary to dig deeper into useful human resource policies and practices in order to attract, motivate, develop and retain employees in the long term (Daft, 2015).

Most HR managers reconfigure human resource policies and practices in order to empower employees to achieve better satisfaction, employee engagement, and organizational culture which are important for organizations to be able to continue their business in line with the times (Aggarwal, , 2020).

Although resource management is widely used in many companies, it reviewed comprehensively in terms of its practices and policies. So that HRM as a system, policy, and practices that can affect folks that work in an organization, while (Hussain & Ahmad, 2012) considered HRM to be a system that attempts to realize an active balance between the personal interests of people and their economic added value, lastly (Burma, 2014). Viewed HRM is a strategic and clear approach for the

organization's most valued assets behind on the employees.

2.1.3 Human resource management policy

The overall HR policy defines how the organization fulfills its social responsibilities to its employees and sets out its attitudes towards them. It is an expression of its values or beliefs about how people should be treated. Peters and Waterman (1982) wrote that if they were asked for one all-purpose bit of advice for management, one truth that they could distil from all their research on what makes an organization excellent, it would be: 'Figure out your value system.. Decide what the organization stands for.' Selznick (1957) emphasized the key role of values in organizations when he wrote: 'The formation of an institution is marked by the making of value commitments, that is, choices which fix the assumptions of policy makers as to the nature of the enterprise, its distinctive aims, methods and roles. 'HR policy, and especially its enactment as HR practice, constitutes an important source of employees' perceptions of fair treatment (Edwards, 2009) Thus, Allen, Shore and Griffeth (2003) argue that supportive HR practices signal management's willingness to invest in, and recognize, employee capabilities, thereby inducing employee affirmation and reciprocity. Hence, the authors' finding is that HR practices (participation in decision-making, fair rewards and development opportunities) contribute to POS that mediates the relationship between HR practices and organizational commitment and job satisfaction. In sum, POS and organizational sociological research (Hodson, 2002) as noted below, argue that management satisfies employees' need for organizational justice that is reciprocated by employees entering into a social exchange relationship and seeking to work more effectively.

2.1.3.1 Purposes of HR policy

The establishment of policies can help an organization demonstrate, both internally and externally, that it meets requirements for diversity, ethics, and training as well as its commitments to regulation and corporate governance of its employees. For example, dismissing an employee by employment law requirements, amongst other considerations, will normally be necessary to meet provisions within employment contracts and collective bargaining agreements (O'Dea, Thomas, 2017). The establishment of an HR Policy that sets out obligations, standards of behavior, and documents disciplinary procedures are now the standard approach to meeting these obligations. HR policies provide frameworks within which consistent decisions are made and promote equity in the way in which people are treated (Armstrong M. , 2001).

HR policies can also be very effective at supporting and building the desired organizational culture (Pain, 2014). For example, recruitment and retention policies might outline the way the organization values a flexible workforce, compensation policies might support this by offering a 48/52 pay option where employees can take an extra four weeks of holidays per year and receive less pay across the year. In developing HR policies, there should be a clear and consistent statement of the organization's policies regarding all conditions of employment and procedures for their equal and fair implementation. To fulfill this objective, policies and procedures should be: (McConnell, John, 2005).

2.1.3.2 Types of HR Policies

There are many policies need to take into consideration but There are nine essential HR policies and procedures for organization:there

1. Anti-Harassment and Non-Discrimination

Anti-discrimination law or non-discrimination law refers to legislation designed to prevent discrimination against particular groups of people; these groups are often referred to as protected groups or protected classes (Levit, 2012). Anti-discrimination laws vary by jurisdiction with regard to the types of discrimination that are prohibited, and also the groups that are protected by that legislation (Springer, 2018). Commonly, these types of legislation are designed to prevent discrimination in employment, housing, education, and other areas of social life, such as public accommodations. Anti-discrimination law may include protections for groups based on sex, age, race, ethnicity, nationality, disability, mental illness or ability, sexual orientation, gender, gender identity/expression, sex characteristics, religion, creed, or individual political opinions.

Anti-discrimination laws are rooted in principles of equality, specifically, that individuals should not be treated differently due to the characteristics outlined above (Holmes, 2005). At the same time, they have often been criticized as violations of the inherent right of free association. Anti-discrimination laws are designed to protect against both individual discrimination (committed by individuals) and from structural discrimination (arising from policies or procedures that disadvantage certain groups) (Seicshnaydre, 2007). Courts may take into account both discriminatory intent and disparate impact in determining whether a particular action or policy constitutes discrimination (Huq, 2017).

2. Recruitment Policy

Recruitment is the overall process of identifying, sourcing, screening, short listing, and interviewing candidates for jobs (either permanent or temporary) within an

organization. Recruitment also is the processes involved in choosing individuals for unpaid roles. Managers, human resource generalists and recruitment specialists may be tasked with carrying out recruitment, but in some cases public-sector employment, commercial recruitment agencies, or specialist search consultancies are used to undertake parts of the process. Internet-based technologies which support all aspects of recruitment have become widespread, including the use of artificial intelligence (AI). (Sulich, 2016)

According to Proclamation to provide for the establishment of the Ethiopian federal police commission Article fourteen the Commission shall recruit, train, employ and administer police officers in accordance with regulations to be issued by the Council of Ministers and also The Commission shall employ and administer the necessary support staff in accordance with the federal civil service laws (Proclamation No. 720, 2011).

3. Leave and time off benefits

Depending on country and/or state, your entitlements to time off will be different. In Ethiopia Employees are entitled to no less than 14 working days of annual leave for the first one year of service, and 14 working days plus one working day for every additional year of service (Travail Legal Database: , 2014). Every employee is also entitled to 13 paid public holidays (Wage Indicator" (PDF)., 2016).

According to Regulation No. 268/2012 Article 31 of federal police commission the duration of Annual Leave A police officer who has served for one year shall be entitled to 20 working days of annual leave, A police officer who has served for more than one year shall be entitled to one working day additional leave for each year of service; provided, however, that the total number of days of annual leave may not exceed thirty

working days and A service rendered in another government office shall be considered for computation of leave in accordance with this Article.

4. Meal and break periods

A break at work (or work-break) is a period of time during a shift in which an employee is allowed to take time off from their job. It is a type of downtime. There are different types of breaks, and depending on the length and the employer's policies, the break may or may not be paid.

Meal breaks, tea breaks, coffee breaks, or lunch breaks usually range from ten minutes to one hour. Their purpose is to allow the employee to have a meal that is regularly scheduled during the work day. For a typical daytime job, this is lunch, but this may vary for those with other work hours. Lunch breaks allow an employee's energy to replenish (Sianoja, Kinnunen, De Bloom, Korpela, & Geurts, 2016). It is not uncommon for this break to be unpaid, and for the entire work day from start to finish to be longer than the number of hours paid in order to accommodate this time.

5. Employee Conduct Policy

A code of conduct is a set of rules outlining the norms, rules, and responsibilities or proper practices of an individual party or an organization.

A company code of conduct is a set of rules which is commonly written for employees of a company, which protects the business and informs the employees of the company's expectations. It is appropriate for even the smallest of companies to create a document containing important information on expectations for employees ("Building a compliance department", 2022). The document does not need to be complex or have elaborate policies.

A code of conduct can be an important part in establishing an inclusive culture, but it is not a comprehensive solution on its own. An ethical culture is created by the organization's leaders who manifest their ethics in their attitudes and behavior (McMillan, 2016). Studies of codes of conduct in the private sector show that their effective implementation must be part of a learning process that requires training, consistent enforcement and continuous measurement improvement (Doig & Wilson, 1998). Simply requiring members to read the code is not enough to ensure that they understand it and will remember its contents (ACC., 2016). The proof of effectiveness is when employees/members feel comfortable enough to voice concerns and believe that the organization will respond with appropriate action (Barman & White, 2016).

6. Employee Safety Policy

Employee safety policies vary greatly depending on your organization and the kind of work it carries out. The employee safety policy of a factory would be very different from that of a travel agency, for example.

A workplace is a location where someone works, for their employer or themselves, a place of employment. Such a place can range from a home office to a large office building or factory. For industrialized societies, the workplace is one of the most important social spaces other than the home, constituting "a central concept for several entities: the worker and [their] family, the employing organization, the customers of the organization, and the society as a whole" (Paul Jackson, 2004). The development of new communication technologies has led to the development of the virtual workplace and remote work. The Workplace Safety and Health Act 2006 is an act issued by the Republic of Singapore. It addresses requirements for safety and health in workplaces, and replaced the Factories Act as of 1 March 2006.

According to Regulation No. 268/2012 Article 24 of federal police commission the Commission shall conduct and submit to the Ministry studies on the types and amounts of ration, allowances and other benefits and implement same upon approval by the government; Any allowance or benefit may be given to police officers if it is necessary to effectively carry out the functions of the Commission and Police officers having the same rank and level of responsibility shall receive the same amount of allowance and benefit.

According to Regulation No. 268/2012 Article 42 of federal police commission the Commission shall provide housing, transport, water and electric power supply services to police officers to the extent possible; Police officers who have to be stationed at camps due to the nature of their duties shall be provided, free of charge, with dwelling units and the supply of water and electricity and The provision of housing and supply of water and electricity to a police officer shall cease following termination of his service provided.

7. Social Media Policy

A social media policy is a policy which advises representatives of an organization on their use of social media. Various businesses have social media policies (Council, 2017). You should also have strict rules regarding posts about the workplace – it's not uncommon for disgruntled employees to get fired about complaining about their job/boss/employer publicly on Twitter or Face book. Various health care organizations have social media policies (Barton & Skiba, 2012). Government use of social media has special considerations (Mergel & Bretschneider, 2013). Libraries can have social media policies. Athletic programs can have social media policies (Sanderson, 2011).

There has been social media policy research in Sweden (Disciplining social media, 2012).

8. Privacy Policy

A privacy policy is a statement or legal document (in privacy law) that discloses some or all of the ways a party gathers, uses, discloses, and manages a customer or client's data (Costante, Sun, Petković, & den, 2012). Personal information can be anything that can be used to identify an individual, not limited to the person's name, address, date of birth, marital status, contact information, ID issue, and expiry date, financial records, credit information, medical history, where one travels, and intentions to acquire goods and services (McCormick, 2011). In the case of a business, it is often a statement that declares a party's policy on how it collects, stores, and releases personal information it collects. It informs the client what specific information is collected, and whether it is kept confidential, shared with partners, or sold to other firms or enterprises (Web finance, 2011). Privacy policies typically represent a broader, more generalized treatment, as opposed to data use statements, which tend to be more detailed and specific.

9. Disciplinary and Termination Policies

Termination of employment or separation of employment is an employee's departure from a job and the end of an employee's duration with an employer. Termination may be voluntary on the employee's part, or it may be at the hands of the employer, often in the form of dismissal (firing) or a layoff. Dismissal or firing is usually thought to be the employee's fault, whereas a layoff is generally done for business reasons (for instance, a business slowdown or an economic downturn) outside the employee's performance.

Firing carries a stigma in many cultures and may hinder the jobseeker's chances of finding new employment, particularly if they have been terminated from a previous job. Jobseekers sometimes do not mention jobs from which they were fired on their resumes; accordingly, unexplained gaps in employment, and refusal or failure to contact previous employers are often regarded as "red flags" (Reasons Employees Get Fired, 2013).

According to Regulation No. 268/2012 Article 67 of federal police commission the service of any police officer shall be terminated upon final decision of penalty imposing dismissal on the ground of disciplinary charge involving grave disciplinary offence in accordance with the relevant provisions of this Regulation.

2.1.4 Human Resources Management Practices

Human resource management (HRM) practices are a set of internally consistent policies and practices designed and implemented to ensure that a firm's human capital contribute to the achievement of its business objectives (Delery and Doty, 1996)

The importance of linking HRM practices and the competitive strategy of firms; strategy-based innovation needs to be created via mid-level people who take the initiative for change and solve problems with new ideas. They referred that some new HRM practices that have a wide generalization and are not entirely new but have reappeared lately. De Miranda Castro, (2020) Considered the horizontal directness among the several human resource practices to business administration leads to good quality of working life and more alignment between HR subsystems and the strategy of organizations, Foss and Lyngsie (2011) give the following reasons for engaging in HRM practices: First, to assign duties to employees and teams; second, to develop

and publicize incentives for knowledge sharing, individual achievements, and benefit sharing; third, as a medium for intra-organization information sharing about practices like job rotation and knowledge sharing; fourth, to generate internal and external training opportunities for employees; and last, to carry out retention, recruitment, and promotion policies to fulfill the organization's HR needs. The last two of these tasks are considered part of conventional HRM practice, whereas the first three are more modern HRM roles (Teece, 2007).

Past research has discussed these practices in the perspective of VRIN ("valuable, rare, imperfectly imitable and non-substitutable") resources, arguing that these qualities of human resources contribute to SOP. (Adam, M, 2018). This means that HRM implementations are becoming critical to organizations. Management personnel are taking a keen interest in their organization's ability to exercise HRM practices to positively shape the working conduct of employees and fully utilize their capacity to deliver innovative business processes, help to meet organizational objectives, and ultimately realize SOP (Chen & Huang, 2009).

Therefore, the authors believe that HRM practices play a dual role in organization. On the one hand, HRM practices and policies are used to manage and to organize the work, incorporating the organization's basic structure. HRM practices and policies serve to manage and employ people by incorporating individual administration tasks and the development of new procedures, either in consultation with or communicated to individuals and teams within the organization (Boxall & Purcell, 2011). On the other hand, diverse HRM implementations can also be viewed as significant to support and stimulate creativity, primarily by empowering the sovereignty of workers and consequently giving rise to novel procedures (Bratton & Gold, 2017). With this dual

role of HRM practices in mind, it is not just a question of managing work and representing business structures, there is also the potential for HRM to unlock the imagination of personnel. Therefore, it is conceivable that HRM practices and policies could be utilized to bring about innovativeness and thus create an innovation-driven path toward organization (Jiang, Lepak, Baer, & Hu, 2012).

There is no agreement on what constitutes HRM practices let alone a prescribed set of them (Boxall, P; Purcell, J; Wright, P, 2007). Researchers have over the years proposed countless and varied lists of practices; however, there is no agreement on what or which practice qualifies as an aspect of Human Resource Management (Beer, Spector, Lawrence, Mills, & Walton, 2005) It is interesting to note that there are still some practices that form the core of the various practices proposed.

HRM Practices are the policy which are been done by the organization for having optimum utilization of human resource. HR Practices are based on policies of the organization. How the policy are used in the organization by the These HR policies are developed in the all Human Resource areas like recruitment and selection, training and development, Performance Appraisal and Reward and Compensation (Arul , 2017).

2.1.4.1 Recruitment and Selection

According to Beardwell et al. (2004) the recruitment and selection process is concerned with identifying, attracting and choosing suitable people to meet an organizations human resource requirement. Ensuring that the right people are in the right place at the right time is a critical factor in gaining and maintaining competitive advantage. Recruitment and selection have always been crucial processes for organizations.

They are integrated activities. (Bratton and Gold 2007) refers to recruitment as “the process of generating a pool of capable people to apply to an organization for employment. Selection is the process by which managers and other use specific instruments to choose from a pool of applicants the person or persons most likely to succeed in the job, given management goals and legal requirements”. Recruitment and selection represent the entry point activities. Recruiting procedures and selection regimes will have an influence over the quality and type of skills new employees possess.

Recruitment and selection involves two interrelated processes, recruitment is the process of generating a pool of capable people to apply for employment to an organization while selection is the process by which specific instruments are employed to choose from a pool of applicant’s persons most suitable for the job taking into consideration management goals and legal requirements (Gold & Bratton, 2003). It is the process of finding and engaging the people the organization needs. Selection is that part of the recruitment process concerned with deciding which applicants or candidates should be appointed to jobs (Armstrong & Gerber, 2016).

Mahapatro (2010), the objectives of recruitment to attract people with multi-dimensional skills and experiences that suit the present and future organizational strategies, to induct outsiders with a new perspective to lead the company, to infuse fresh blood at all levels of the organization, to develop an organizational culture that attracts competent people to the company, to search or head hunt people whose skills fit the company’s values, to devise methodologies for assessing psychological traits, to seek out non-conventional development grounds of talent, to search for talent globally

and not just within the company, to design entry salary that competes on quality but not on quantum and to anticipate and find people for positions that does not exist yet.

2.1.4.1.1 Goals of Recruitment

There are mainly two goals of recruitment

1. Attracting candidates

The first step in attracting candidates is to analyze recruitment strengths and weaknesses. The outcome of this analysis can be used to develop an employee value proposition and employer brand. The general purpose of recruitment according to (Gamage, 2014) is to provide the organization with a pool of potentially qualified job candidates. The quality of human resource in an organization highly depends on the quality of applicants attracted because organization is going to select employees from those who were attracted. In the same vein, Henry and Temtime (2009) construed recruitment as the entry point of manpower into an organization and the path an organization must follow from there on in order to make sure that they have attracted the right individuals for their culture and atmosphere so that the overall strategic goals are achieved.

2. To discourage non-qualified Applicants

When recruiting is based upon careful designing of the job description and job specification most of the applicants having irrelevant qualifications are eliminated from the list of potential applicants which makes recruiting process more effective and easier.

2.1.4.1.2 Recruitment Methods

According to Sims, (2002) A numbers of methods may be used to recruit applicants. To decide which method to use, the organization should know which are most likely to attract potential employees. The recruitment methods refer to the ways of establishing contacts with potential job seekers. Those methods can be broadly classified into three categories: Direct, Indirect, and Third party.

2.1.4.1.2.1 Direct Methods of Recruitment

The most frequently used direct method is at schools, colleges, educational and training institutes. The representatives of the organization are sent to establish contacts with the prospective candidates. Usually, employer firms work in cooperation with placement bureaus of educational institutions or contact professors directly to gather information about students with outstanding academic records. This method is low-cost and attracts numerous applicants at a short period of time. Other direct methods include establishing exhibits at job fairs, shopping centers and rural areas where unemployed people may be contacted (Sarma, 2008).

2.1.4.1.2.2 Indirect Methods of Recruitment

Indirect methods include the use of advertisements in newspapers, magazines, various professional journals, on the radio and television and various notice-boards. As it was stated earlier, an advertisement should be brief, catchy and comprehensive to make the potential candidate interested in the vacancy. In addition, a carefully prepared and worded sound advertisement can help in building a good image of an organization. The indirect method is useful when there are no suitable candidates to be promoted within the company; the organization is aiming at reaching out a vast territory; or a very specific specialist is needed. (Sarma 2008).

2.1.4.1.2.3 Third Party Methods of Recruitment

Third Party Methods include the use of public and private employment agencies, management consultants, trade unions, employee referral, voluntary organizations and various data banks.

They are typically used for recruiting candidates for the positions that are difficult to fulfill or for candidates from a specific working field. (Sarma 2008). The most frequently used third-party methods are public and private employment agencies.

2.1.4.1.3 Recruitment and Selection Criteria

Reasonable criteria for the choice must be set prior to selection. If a selection program is to be successful, the employee characteristics believed necessary for effective performance on the job should be stated explicitly in the job specification. The criteria usually can be summarized in several categories: Formal education, experience, physical characteristics and personal characteristics (Ivancevich, 2004). The criteria for selection are affected by the nature of the employee, the task and the supervisor employee attitudes and preferences, abilities and altitudes required will vary with the task.

1. Formal education: An employer selecting from a pool of job applicants wants to find the person who has the right abilities and attitudes to be successful. Most employees attempt to serene for abilities by specifying educational accomplishments. Employers tend to specify as a criterion a specific amount (in years) of formal education and types of education
 - Formal education can indicate ability or skills present

- Most employers“ attempt to screen for abilities by specifying educational accomplishment.
 - The educational criteria must be validated against job performance.
2. Experience: One way to measure experience within the organization is to provide each employee with a seniority rating, which indicates the length of time he or she has been employed in the organization. Employers often equate experience with ability, as well as with attitude, reasoning that a prospect who has performed the job before and is applying for a similar job likes the work and will do it well (Ivancevich, 2004).
 3. Physical characteristics: There are some tasks that require certain physical characteristics, usually stamina and strength, which can be tested. Candidates cannot legally be screened but by arbitrary height, weight and similar requirements.
 4. Personal characteristics: It catches all categories, including
 - Marital status: some prefer stable married people it leads to lower turnover and higher performance. Some prefer divorced or single persons. They are willing to be transferred or to work weekends.
 - Discrimination in selection based on marital status is illegal in some places, and unless an organization has data to support the relation of this criterion to performance, it makes sense
 - Any age criteria should be examined by saying how it relates to present successful employees.

Generally, this category is extremely difficult factor to measure and consequently it is seldom used as a formal factor.

2.1.4.2 Training and development

Training and development is considered to be the most common human resources practice (Tzafrir, 2006). Training and development refers to any effort to improve current or future employees' skills, abilities, and knowledge (Ashwathappa, 2006). Training and development constitute an ongoing process in any organization. "Training is the formal and systematic modification of behavior through learning which occurs as a result of education, development and planned experience (Armstrong, M, 2001). In contrast, staff development refers to the development of supporting, technical and professional staff in organizations, such as local authorities, in which such staff form a large proportion of those employed. Its aim is to enable such employees to perform their current and future role effectively (Collin, 2001).

Furthermore, it helps employees to identify organization goals and mission, helps not only managing change but also developing positive culture in the organization, which in turn may lead to providing higher level of service to stakeholders (Armstrong, 2001). On the other hand human resource development (HRD) acts as a triggering mechanism for the progression of other HRM policies that are aimed at recruiting, retaining and rewarding employees, who are recognized as the qualitative difference between organizations. The investment in employee learning is a way of creating a primary internal market, and policies aimed at upgrading skill reduce an organization's dependency on external source of skill (Bratton and Gold, 2007)

Training is the most basic function of human resources management. It is the systematic application of formal processes to help people to acquire the knowledge and skills necessary for them to perform their jobs satisfactorily (Armstrong M. , Handbook of human resource management practice. Kogan Page, 2020). These activities have

become widespread human resource management practices in organizations worldwide (Hughes, Zajac, Woods, & Salas, 2019). In today's business world, training is the main strategy to perform the institutional objectives. It helps to improve employee and employer performance (Ruttledge & Cathcart, 2019). Employees are the most precious asset for any organization in building up or destroying its reputation and profitability (Elnaga, A; Imran, A, 2013). Some of the factors that determine the performance of employees are training of employees, organizational policies, working situations, job satisfaction, interactions with in the organization (Aktar, Sachu, & Ali, 2012). Thus, training is one of the most effective tools to enhance the employee performance and to achieve the organizational objectives and goals effectively and efficiently (Garavan, McCarthy, & Carbery, 2020).

Training is consists of an organization's planned efforts to help employees acquire job-related knowledge, skills, abilities, and behaviors, with the goal of applying on the job (Noe & Hollenbeck, 2019). Training is the systematic modification of behavior through learning processes, which enable individuals to upgrade the levels of knowledge, practice, and qualification needed to carry out their tasks efficiently. It improves the performance of both employees and employers (Khan, Khan, & Khan, 2011). In addition, according to (Khan, Abbasi, Waseem, Ayaz, & Ijaz, 2016) training helps the workforce adapt flawlessly to new technology thereby increasing the efficiency and productivity of individuals and organizations.

As cited on (Abeeha & Bariha, 2012) while considering a training process it is essential to know who is to be trained, the method and program of training and also whether the main goals of the trainings are being achieved or not. Formal training is indeed only one of the ways of ensuring that learning takes place (Armstrong, M, 2014).

2.1.4.2.1 Methods of training

1. On-the-job training Methods:

According to Greer (2003) under these methods new or inexperienced employees learn through observing peers or managers performing the job and trying to imitate their behavior. These methods do not cost much and are less disruptive as employees are always on the job, training is given on the same machines and experience would be on already approved standards, and above all the trainee is learning while earning.

Some of the commonly used methods are:

1. Coaching: Coaching is a one-to-one training. It helps in quickly identifying the weak areas and tries to focus on them. It also offers the benefit of transferring theory learning to practice. The biggest problem is that it perpetrates the existing practices and styles (Dessler & Varkkey, 2010).

2. Mentoring: The focus in this training is on the development of attitude. It is used for managerial employees. Mentoring is always done by a senior inside person. It is also one-to- one interaction, like coaching (Dessler & Varkkey, 2010).

3. Job Rotation: In which an employee moves from job to job at planned interval to broaden their understanding of all parts of the business and to test their abilities (Dessler & Varkkey, 2010)

4. Apprenticeship: Is a process by which people become skilled workers, usually through a combination of formal learning and long term on the job training (Dessler G. , A Framework for Human Resources Management. Prentice-Hall, 2005)

2. Off-the-job Training Methods Off-the-job training methods are conducted in separate from the job environment, study material is supplied, there is full concentration on

learning rather than performing, and there is freedom of expression (Geer, 2003).

Important methods include:

According to Regulation No. 268/2012 there are on Job or Off Job Education and Training for police officers. Any police officers shall be given on job or off job education and training which qualifies him for the duty he is assigned for. The police officer shall be obliged to serve for a period equivalent to the time he spent for attending on job education and training or for a period equivalent to double through he has spent for attending of education of training.

2.1.4.2.2 Types of off the job training

1. Classroom Lectures and Seminars:- Traditional forms of instruction revolve around formal lecture courses and seminars. These help individuals acquire knowledge and develop their conceptual and analytical abilities. Many Organizations offer these in- house, through outside vendors, or both (Decenzo & Robbins, 2010).
2. Simulated training (Vestibule training):- is a method in which trainees learn on the actual or simulated equipment they will use on the job, but are actually trained off the job. It is necessary when it's too costly or dangerous to train employees' on the job (Dessler & Varkkey, 2010).
3. Multimedia Learning:- can demonstrate technical skills not easily presented by other training methods. This may include videos and DVDs that may be offered online (Decenzo & Robbins, 2010).

2.1.4.2.3 Training and Development Process

The typical first step in designing any training program would be identification of training needs (Goldstein & Ford, 2002). This step normally includes analysis of tasks

and personnel so that gaps would be determined through an analysis of organizational needs. Following needs assessment, it is important to specify objectives of training (Reed & Vakola, 2006). The overall purpose of training is to increase organizational effectiveness through increased productivity, improved quality, better human resource planning, higher morale, better health and safety, prevention of obsolescence and enhanced personal growth. The third typical step is organizational set-up for training (Salas, Wilson, Priest, & Guthrie, 2006). In this step, organization is to decide if it will have its own training center or to outsource training. Away from typical debate about advantages and disadvantages of both methods, organizations need to take into considerations the support of the top management to, amount of investment, volume, continuity, flexibility and privacy desired in a training program (Tannenbaum, 2002).

2.1.4.2.4 Reasons for Carrying out Training and Development

Employers do not regularly consider the feelings of their employees regarding skills development. Accordingly, Frost, Vos and Dreyer (2003) claim that the traditional business organization is closely modeled on the military style of management, probably because armies are the largest and almost certainly the oldest human organizations in response to this, Katcher and Snyder (2003) identify some of the reasons why employers need their employees to continuously learn new skills:

I) Capital improvement: Organizations tend to spend millions of rants on upgrading their plants and equipment, yet little on upgrading their human capital. Employees are an asset to the organization but employers are more concerned about reaching deadlines and profit maximization rather than employees skills development, without which employee performance could be hampered. Although the organization still achieves productivity, the focus should also be on the dedication, commitment and loyalty of

employees. If employees do not receive ongoing training, up-to-date equipment will not be used optimally.

ii) Morale improvement. Employees who continuously upgrade their job skills will also improve their productivity. Developing employee skills not only plays a role in the workplace, but in the external world as well. It contributes to the full personal development of each employee and the socio-economic development of the nation at large; therefore, happy employees may be productive, but more productive employees are happier.

iii) Ability to adapt to change. The more skilled the workforce is, the easier it will be for the entire organization to adapt to changes that may arise in the domestic and global market place in the demand of its products and services. Sometimes employees are reluctant to adapt to change because of the uncertainty involved.

Armstrong (2006) summarizes that human resources development empowers employees of organization to increase their contribution to its success while enabling them to build their skills and capabilities simultaneously. Lastly, Training is also important in the health and safety at workplaces because professional employees are very familiar with dangers related to their work and therefore makes possible efforts to limit those dangers.

The objective of promotion in assignment to a position the police officer shall be to staff the Commission with the necessary manpower at all ranks and positions and to motivate police officers and thereby improve performance of the Commission.

2.1.4.3 Performance appraisal

Performance appraisal (PA) is a systematic process to evaluate the performance of an employee after certain period. Performance appraisal also influences other human resources practices such as recruitment and selection, training and development, rewards and incentives, and employee relations. According Armstrong, (2001).

Performance Appraisal means evaluating an employee's current and/or past performance relative to his or her performance standards. The PA process contains three steps: define the job, appraise performance, and provide feedback. Defining the job means making sure that the supervisor and the subordinate agree on his or her duties and job standards. Appraising performance means comparing the subordinate's actual performance to the standards that have been set. Third, PA usually requires one or more feedback sessions. Here the supervisor and subordinate discuss the subordinate's performance and progress and make plans for any development required Dessler, (2008).

PA should be transparent because the evaluation motivates employees to work more in order to achieve the organizational objectives. PA includes a communication occasion planned between a manager and an employee for the main purpose of assessing that employee's previous performance and establishing ways for further improvement. In line with this, Armstrong M. (2009) has explained that the goal of PA is to create a two-way communication, helps decision making and create motivation. In this regard, a two way communication between manager and employee in away management uses this process to clearly state what is expected from employees, how they have performed towards attaining the set goals, and what needs to be improved for better performance. Meanwhile employees take the opportunity to state the support they require from the

organization in order for them to achieve the goals, what worked for them, what needs to be improved from the management side for future. Management uses the information gathered through annual PAs to make administrative decisions concerning the workforce such as pay raises, promotions, demotions, training and development, and termination. Valid and reliable information concerning each individual employee enables management to make decisions which enhances the productivity of employees.

It is concerned with performance improvement, employee development, satisfying the needs and expectations of all the organization's stake holders-owners, management, employees, customers, suppliers and the community. As performance appraisal leads to pay raise, promotion, and training; it is assumed that better performance appraisal can have impact on organizational performance.

A performance appraisal, also referred to as a performance review, performance evaluation (Muchinsky, 2012), (career) development discussion, or employee appraisal, sometimes shortened to "PA", is a periodic and systematic process whereby the job performance of an employee is documented and evaluated. This is done after employees are trained about work and settle into their jobs. Performance appraisals are a part of career development and consist of regular reviews of employee performance within organizations.

Performance appraisals are most often conducted by an employee's immediate manager or line manager (Tyskbo, 2020). While extensively practiced, annual performance reviews have also been criticized. As providing feedback too infrequently to be useful, and some critics argue that performance reviews in general do more harm than good. It is an element of the principal-agent framework, that describes the relationship of

information between the employer and employee, and in this case the direct effect and response received when a performance review is conducted (Evans & Tourish, 2017).

2.1.4.4 Reward and Compensation

Reward and compensation management is a concept that conveys the signal to the employees that are being appreciated in the organization (Shoaib, Noor, Tirmizi, & Bashir, 2009). Armstrong and Taylor (Armstrong, M; Taylor, S, 2014) in his seminal work designated that “reward management deals with the strategies, policies and processes required to safeguard that the value of people and the contribution they make to achieving organizational, departmental and team goals is recognized and rewarded”. Whilst discussing the characteristics of reward management Armstrong indicated that reward management includes developmental and application relating areas of reward system that is a mean to achieve organizational targets. Similarly, Bratton and Gold mentioned that reward management is “central to the regulation of the employment relationship and is one of the central pillars of human resource management in a different study added to the meaning of reward management by signifying that the ultimate aim of reward management is to enable organization to achieve its strategic goals (Bratton, J; Gold, J, 2001).

Generally reward practices enable organization to answer two questions, (i) where do we want our reward practices to be in a few years” time? & (ii) how do we intend to get there? (Armstrong, M; Stephens, T, 2005). Similarly (Armstrong, M; Brown, D, 2001). suggested that reward management of an organization “deals with both ends and means”. Putting simply a comprehensive reward strategy defines the purposes of the reward programs, their components, and how they allied to accomplish organizational objectives. Kaplan in the same vein came up with the ability of reward strategy to

define the philosophy behind the programs, which as a result offers the basis for future plan design (Kaplan & Denno, 2007). Armstrong and Murlis, earlier arguments appear in line with the recent description of reward strategy, he mentioned that “a business focused statement of the intention of the organization concerning the development of future reward processes and practices which are aligned to the business and human resource strategies of the organization, its culture, and environment in which it operates” (Armstrong, M; Murlis, H, 2007). That is why Wilson, regards reward strategies as a process by which an organization interprets its competitive business strategy into a sequence of programs and initiatives that will have an encouraging influence on human behavior (Propper & Wilson, 2003).

Non-financial Rewards Researchers like Daniel (2009) showed their apprehensions about financial rewards. Polemics of financial rewards pointed towards the negative effect of financial rewards like decrease in intrinsic motivation as it can cause short term thinking and more frauds (Morrell, 2011). Morrell (2011) additionally added that significance of both financial and nonfinancial rewards are imperative as there are diverse jobs in the industry where one kind of reward does not accomplish the purpose. The early findings of Drucker Peter (1954) about the significance of rewards are consistent with (Aizza , Shakeel, & Hassan, (2018).) Drucker Peter suggested that workers or managers, in business or outside needs reward for pride and prestige. Further upheld that financial benefits are not single major sources of optimistic motivation even though dissatisfaction with them inhibits performance conversely, nonfinancial incentives cannot compensate for displeasure with economic rewards (Drucker, 2012). Whilst proposing ingredients of effective performance Jensen, McMullen, and Stark (2007) regards non-financial rewards as crucial in helping an

organization stand out as a top employer, and also have the dual impact of increasing engagement among employees. Similarly, Brewster and Mayrhofer (2012) highlighted the importance of nonfinancial rewards by revealing their role in the enhancement of job satisfaction of employees, their commitment and performance. Scott, Yeld, & Hendry, (2007) termed nonfinancial rewards as a vehicle to develop the value of reward programs to justify significance employees give to nonfinancial rewards.

The term 'reward' is discussed frequently in the literature as something that the organization gives to the employees in response of their contributions and performance and also something which is desired by the employees (Adebaby , 1998). In the context of managing people, the reward and incentive system underlines a core feature of the employment relationship. According to Bratton and Gold (2007). "Reward refers to all the financial, non- financial and psychological payments that an organization gives for its employees in exchange for the work they perform." Reward practices engendering debate among academics and organizational leaders on the role that it plays in achieving substantive employee behaviors like task performance, flexibility, quality and commitment. It is also argued that the design and management of reward systems holds one of the most difficult HRM tasks for general manager. Compensation refers to all types of pay or rewards going to employees and arising from their employment (Dessler G. , 2007).

2.1.4.4.1 Types of Rewards

Performance management can play an important part in a total reward system in which each reward element is linked together and treated as an integrated and coherent whole. These elements comprise base pay, contingent pay, employee benefits, and non-

financial rewards, which include intrinsic rewards from the work itself (Armstrong, 2006).

According to Armstrong (2010), rewards can be seen broadly from two perspectives:

1. Financial Rewards

Financial rewards comprise all rewards that have a monetary value and add up to total remuneration base pay, pay contingent on performance, contribution, competency or skill, pay related to service, financial recognition schemes, and benefits such as pensions, sick pay and health insurance.

2. Non-Financial Rewards

Non-financial rewards are those that focus on the needs people have to varying degrees for recognition, achievement, responsibility, autonomy, influence and personal growth. They incorporate the notion of relational rewards, which are the intangible rewards concerned with the work environment (quality of working life, the work itself, work–life balance), recognition, performance management, and learning and development.

Increasing motivation and raising levels of commitment and engagement are key organizational imperatives. The development of reward management policies, structures and practices will be underpinned by assumptions about how people can best be motivated to deliver high levels of performances, discretionary effort and contribution. These assumptions may not be articulated but the reward philosophies and policies of an organization can be no better than the motivational theories and beliefs upon which they are based (Armstrong, Michael ; Murlis, Helen, 2004).

2.1.4.4.2 Total Rewards

According to WorldatWork (2007) total rewards can be defined as all of the employer's available tools that may be used to attract, motivate, and retain employees. This encompasses every single investment that a company makes in its people and everything its employees value in the employment relationship. A total reward is the monetary and nonmonetary return provided to employees in exchange for their time, talents, efforts, and results. It involves the deliberate integration of five key elements that effectively attract, motivate, and retain the talent required to achieve desired business results. The five key rewards elements are:

A. Compensation- Pay provided by an employer to an employee for services rendered (i.e., time, effort, and skill). Includes both fixed and variable pay tied to levels of performance.

B. Benefits-Programs an employer uses to supplement the cash compensation that employees receive. These health, income protection, savings, and retirement programs provide security for employees and their families.

C. Work-Life-A specific set of organizational practices, policies, and programs plus a philosophy that actively supports efforts to help employees achieve success at both work and home.

D. Performance and Recognition-

a) Performance: The alignment of organizational, team, and individual efforts toward the achievement of business goals and organizational success. It includes establishing expectations, skill demonstration, assessment, feedback, and continuous improvement.

b) Recognition: Acknowledges or gives special attention to employee actions, efforts, behavior, or performance. It meets an intrinsic psychological need for appreciation for one's efforts and can support business strategy by reinforcing certain behaviors (e.g., extraordinary accomplishments) that contribute to organizational success.

E. Development and Career Opportunities-

a) Development: A set of learning experiences designed to enhance employees' applied skills and competencies. Development engages employees to perform better and engages leaders to advance their organizations' people strategies.

b) Career opportunities: A plan for employees to advance their career goals. May include advancement into a more responsible position in an organization (WorldatWork, 2007).

According to Armstrong (2010), the concept of total rewards describes an approach to reward management which emphasizes the need to consider all aspects of the work experience of value to employees, not just a few such as pay and employee benefits. It aims to blend the financial and non-financial elements of reward into a cohesive whole. It is a holistic view of reward which looks at the overall reward system in order to determine how its elements should be integrated so that they provide mutual support in contributing to the overall effectiveness of the system. The concept of total rewards combines the impact of the two major categories of reward as defined below:

i. Transactional rewards: tangible (financial) rewards arising from transactions between the employer and employees concerning pay and benefits. These are all extrinsic.

ii. Relational rewards: intangible (non-financial) rewards concerned with the work environment (quality of working life, the work itself, work–life balance), recognition, performance management and learning and development.

2.1.5 Employee's performance

Companies and organizations should focus on building employees positive performance, through providing employees with a group of tools and skills to meet out new realities and challenges (Batarlienė, Čižiūnienė, Vaičiūtė, & Šapa, 2017). Globalization, new market demands, innovation and smart economy are considering a challenge, as well as, drivers for companies to maintain and improve employee performance (Cooper & Ezzamel, 2013). Dealing with quick changes in technologies, stakeholders' requirements and market demands are depending on reducing the gap within employees' attitude as underpinning factor on achieving smart goals of the organization (Shah, Irani, & Sharif, 2017). Researchers have defined employee performance as well as highlighted parameters affecting employee performance as in the following. Anitha (2013) reports that the performance of an individual or an organization depends strongly on all organizational activities, policies, practices, knowledge management practices and employee engagement. These elements are vital determinants fostering high levels of employee performance. While (Islami, Mulolli, & Mustafa, 2018).recognize managing performance as a planned process of which the key elements are agreement, measurement, support, feedback and positive reinforcement, which shaped outcomes in terms of performance expectation. Also, (Bataineh, 2017) highlight Employee's performance as a combination of efficiency and effectiveness of the employee's daily tasks to meet the expectations of the stakeholders (Isaac, Abdullah, Ramayah, & Mutahar, 2017). Show that employees highly agree that

implementing the internet in their job helped them in improving task process, education acquisition and the quality of their communication which lead to improving individual performance as well as organization. On the other hand, (Pawirosumarto, Sarjana, & Gunawan, 2017). Tide between employee performance and work environment that contains physical and non- physical factors around employees which have a positive and significant effect on improving employee performance. While (Smith & Bititci, 2017). Emphasis on improving performance measurement systems and performance management practices as factors of work's environment which enhance employee's engagement levels. Also, (Mensah, 2018)support their ideas when considered talent management as a critical success factor within companies which become the most core managerial value in our highly dynamic and uncertain market environment of the twenty-first-century era. Based on these observations, this paper aims to enhance the understood of employee performance and the factors affecting it. Author proposing a conceptual model, consisting of five factors which are knowledge management, information and communication technology, employee's empowerment, innovation and creativity and organization culture (de Menezes & Escrig, 2019)

2.1.6 Relationship between HRMPP with Employee's performance

An organization that performs HRMP such as Recruitment and selection, Training and development and Performance appraisal and Reward management system is able to achieve goals and develop strategies effectively and flexibly and is also able to implement policies within the organization, HRMP is consistent with internal policies and methods established and applied to ensure the organization's human resources contribute to achieving the organization's goals, coming up with solutions for developing human to help improve the ability, opportunity, and motivation of

employees (Nguyen, Ha, & Dang, 2020). HRMP and their implementation are among the most important factors that contribute to increasing employee satisfaction and achieving job commitment, which contributes to raising productivity (Khan M. , 2010) (Quresh, Akbar, Khan, Sheikh, & Hijazi, 2010).

HRMP is an important predictor of organizational performance and has the potential to promote organizational innovation. Effect HRMP such as including sophisticated methods to recruitment and selection, orientation, appraisal, and training envisage organizational innovation in products and services (Shipton, Fay, West, Patterson, & Birdi, 2005). In line with the changing business environment and the rising demands and desires of the employees, companies need to constantly change their HRM practices. Employee engagement will be fostered by this, which in turn leads to improved performance for the organization and also improved well-being and development for employees to influence employee behavior and thus promote business goals. Companies must create a bundle of internally consistent HRM practices (Jiménez & Valle , 2005).

Few researches have been conducted to investigate the relationship between the HRM practices and the job performance of the employees. The results have shown that HRM practices Recruitment and selection processes are important practices for human resource management, and are crucial in contributing to organizational success. Recruitment and selection highly contribute to the performance of the organization (Tehitna, Melkamu, 2021). Training and development had positively correlated and claimed statistically significant relationship with employee performance and effectiveness. It is recommended that the organization maintain providing employee training and development activities and ensure the participation of employees in

planning, need or skill deficit identification and evaluation of training and development programs (2015). HRM practices perceptions of employee of (recruitment and selection, and Reward management, Performance appraisal and training and development) were low. The Correlation results indicated that recruitment and selection, Reward management, Performance appraisal and training and development were significantly and positively correlated with the employee performance in organization (Yeshihareg , 2019).

2.2 Empirical Review of Literature

2.2.1 Empirical evidencen on HRM In the global studies

Empirical Reviews Here different empirical literature reviews are presented containing Several studies about human resource policy and practices like recruitment and selection, performance management ,training and development and reward management that have also influence on employee's performance. For instance, Ombui, K., Elegwa, M., & Gichuhi, A.(2014), conducted a study on “The Influence of Recruitment and Selection on the Performance of Employees in Research Institutes in Kenya”. The result showed that the correlation between employee performance and recruitment and selection were highly significant (2014)

Ekwoaba, J., Ikeije, U., and Ufoma, N. (2015) in a study of the impact of recruitment and selection criteria on organizational performance revealed that recruitment and selection criteria have significant effect on organization’s performance that the more objective the recruitment and selection criteria, the better the organization’s performance.

Morris, N. & Jane, M. (2017) concluded from his study findings that enacting performance management system enhances employee performance through setting individual objectives that are derived from overall organizational goals and identifying skills gap. Zhang (2012) highlighted on his study that the major aims of performance management system as to ensure that -the work performed by employees accomplishes the work of the company; employees have a clear understanding of the quality and quantity of work expected from them; employees receive ongoing information about how effectively they are performing relative to expectations.

Training is necessary for the employees to perform particular job because most jobs require specific skill and knowledge by which the job is much easier to perform as it is in the benefit of the employee. Qureshi et al (2007) came to the conclusion that training as an human resource management practice has a very positive impact on the performance of the employees since a highly positive correlation was found in that study. Additionally Raji et al, (2011) concluded from finding of their study that On the Job Training, Training Design and Delivery style have significant affect on organizational performance and all these have positively affect the organizational performance. It means it increases the overall organizational performance.

Lotta, L. (2012) studied the impact of financial and non financial rewards on employee motivation and concluded that the importance of rewarded employees is very significant towards employee performance among many companies.

Employees take recognition as their feelings of value and appreciation and as a result it boosts up morale of employee which ultimately increases productivity of organizations. On their study Rizwan, Q. , and Ali, U. (2010) showed that rewards playing a vital role

in determining the significant performance in job and it is positively associated with the process of motivation.

The result of the study of Oladejo M., & Yinus, O. (2014) showed that compensation plan has significant and positive effect on workers performance which will eventually increase the overall performance of the organization. Compensation system was also found to be the backbone of all policies concerning the acquisition and utilization of human resources. The result of other study also indicated that there is a statistical significant relationship between rewards with employee work performance and rewards have a positive influence on employee work performance (Rashmi, R., & Umesh M., (2017)

Regarding the human resource management practices the finding of a study of Devender, S. (2014) showed that human resources practices i.e. job performance in organization are correlated with human resource practices (compensation, performance evaluation process & promotion practices) . Akram et al (2016) on their study findings have reported that human resource management practices (recruitment and selection, training and development, compensation and incentives, performance appraisal) are positively related to employee's performance.

2.2.2 Empirical evidence on HRM in Ethiopia

In Ethiopia like abroad there are several studies conducted on the factors that are affecting the effectiveness of human resource policy and practices like recruitment and selection, Training and Development, Performance Proposal and Reward and compensation on employee performance.

Degu, M (2010) in his study on Evaluation of personnel management capabilities of the federal police of Ethiopia in Addis Ababa reveals that the personnel management capability of the Federal Police of Ethiopia was characterized by incompetence.

Dirk J. van (2004) conducted a study on Human Resource Management Practices in Selected Ethiopian Private Companies. The result reveals that the importance of human resource management is not uniformly understood at all the case-study companies. Although the multinational companies based in Ethiopia see their human resources as the companies' most important asset, as human capital, the local companies generally do not.

Dawit, T (2019) conducted an Assessment of Human Resource Management Practices and Challenges in Selected Construction Projects and concluded that the key challenges of the human resource management practices were high labor turnover, lack of incentives and benefits, inadequate retirement benefit, skill gap, null occupational health and safety practices.

Daniel, T (2020) examines the human resource management practices Vis-A-Vis organization performance in the case of public organizations He concludes that The Major challenges the human resource management practices were lack of sufficient budget, absence of accountability and transparency, technological resistance, uncomfortable working environment, insufficient managerial capacity building and lack of employee inspiration. He concludes that there is a positive relationship between recruitment and selection, training and development, performance appraisal and reward system, and organizational performance.

Tigist, S (2022) Impact of Human Resource Management Practices on Employee Performance show that lack of skills, knowledge, and experiences, identifying gaps that

need training, and lack of performance appraisal are the main factors affecting HRM practices and employees' performances in the university. Thus, the selected HRM practices have a significant impact on employees' commitment, punctuality, trust, and deliverables in both quality and quantity negatively. It is also indicated that the practices have also impacted the productivity of the university. Thus, there are significant relations between training, performance appraisal, and commitment.

Selamawit, A (2016) The Effect of Performance Appraisal on Employee's Performance in Commercial Bank of Ethiopia, Jimma District The research revealed that competence, assessment and development, management by Objectives, performance based pay and employee training all had an effect on employee Performance in organization. However the factors, employee training, Performance based pay, and management by objectives were the key factors that influenced Employee performance. However, the factor, competence, assessment and development could not be ignored since it was rated to a moderate extent by the employees an indication that it also contributed a lot to employee performance.

2.2.2.1 Requirement and selection

Recruitment and selection are essential tools in assisting the human resource managers and the entire company to hire the right people and retain them. The studies have been carried out on Requirement and selection for instance

Thomas, H (2020) studied the Employee Recruitment and Selection Practices in Oromia Region, The case of EEPCO of Adama Branch. The study reveals the organizations policies and principles of recruitment is that they use both internal and external source of recruitment. The organization uses different alternatives to recruitment the rate how the organization focus on alternatives to recruitment is

medium and the organization uses contingent worker more than other alternatives. The most factors that affect the organization recruitment process are working condition and labor market from internal and external respectively. External recruitment has some problem for the organization because of that it needs long training and the related cost. Even though the organization makes different recruitment and selection activities to feel the vacancy position, the process the way and the methods it uses are ineffective that makes them less performed or such activities brings nothing growth to the organization.

Tehitna Melkamu (2021) conducted study on the Role of Employee Recruitment and Selection on the Organization Performance, the Case of Wegagen Bank findings revealed that the organization uses several practices to recruit and select. Newspaper is used as a vacancy announcement, and interview as a selection practice. The recruitment and selection practice of the company were evaluated by the respondents. Based on the given responses, most respondents stated that the number of applications affect the employee selection process. Regarding the selection criteria, the organization uses formal education. Therefore, it is concluded that recruitment and selection highly contribute to the performance of the organization.

Habtamnesh, G (2019) also investigated the effect of recruitment and selection practices on organizational performance of United Bank S.C. The Findings of the study, shows that recruitment practices ($r=.391^{**}$ with $p<0.05$), Selection practices ($r=.546$ with $p<0.001$) have a high degree of positive relationship with organizational performance. These indicate there are slightly little but positive influence on the recruitment processes on the UB performances.

2.2.2.2 Training and Development

Training and development is the method of update the mental of the workers and motivated the workers to stay in the organization. The absence of training and development may cause the de-motivation of the workers (2022). The objectives of awarding prizes shall be to ensure the Success of the mission of the Commission through encouraging police officers with outstanding achievements and long years of service (Regulation No. 268, 2012).

Alemayehu, M (2017) in a study of the Effects of Training on Employee Performance in Ethiopia Revenue and Customs Authority at Customs procedure Sector shows that the trainers didn't deliver the training as expected by the trainee and employees' have an average performance level since they were not comfortable with the present design and delivery of the training program. The trainees will reach at the desired level of performance if the training is well designed and delivered. The other finding of the study shows that delivery style also has a positive and significant relationship with employee performance.

Shiferaw, D (2013) make Assessment on the Human Resource Management Practices in Ethiopian Public Health Association (EPHA) and The findings show that there are gaps in HRM practices regardless of HR manager's high level of education in their respective job fields. On this ground, it has been concluded that the organization managers and supervisors need additional HR related skills and knowledge to carryout HRM functions and therefore, an organized effort from the organization and other concerned bodies is of paramount importance to address this lack of HR management capacity.

Mohammed, H (2022) Impact of training on employees performance Results show that training design, training needs assessment, training delivery style and training evaluation have significant positive effect on employees' performance. Abeba, M (2015) also on his study on The Impact of Training and Development on Employee Performance and Effectiveness and conclude that Training and development had positively correlated and claimed statistically significant relationship with employee performance and effectiveness.

2.2.2.3 Performance Proposal

Trsit, G (2018) the effect of performance appraisal practice on employee performance: the case of goal Ethiopia. The results showed that all the factors, rater accuracy being the stronger and major influencer one, are significant in ensuring the effectiveness of employee performance.

Chemeda, D (2012) a Comparative Study of Employees Performance Appraisal Practices and Problems in Ethiopian Higher Education Institutions: The Case of Addis Ababa University and St. Mary University College. The study reveals that such mixed interests rather discourage workers from competitive workings and creativities. Hence, the primary purposes of performance appraisal are missing its direction, which is creating competitive working systems and giving balanced rewards for workers for their contributions to an organization. In the study, performance appraisal is seen to be implemented in a biased manner based on proximity and mixed interests as mentioned before for punishing employees performing at the lowest status. Thus, in order to create competitive working conditions and systems of balanced benefits for employees, performance appraisal should be understood very well particularly by heads of human

resources and supervisors; and, should be implemented in the desired way for the desired purposes.

2.2.2.4 Reward and compensation

Employees are the key resources for any organization and in the circumstance of managing people, the reward and compensation system underlines a center feature of the employment association. The success or failure of the organization mostly depends on their employees. To be successful or to get a well performed tasks or achieving the desired goals of the company, Employees should be motivated, attracted and retained in the organization. The key tools or instruments for these are reward and compensations management systems of the Organization.

Zehara, K (2021) examine the effect of compensation and reward on employee performance: the case of wegagen bank, Addis Ababa city branches. The findings show that as a result the performance of employees is affected by the compensation and reward system of the organization. Therefore, since majority of employee's performance is affected by the compensation and reward system of the company, the organization should review their compensation and reward system and work towards having an attractive and competitive compensation, reward and recognition system in place to encourage, motivate as well as get the best performance from employees.

Bazew, M (2017) The Effect of Nonfinancial Reward on Employee Retention: The case of United Bank S.C. The result of correlation analysis evidenced recognition, career advancement opportunity and training & development had positive and moderate relationship with employee retention. The beta coefficient value in multiple regressions also revealed nonfinancial rewards studied had a positive influence in bringing variation in employee retention. The finding of descriptive analysis also revealed that

the respondents average agreement on recognition, career advancement and training & development rewards were moderate level. This implies the practice of these rewards at organization were unsatisfactory to retain its employees.

Getachew, E (2016) concluded on the study of Practices and Challenges of Human Resource Management in Major General Muluget Buli Technical College that employees generally demotivated due to lack of transparency on management appraisal process and the issue of leadership development

Bruktawit, M (2006) study the effect of compensation and reward on employee performance: the case of management sciences for health – Ethiopia. The study shows that the major factors that led to low level of satisfaction are lack of transparency from the supervisors in rationally evaluating the subordinates, employee's salary history, supervisor's powerlessness regarding negotiation of salary for their staff, and reduced attention from the HR in implementing organization HR policies are frequently mentioned by the respondents.

Meseret, (2022). The effect of non-monitory rewards on employee retention, the case of Lideta sub-city land development and management. Results of the findings shows that the organization not promoted their employees from lower level to middle or upper levels these may cause the turnover in the organization so to long stay with all employees and make employee to stay in the organization it is important to prompt.

Begashaw,T (2017) The Role of Effective Compensation and Reward System on Employee Performance in the Case of Commercial Bank of Ethiopia. The findings of this study indicated that there was a significant relationship between compensation and reward system with employee performance. The study also indicated both financial and non-financial compensation and rewards have a significant relationship with employee

performance. The non-financial compensation and rewards were found to be a more motivational than the financial rewards in the organization. Therefore, creating competitive and effective compensation and rewards should be developed to motivate employees' performance.

Esete, M (2019) Effect of reward practices on employees' performance: a case study on Zemen bank S.C. The finding of the study indicated that there was a significant relationship between reward system and employee performance in general and financial and non-financial rewards in particular.

In Jimma, survey conducted on the effect of compensation on employees' motivation in Jimma University academic staff showed that payment, promotion, recognition, working conditions, and payment influence work motivation. The study also indicated there was significant and positive relationship between compensation and work motivation. The study has shown that Jimma University staffs were not motivated and satisfied in payment system of the university. The findings of this study also indicated that there was a relationship between compensation and its components and employee work motivation. Moreover, money they earned from their job was not satisfactory and staffs dissatisfied with the assignment of responsibility in the university and fairness promotion is in appropriate (Negash, Zewude, & Megersa, 2014).

2.2.2.5 In police organization

Several studies have been carried out on HRM practices on organizations in Ethiopia, For instance, Esayas, Y (2019) studied The effect of selected human resource management practices on employees' turnover intention: the case of civil employees of Ethiopian federal police commission. The findings shows that the selected human

resource management practices; selection, training and career development, have been found vital to employees and indeed influence turnover intention.

Zahari Goranov (2019) Human resources management in the police system findings shows that if you have well-trained staff it is possible to improve the quality of work. The most important resources for the organization are HR. They are especially valuable because they are very difficult to be skilled. Also the federal Police Officers Administration Council of ministers explains any police officers shall be given on job or off job education and training which qualifies him for the duty he is assigned for (Regulation No. 268, 2012).

Biruk, H (2019) study the Impact of Training on Employee Performance reveals that training led to a positive impact on the performance of employee and an improvement in their skills and commitment.

Teshale, A (2010) conducted Assessment on Recruitment and Selection Practice shows that In recruitment and selection activities no much attention given to the back ground of the candidates, it means that the new comer was a criminal before or not has a good manner then he reflects his bad behavior after he deployed to the community. The participation of training center is not much given attention to the criteria' used t select the candidates.

Fikru, W (2022) study The effect of police job stress on their performance and concluded that The police profession is a very risky and susceptible job for a variety of reasons, including traumatic occurrences such as the sad death of friends, the majority of officers living in terrible weather, the use of force, and other issues. Job stress is also an increasing problem for employees in government institutions, particularly among

police officers. Job stress was job significantly and negatively associated with performance of the officers.

The objective of performance evaluation shall be to enable police officers to discharge their duties in the required volume, quality, speed and cost; to identify the strength and weakness of police officers and thereby to implement appropriate capacity building programs based on plans; Enable police officers to improve their performance by enhancing their self motivation; Enable to provide incentives to police officers based on the results; and Enable the management body to make administrative decisions based on tangible information.

Performance evaluation shall be carried out in a transparent manner with the participation of the concerned bodies and the police officer. A report sent to the Commission by an institution in which a police officer is attending education or training shall be taken as performance evaluation report.

2.3 Conceptual Frame work

The conceptual framework provides the study of a structure that represents the systematic approach of researching and finding out fundamental relationships between variables. The conceptual framework shows the crucial process, which is useful to show the direction of the study (Creswel, 2009).

It is used to make conceptual distinctions and organize ideas. In this section, the Researcher developed the Conceptual framework based on the review of literatures of the study that indicates the relationship between HRM policy and practice as (independent Variables) and Employee Performance (as dependent variable).

Figure 0-1 conceptual framework of the study

Source: own survey (2023)

2.4 Summary

CHAPTER THREE

RESEARCH DESIGN AND METHODOLOGY

Introduction

In order to achieve the objective of the study, a clear and appropriate research methodology is vital. Hence, this chapter outlines the overall methodology that was used in the study. It begins with the research design, the research approach, target population and techniques of sample size determination, type and sources of data, data collection procedures, and the research methods and ways of data analysis and presentation that were adopted in the course of the research.

3.1 Research Design

Research design is an overall framework of research that explains the direction and method to be used in the study to gather the information needed, either from primary or secondary sources (Malhotra, 2007). It is a strategy used to carry out research that defines a succinct and logical plan to tackle established research question(s) through the collection, interpretation, analysis, and discussion of data (Claybaugh, 2020). The study used a descriptive survey, which is classified as non-experimental research. Out of the two types of descriptive surveys, cross-sectional and longitudinal studies, as categorised by Kothari (2004), as cited in Saunders et al. (2009), I preferred cross-sectional studies. This is because my study compared the responses of groups of respondents on the existing status and link between human resource management policy and practice and employee performance in the Addis Ababa Police Commission head office at the same time. Moreover, concurrently gathering data from the groups of

respondents was found to be useful to correctly triangulate the realities behind the subject matter studied.

3.2 Research Approach

Research approach is selected by researcher(s) based on the research purpose, the nature of the research, the problem area, and research questions (Alhamdani et al. 2006). The research approach in this study is chosen based on the purpose and the research questions set out to be addressed. According to Creswell (2003). There are three basic types of research approaches, quantitative, qualitative, and Mixed approach.

3.2.1 Quantitative research approach

Quantitative research approach is based on the philosophy of post positivism worldview. It is also reductionist in that the intent is to reduce the ideas into a small, discrete set of ideas to test, such as the variables that constitute hypotheses and research questions. In addition, quantitative approach uses statistical methods in describing patterns of behavior and generalizing findings from samples to population of interest, and employs strategies of inquiry such as experiments and surveys (Creswell 2003).

3.2.2. Qualitative research approach

Under qualitative approach or social-constructivist worldview, inquirers generate or inductively develop a theory or pattern of meaning rather than starting with a theory as in post positivism. Qualitative researchers tend to use open-ended questions so that participants can express their views and meanings are constructed by human beings as they engage with the world they are interpreting (Creswell 2003).

3.2.3. Mixed research approach

Mixed research approach or pragmatist worldview is not committed to any one system of philosophy and reality. In this approach, inquirers draw liberally from both quantitative and qualitative assumptions.

Employing this approach is used to neutralize or cancel the biases of applying any of a single approach and a means to offset the weaknesses inherent in a single method with the strengths of the other method (Creswell 2003). Mixed research approach opens door to multiple methods of data collection and helps to generate the findings to a population and develop a detailed view of the meaning of a phenomenon or concept for individuals (Creswell, 2003).

This research approach pose the researcher to the challenges that need for extensive data collection, the time-intensive nature of analyzing both text and numeric data, and the requirement for the researcher to be familiar with both quantitative and qualitative forms of research (Creswell, 2003).

Mixed methods approach can be implemented in different ways. The literature identifies three strategies in integrating the two approaches, i.e. quantitative and qualitative methods (Wollela, 2009). First concurrent, in which the quantitative and qualitative phases occur simultaneously; second, sequential, in which the researcher starts with gathering qualitative data and then gathers quantitative data or vice versa in two different phases; and third, transformative where the researcher (either concurrently or sequentially) may be able to give voice to diverse perspectives, to better advocate for participants or to better understand a phenomenon or process that is changing as a result of being studied.

In order to achieve the objective of this study and answer the research questions researcher adopts mixed research approach to assess effect of human resource management policy on employee performance in the case of Addis Ababa police commission head office

3.3 Target Population, Sampling Technique, and Sample Size

3.3.1 Target Population

A target population refers to all the members who meet the criteria specified for a research investigation" (Alvi, 2016). The author's further emphasis that the target population must be a complete subset of the population of interest means that members of the target population must also be described by the boundaries of the population of interest (Casteel & Bridier, 2021). According to Wellman and Kruger (2003:119), the target population is the number of respondents that would be included in the research study. For this study, the target populations were both civil workers and police officers in the head office of the Addis Ababa police, which comprise technical officers, administrative staff, secretaries, record officers, and logistic staff. These targets were selected because of their easy access to data, cost effectiveness, and ease of manageability. The total population of the study is 5240, which includes both civil workers and police forces.

3.3.2 Sampling Technique

Sampling is related to the selection of a subset of individuals from within a population to estimate the characteristics of the whole population. The two main advantages of sampling are faster data collection and lower cost (Robert M. G., 2004). Sampling is the process of selecting a statistically representative sample of individuals from the

population of interest (Kamangar & Islami, 2013). In this study, the samples were selected by both purposive and simple random sampling procedure. For the purposive (non-probability sampling), respondents were chosen based on researcher judgment that they have desirable position and could provide the required information. Stratified simple random sampling techniques were employed. The study used stratified random sampling techniques for current employees. Stratified random sampling was used to achieve representation of the respondents. The respondents are stratified on the basis of their department category. Currently 5240 employees working in these seven department and among these employees a sample of 372 employees were drawn.

3.3.3 Sample Size

The sample size is defined as the minimum number of respondents from which data could be drawn for the generalisation of results (Loganathan, 2013). According to Shah (2011), researchers must calculate the sample size before starting any animal study. Malhortra and Peterson (2006) and Zikmund (2001). It was stated that the larger the sampling size of a research project, the more accurate the data generated, but the sample size was different due to different situations. The sample size should be studied from the perspective of the primary objective of the study and limited to only subjects from which relevant information would be obtained.

At the time of study, the number of employees in the Addis Ababa Police Commission head office was 5240 in total. These employees are located in the eight departments of commission illustrated in the table below, and the sample size from the population and sample size per strata are calculated according to the different known formulas as included in Table 3.1. The sample size calculation formula for the population is adapted

from Yamani (1967), and the sample size formula per strata is adapted from C. Kothari (1984).

In this research, sampling size is determined accordingly by using the sample size formula, which was developed by Tara Yamane in 1967 to determine the sample size from a given population.

$$n = n = \frac{N}{1+N(e)^2}$$

$$n=5240/1+5240(0.05)^2$$

$$n = 5240/14.1 = 371.6 = \underline{372}.$$

Where

n = sample size

N = population size

e = level of precision. At a 95% confidence level, degree of variability = 0.5, and level of precision/sampling error = 5%, using this formula resulted in 372 employees being the total sample size selected from the total study population of 5240 employees.

Table 3-1 Staff Data with Sample Size

No	Main sectors	No of employees	Number of employees in % from total population	Sample size per to each strata.
1.	Human Resource Management and development sector	375	7.2	27
2.	Crime and University Disaster Prevention Sector	3435	66	244

3.	Crime and University Disaster Investigation Sector	542	10.2	38
4.	Public Communication; Music, Theater and Sports Directorate	246	4.5	17
5.	Intelligence and Radio Communication Directorate	117	2.1	8
6.	Commissioner Staff Directorate	94	1.8	7
7.	Police Academy Director	194	3.7	14
8.	Civil	237	4.5	17
	Total	5240	100%	372

Source: Researcher's Own Development, 2023

To calculate the sizes of the samples from the different strata, the researcher used the below formula, as per C. Kothari (1984)

$$n_i = \frac{n \cdot N_i}{N}$$

Where

n represents the total sample size.

N_i represents the proportion of population included in stratum i and

n_i is the number of elements selected from stratum i. This calculation would give the sample size per stratum, as illustrated in the table above.

3.4 Data source and collection methods

3.4.1 Sources of Data

The objective of this study is to investigate the effect of human resource management policies on employee performance. To achieve the ultimate objectives of the study, both primary and secondary sources of data were used. The primary sources of data was obtained from the Addis Ababa Police Commission head office by all department leaders and staff members. These participants were selected because they directly or indirectly participate in recruitment and selection, training and development, composition and reward, and prosomal approval. The secondary sources of data were obtained from books, articles, and reports of the organization.

3.5 Data Collection Instruments

Data collection instruments included questionnaires, interview guides, and the documentary review checklist.

3.5.1 Quantitative Methods

The questionnaire was method used to generate quantitative data.

3.5.1.1 Questionnaire Tools

This involved the use of self-administered questionnaires for respondents in relation to human resource management policy and practices, and they were given to staff members and their leaders. In seeking quantitative data, closed-ended questionnaires in a scale (five-likert) form were used. The questionnaire method was used because it helps to investigate motives and feelings in Likert scales (Franz, Worrell, & Vögele, 2013).

3.5.1.2 Questionnaires

A questionnaire is a research instrument that consists of a set of questions (or other types of prompts) for the purpose of gathering information from respondents through a survey or statistical study. A research questionnaire is typically a mix of closed-ended and open-ended questions. Open-ended, long-term questions offer the respondent the ability to elaborate on their thoughts (Gault, 1907).

The questionnaire was administered office-to-office since most of the respondents in this category are known. The Likert scale was used since it is very flexible and can be constructed more easily than most other types of attitude scales (Yoder, VIRDEN III, & Amin, 2005).

3.5.2 Qualitative Methods

To obtain qualitative data, interviews and document reviews were conducted.

3.5.2.1 Interview Guide

Interviews Interviews are more suitable for questions that require probing to obtain adequate information. They are particularly useful when qualitative data are required. To strengthen the data collected through questionnaires the researcher carried out Semi-structured interview through 32 leaders who are above the division position in the organization those purposefully selected by the researcher including human resource managers and other managers those are related to the human resource policy to elaborate the original response with line of inquiry introduced by the interviewee. Because those managers have close contact with the employees and know the performance of each individual as well as have the exposure to know the challenges that hinder the employees to utilize their potential effectively. The researcher conducted

a face-to face interview and by telephone with those managers in the Addis Ababa police commission head office during data collection time.

3.5.2.2 Interview

The interview method was used to qualitatively explore the influence of human resource management policy and practices on employee performance at the Addis Ababa Police Commission. This method took the option of face-to-face interviews and sought to provide the required data as specified above. The interview method was used because it provides an excellent opportunity to probe and explore questions (Denzin, Robbins, Carboy-Newcomb, & Cresswell, 1994).

3.6 Data Collection Procedure

The study utilized both qualitative and quantitative data collection methods. Primary data was obtained using questionnaires as well as interviews. Secondary data were sourced from reading the literature.

3.6.1.1 Document Review Method

A document review method was used in sourcing secondary data in all relevant documents in relation to the influence of human resource management policy and practices on employee performance in the Addis Ababa Police Commission. These were sourced from journals, text books, and other relevant, reliable sources. Novak (1996) explains that if secondary research and data are undertaken with care and diligence, it provides a cost-effective way of gaining a broad understanding of research questions and the broader concept under study. Secondary data is also helpful in designing the research and can provide a baseline with which to compare primary data collection results (Hoffman & Novak, 1996).

3.7 Data Analysis

Data analysis is the process of inspecting, cleansing, transforming, and modeling data with the goal of discovering useful information, informing conclusions, and supporting decision-making. (TUDUI, 2014). Data analysis has multiple facets and approaches, encompassing diverse techniques under a variety of names, and is used in different business, science, and social science domains (The Multiple Facets of Correlation Functions, 2017). In today's business world, data analysis plays a role in making decisions more scientific and helping businesses operate more effectively (Xia & Gong, 2015).

In analyzing the data, I applied the dominantly inductive method. The inductive method of analysis was applied to draw the findings by triangulating different data collected from various sources using different instruments. Moreover, the method was used to draw valid conclusions out of the most related findings that were taken as premises for the inference.

As indicated above, there are two types of (qualitative and quantitative) data that were concurrently analyzed under the result section of the study. Both types of data were analyzed by applying different statistical tests. Quantitative data were analyzed by applying both descriptive and inferential statistics. Among the descriptive statistics, percentages and mean scores were used in the study.

Percentage was employed to summarize and analyze the background variables, while mean scores were used to represent the calculated and condensed average responses of the respondents related to the effect of human resource management policy and practice on employee performance in the Addis Ababa Police Commission head office.

With regard to inferential statistical analysis, parametric tests were applied in this particular study. This is because, as supported by scholars, almost all of the assumptions of this test (randomly determined samples, defined population size, data measured by ordinal or interval scale, and data measured by mean scores) were fulfilled (Singh, 2006).

Based on the nature of the gap or problems justified and addressed, the specific research questions set, the specific objectives intended, and the items developed in the questionnaire, there were three areas of analysis requiring inferential statistics. The first is an analysis of the existence of statistically significant differences between the average responses. This was conducted by applying a one-way ANOVA. The second is to analyze the link or association between the levels of human resource management policy and practice and employee performance. This part of the analysis was conducted by applying the Pearson correlation coefficient. The last area that required inferential analyses was to examine the impact of the confined factors on the existing status of human resource management policies and practices on employee performance. This analysis was conducted using linear regression analysis (as consulted by Hair et al., 2006). Actually, similar to the current study, the related studies applied linear regression to investigate the practices of SM in universities in Nairobi and Ghana, respectively (Kinyanjui & Juma, 2014).

Moreover, since the study applied a descriptive survey, the statistical difference between the overall responses of the respondents to the universities was judged at a confidence level of 95% (at an alpha level of 5%).

Unlike quantitative data, qualitative data were transcribed in Amharic (the official language of the nation) and then translated to English, then coded and thematically

organized before they were analyzed to serve the purposes of the present study. They were analyzing, examining, and exploring the deeper meaning behind the words or phrases.

3.8 Ethical Considerations

The study has attempted to take all the necessary precautions to protect the study participants from such problematic encounters by applying certain measures. In the process of conducting any research, a researcher has the responsibility to be ethical to her or his profession as well as to her or his respondents so that the smooth accomplishment of the research towards the achievement of the stipulated objectives of the proposed study can be guaranteed (Bogdon & Biklen, 2007). Accordingly, as indicated under the procedure of data collection above, letters of cooperation were initially secured from Gelila International Seminary. Permission and consensus were obtained from both my college and the studied organization before the data were gathered. Thus, the current study was made to have official ground.

On top of this, as advised by many scholars, pseudonyms were used instead of the true names so as to maintain the confidentiality of the individual interviewees and members of the focus group discussion, the anonymity of their responses, and the freedom of the respondents in providing the information (Bogdon & Biklen, 2007).

Moreover, in line with the suggestion forwarded by Neuman (2007) throughout the whole circumstances of the research, I respected all participants in every aspect of communication.

Accordingly, as recommended by Cohen et al. (2005), gathering data was started in accordance with the informed consent of the respondents. Finally, the data were

collected after informing the respondents that all the information gathered would never be used for any other purposes other than serving the purpose of the present study. Generally, I respected the values, beliefs, and privacy of my participants and avoided any act or word that might harm the morals or psychology of my respondents.

3.9 Insuring the Quality of Data

Validity and reliability tests were performed to confirm the accuracy of the data or data collection tools. These two tests typically overlap. This is due to the fact that the two tests have a positive correlation simply because dependable instruments are those that are valid (Bryman & Bell 2003). However, each test was carried out and reported separately, as follows:

3.9.1 Validity Test

The amount to which an instrument measures what it claims to measure is referred to as validity (Sekaran, 2003). The questionnaires were therefore modified from earlier research to assure the validity of the research instrument.

As a small-scale preliminary investigation, a pilot test also known as a pilot study was carried out in order to evaluate the timeliness and cost-effectiveness of the instrument as well as the relevance and clarity of the questionnaire's contents (as proposed by Creswell, 2009). This was accomplished by providing the tools, primarily the questionnaire, to 20 policemen stationed at the headquarters of the Addis Abeba Police Commission. In this particular test, it was primarily determined whether or not the sampled respondents could understand the questionnaire. Which led to a review and improvement of the content.

Actually, I had circulated the questionnaire to a group of people with a similar demographic make-up, who were taken to be a stand-in for my actual respondents, in the same manner that I had done during the actual data collection. For instance, as the respondents' makeup was anticipated to be diverse across all departments, I chose participants from a range of academic specializations, educational levels, and sexes. I then chose a few of my acquaintances (from the pilot test participants) and asked the following questions:

1. How do you see the length of the items? What was the average time it took?
2. What are items that are confusing by their nature?
3. Are there incompletely stated, ambiguous, or unrelated options?
4. What are your overall comments?

As a result, I gathered feedback and updated the survey. We recognized, altered, or eliminated any elements that "confused" the respondents or conceptually repeated information. As a result, everyone who answered the newly amended version of the survey could understand it. As previously said, the face validity of the questionnaire was discussed by my study advisors, who cheekily commented on it. The questioners changed the margins, font size, and spacing based on the advisor's suggestions.

3.9.2 Reliability

The reliability of the questionnaire was measured by calculating Cronbach's alpha value through SPSS 24. Sekaran (2003) explains that Cronbach's alpha is a reliability coefficient that indicates how well items in an instrument are positively correlated to one another. According to Lombard (2010), Cronbach's alpha coefficients of 0.9 or

greater are nearly always acceptable, 0.8 or greater is acceptable in most situations, and 0.7 may be appropriate in some exploratory studies for some indices.

According to table 3:2 the Cronbach's alpha value is 0.6332 indicating that the measurements employed in this study will be reliable and consistent.

The reliability of the questionnaires in this research will be measured by using Cronach's coefficient, which indicates whether the levels of the items are correlated to each other. Therefore, based on the test, the results for the items are reliable and acceptable.

Table 3-2: Cronbach's alpha internal consistency rule of thumb

Cronbache"s Alpha	Internal Consistency
$\alpha \geq 0.9$	Excellent (High- Stakes) testing)
$0.7 \leq \alpha < 0.9$	Good (Low- Stakes testing)
$0.6 \leq \alpha < 0.7$	Acceptable
$0.5 \leq \alpha < 0.6$	Poor
$\alpha < 0.5$	Unacceptable

Source: Manerika, Vijaya and Manerikar, Sumeet (2015)

Furthermore, the widely acceptable cut-off level of the alpha value in most social science studies is 0.7 (Hulland, 1999). Consequentially, the investigator checked the Reliability of the 20 and 25 items in the Likert-type Questionnaires and got a good coefficient of Cronbach's alpha of 0.881 and 0.934, which is more than the cut-off level

value of alpha 0.7. This shows the presence of acceptable internal consistency and reliability in the questions.

Table 3-3 Reliability test

Items	Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
Effectiveness in achieving goals (evaluation criteria)	.897	7
Recruitment and Selection	.891	9
Training and development	.924	9
Performance appraisal	.934	10
Reward and Compensation	.921	8
Employee's performance	.881	10

Source: Author's computation, 2023

Therefore, as shown in Table 3.2, the values of Chronbach's alpha for each field of the questionnaire and the entire questionnaire for the fields were in the range of 0.881 up to 934. So, the reliability of the whole set of items was reliable and acceptable because, as Lombard stated, coefficients of 0.80 or greater are acceptable in most situations. Therefore, it can be said that the questionnaire is valid, reliable, and ready for distribution to the population sample.

2.5 Summary

CHAPTER FOUR

4. DATA PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS, AND INTERPRETATION

Introduction

This chapter presents the results and findings of the research. The chapter mainly includes data results from the statistical tests conducted on the gathered primary data. The research's main emphasis was to investigate the effect of human resource management policies and practices on employee performance. Descriptive analysis and inferential analysis of the study are presented, respectively.

The data for this study was collected in the month of September 2023 by questionnaires distributed to the sample of 372 respondents in the organization. The survey questionnaires were distributed to the participants, 340 respondents. Out of the 340 sample respondents, 291 respondents filled out and returned the questionnaires, making a response rate of 85.6%. 49 of the questionnaires were not returned, and all the questionnaires were properly filled out and used by researchers. Accordingly, the analysis of this study is based on the number of questionnaires collected. Here The statistical programme used for the analysis and presentation of data in this study is the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 24.

The researcher also asked for interviews with 32 leaders who are above the division in the organization. The interview questioners were analysed using thematic analysis because interview questioners are about the emotions or perceptions of people and what they feel.

4.1 Demographic characteristics of the respondents

This part of the questionnaire requested a limited amount of information about the respondents' personal and demographic status in relation to the human resource management policy and practices of the Addis Ababa Police Commission. This includes gender, age, rank, position, educational background, and work experience. Therefore, these variables are summarised and described in the tables shown below.

4.1.1 The human resource management policy and practices of the Addis Ababa Police Commission

Table 4-1 Background of the Respondent

		Frequency	Percent
Gender	Male	212	72.9
	Female	79	27.1
Age	18-25	76	26.1
	26-30	112	38.5
	31-35	64	22.0
	36 -40	24	8.2
	41 and above	15	5.2
Ranks	Deputy commander – commander	47	16.2

	Assistance Inspector - chief Inspector	108	37.1
	Assistance Sergeant - chief Sergeant	134	46.0
	Constable	2	.7
Position	Directorate	25	8.6
	Division	20	6.9
	Coordinator	87	29.9
	Team Leader	51	17.5
	Officer	108	37.1
Educational	MA and above	35	12.0
	BA	37	12.7
	Diploma and level 1-4	76	26.1
	Grade 10 or 12 complete	71	24.4
	Grade 10 and Below	72	24.7
Work Experience	from 0 to 10 years	173	59.5
	From 11 to 20 years	107	36.8
	From 21-30 years	5	1.7

	From 31 and above years	6	2.1
	Total	291	100.0

Source: Survey Result 2023

The respondents were asked to indicate their sex. With regard to the sex of the respondents, as shown in Table 4.1, below 212 (72.9%) of them are male, and the remaining 79 (27.1%) out of the total of 291 participants (who filled out the questionnaire) were females. This clearly points out that, sexually, the members of the police force were dominated by males, and the responses given for the current study might be subjected to the perception of the male respondents. This, in turn, might tell us that the human resource management policy and practices were not well implemented for the sex of the employee. on the other hand, were strongly linked with the perception of males. This shows that human resource management policy and practice do not well implement affirmative action during requirements and selection.

Basically, such male-affiliated participation, particularly in a study conducted in the context of Ethiopian public offices, is not a new incident. Another study (Daniel, Human Resource Management Practices and Reflective Organisational Performance: A Focus on Public Offices in Ambo Town, Oromia, Ethiopia) in an international peer-reviewed journal (Vol. 68, 2020) confronted the same challenge. This might still point out the types of themes to be considered in developing and implementing the future strategic plan for the institutions. It requires planners to think over and include gender balancing issues in the upcoming strategic plans of their institutions.

As indicated in Table 4:1 above, the majority, 112 (38.5%), of the respondents fall between the age groups of 26–30, followed by 64 (22.0%), which is between the 31–35

age group; 76 (26.1%) of respondents were in the age group of 18–25; and the remaining are included in the age groups of 36 and above. This demonstrates that there are a higher number of young people. This shows that human resource management practices are not well implemented among the ranks of employees during reward and compensation.

The majority of respondents' ages fell between the age groups of 18 and 30, which is a higher number of young people. This shows that human resource management practices are not well implemented among all HR practices, and because of that, there are high numbers of police officer turnovers in the organization.

This also shows that human resource management policies and practices were not implemented, for instance, the retirement policy. As explained in Regulation No. 268, 2012, Article 68 of the Federal Police Administration Regulation, the service of a police officer shall terminate on the last day of the last month in which he attained the retirement age, unless extended. Article 71 of this regulation explained that the service of a police officer may be extended beyond the age of retirement where his qualification, knowledge, special skill, experience, and capability are found to be critical to the Commission; it is ascertained impossible to replace him by another police officer through promotion, assignment, transfer, or recruitment; he is proved medically fit for service; but the implementation is different from that because all the officers need to be extended without any precondition laid down on the article extended for them. This may make the young and educated for promotion and push the employee for turnover.

Also, the compensation and reward system of the organisation was not attractive, as shown in Article 85 of this regulation. The police commission rewarded medals,

ribbons, and certificates to be awarded to police officers on the basis of outstanding accomplishments of missions and meritorious service for a period of 15 years.

This finding, however, has a relationship with the findings of Zehara (2021). Zehara revealed that the performance of employees is affected by the compensation and reward system of the organization. The majority of an employee's performance is affected by the compensation and reward system of the company; in this case, there is a high turnover rate in the organisation in general among lower-level employees. Therefore, the organisation should review their compensation and reward system and work towards having an attractive and competitive compensation, reward, and recognition system in place to encourage, motivate, and get the best performance from employees.

As depicted in Table 4.1, the rank of the respondents according to proclamation number 268/2012 categorises the involved participants according to rank: 47 (16.2%) were from Deputy Commander to Commander, 108 (37.1%) were from Assistance Inspector to Chief Inspector, 134 (46.0%) were from Assistance Sergeant to Chief Sergeant, and the remaining were Constable-ranked police officers. This revealed that the majority of the respondents are from Assistance Sergeant up to Chief Sergeant, which shows that there is a high turnover of the lower-ranked police officers.

As depicted in Table 4.1 above, participants were asked about their working position in the organization. 25 (8.6%) of the participants are directors, 20 (6.9%), 87 (29.9%) are coordinators, 51 (17.5%) are team leaders, and the remaining 108 (37.1%) are police officers. This shows that the majority of the respondents are officers.

Here, participants were asked to state their level of education. From the table above, the result of the survey demonstrates that the majority of participants, those from the total participant rate who have an MA degree or higher, were 35 (12.0%), and 37 (12.7%)

were BA degree holders. Diploma and level 1-4 holders are 76 (26.1%) of the total participant rate; those who completed Grade 10 or 12 are 71 (24.4%); and the remaining 72 (24.7%) are Grade 10 and below. This indicates that the majority of respondents are in grade 10 or higher, implying that they understand the questions to be answered.

With reference to the experience of the respondents, as shown in Table 4.1 above, almost all about 173 (59.5) of the participants served in their institution were under 10 years of age, and 107 (36.8%) of the participants served in their institution were from 11 to 20 years of age. This implies that the vast majority of the respondents had less experience with the institution since the onset of the ongoing strategic plan. With reference to the experience of the respondents, almost all were under 20 years of age and served in the organisation, but when we see the rewards of the organisation.

This finding, however, contradicts the findings of Fikru (2022). Fikru reported that the majority of his respondents had more experience, and hence he generalised that there was no more turnover in the federal police commission. This inconsistency might be explained by the fact that after the Fikru study, after one year, there might have been a change in the institutional climate so that the rate of turnover might have been greatly increased. For that reason, the results revealed that the human resource policy and practice of the Addis Ababa Police Commission highly influence the effectiveness of the performance of the human resources department.

4.2 Descriptive Statistical Analysis

The mean, or average, is a type of measure of central tendency that is calculated by finding the sum of the study data and dividing it by the total number of data points. In other words, it offers a general picture of the data without unnecessarily covering each

of the observations in the data set. The mean of respondents in each variable shows the average number of responses from the respondents in each variable.

The extent to which the sample group, on average, agreed or disagreed with the raised statements was analysed using the mean results. A low mean implies that the majority of the respondents disagree, while a higher mean value indicates their agreement. Accordingly, the perceptions of the respondents were captured using a five-point Likert scale (1-strongly disagree, 2-disagree, 3-neutral, 4-agree, and 5-strongly agree) and interpreted in accordance with the below detailed According to Zaidatol (2012), the mean score from 1.00 up to 2.33 was considered low; the mean score from 2.34 up to 3.67 was considered moderate; and the mean score above 3.68 was considered high, as illustrated by the comparison based on the mean score of five points. Likert scale instrument. The standard deviation was also used to show the variability of measurements from the mean (average). The higher standard deviation indicates a wider distribution of the scores from the mean. This distribution indicates a more heterogeneous or dissimilar spread of scores on a scale.

While a lower value shows a smaller conveyance with a progressively comparable or homogeneous spread of scores around the mean (Mark, Philip, and Adrian, 2009), Accordingly, employees intention to stay and their perceptions towards the studied independent variables are analysed with the mean and standard deviation results as follows:

4.2.1 The effect HRMP on the Addis Ababa Police Commission

Table 4-2 Descriptive effect human resource management policy

While a lower value shows a smaller conveyance with a progressively comparable or homogeneous spread of scores around the mean (Mark, Philip, and Adrian, 2009),

Accordingly, employees intention to stay and their perceptions towards the studied independent variables are analysed with the mean and standard deviation results as follows:

No	Iteme	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
1.	Effectiveness in achieving goals (evaluation criteria)	291	3.20	1.182
1.1	HR change employees by initiating transformation first within the HR function	291	3.07	1.171
1.2	HR demonstrates understanding of the theory and tools of change (Provides a model of change that can be used throughout the organization)	291	3.10	1.266
1.3	HR plays a leading role in the communication of change (any type of change) in the organization.	291	3.35	1.251
1.4	HR ensure the effective evaluation (measurement) of employee's readiness to deal with organizational change	291	3.37	1.294
1.5	HR timeously / proactively takes the lead in change projects	291	3.48	1.216
1.6	HR serves as a facilitator in change projects	291	2.97	1.168
1.7	HR provides continuous support to employees during change projects			
	Over all result			

Source: Survey Result 2023

As shown in table 4:2 respondents moderately agreed to the statements “HR shows change leadership by initiating transformation first within the HR function;”, “HR demonstrates understanding of the theory and tools of change (Provides a model of change that can be used throughout the organization)”, “HR plays a leading role in the communication of change (any type of change) in the organization”, HR ensure the effective evaluation (measurement) of employee’s readiness to deal with organizational change”, “HR timeously / proactively takes the lead in change projects”, “HR serves as a facilitator in change projects” and “HR provides continuous support to employees during change projects” as shown by a mean score of 3.20, 3.07, 3.10, 3.35, 3.37, 3.48 and 2.97 respectively Which indicate the respondents moderate agreement as per (Zaidatol, 2012) mean score value comparison. The overall average agreement of the respondents with regard to the evaluation criteria of effectiveness in achieving the organizational goals of the human resource management policy of the Addis Ababa Police Commission head office was 3.22 (SD = 0.962). When this mean value is compared with the mean score comparison (Zaidatol, 2012), the mean result indicates that the feelings of respondents towards this statement indicate their moderate agreement. It shows that the respondent was not in full agreement, but more than a little on the evaluation criteria of effectiveness in achieving organization goals, which means if there is a moderate level, there is a problem in evaluation criteria for effectiveness in achieving organization goals and employee performance. These show the effectiveness in achieving goals (evaluation criteria) is relatively enough and adequate, but it isn't as good as it is expected, and the administration must do more on evaluation criteria to address assessment issues. Likewise, an increase in one variable of the independent variable will increase the dependent variable positively. This shows that most of the respondents moderately agree that the evaluation criteria for effectiveness in achieving

organizational goals are a determinant factor for them. The right feedback is regular feedback done through coaching activity (Sharma et al., 2016). Therefore, to place performance assessments to motivate, direct and develop subordinates and to maximize access to important resources within the organization. The results of employee performance assessments are able to provide information about improved performance, ideal workload, employee compliance, employee education and training needs, and the basis for placement and award considerations. Employee Performance Goals (SKP)-based work performance assessment system provides opportunities for more intense interaction and communication between employees and assessors. Communication is carried out at the stage of preparing performance goals, the stage of work implementation and the stage of performance assessment, where the assessment officer (as the supervisor) directly describes the work plan to be achieved over the next year.

4.2.2 The extent of HRMPP affect the employee's performance

Table 4-3 HRMPP affect the employee's performance

No	Items	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
1.	Recruitment and Selection	291	2.8290	.87383
2.	Training and development.	291	2.9831	.98506
3.	Performance appraisal	291	3.2151	1.01314
4.	Reward and Compensation	291	2.3482	.96711
5.	Employee's performance	291	3.3805	.85407

Valid N (listwise)	291	3.2186	.96154
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Source: Survey Result 2023

Table 4.3 shows that the overall average agreement of the respondents with regard to recruitment and selection was 2.82 (SD = 0.874). The mean result indicates that the respondents' feelings towards this statement indicate moderate agreement. It shows that the respondent was not in full agreement, but more than a little on the recruitment and selection of the organization. These show that recruitment and selection are relatively adequate, but they aren't as good as expected, and the administration must focus more on evaluation criteria to address assessment issues. Which means if there is a moderate level, there are no strong criteria for recruitment and selection of new employees for the organization, and there are also no strong criteria for recruitment and selection for new promotions.

The figure implies that there is a practice of recruiting and selecting employees for the sampled construction projects. In the construction sector, according to Fajana et al. (2011), skills and competencies are rated far higher than the normative paper qualifications commonly used for employee selection in most other sectors of the economy. The implication of the given figure is that recruitment is used to attract sufficient job candidates who have the necessary potential, competencies, and traits to fill job needs. Similarly, selection involves choosing the candidate(s) who succeed in meeting the recruitment criteria. This shows that recruitment and selection are determinant factors for them.

It also shows that the overall average agreement of the respondents with regard to training and development was 2.98 (SD = 0.985). The mean result indicates that the

respondents' feelings towards this statement indicate moderate agreement. It shows that the respondent was not in full agreement, but more than a little on the training and development of the organization. These show the training and development of the organization are relatively adequate, but they aren't as good as expected. This shows that the organization does not provide enough training and development for their employees, and the administration must focus more on training and development to address assessment issues, which means if there is a moderate level, there are no strong criteria for training new employees to develop in a new position. This causes the employee to be dissatisfied with their work and leave the organization. One of the biggest impacts of learning and development on employee engagement is that it boosts employee confidence. When employees are provided with the necessary training and development opportunities, they feel more confident in their abilities to perform in their roles. This shows that training and development are determinants.

Training is a set of activities planned on behalf of an organization that increase job knowledge and skills or modify the attitudes and social behavior of organizational members to align with organizational goals and job requirements (Kraiger, 2017). The development portion of training refers to employees' personal growth, seen in newly learned abilities and skills that can translate into their jobs. Most organizations invest in T&D so employees can remain competitive and viable within their roles. Not only will ongoing T&D aid employees in being competitive in the workplace, but ongoing T&D will also allow companies to compete with others in their industry. With many training opportunities available, people who search for opportunities are more likely to advance in their careers.

Performance appraisal also shows that the overall average agreement of the respondents with regard to the mean was 3.22 (SD = 1.013). The mean result indicates that the respondents' feelings towards this statement indicate moderate agreement. It shows that the respondent was not in full agreement, but more than a little on the performance management of the organization. This shows the performance management of the organization isn't as good as expected. This shows that the organization did not measure the performance of the employees as expected. This means there is no strong policy for measuring the performance of the employee. This shows that performance appraisal is a determining factor for them.

As shown in Table 4:2, the respondent's agreement with the overall average agreement with regard to the reward and compensation mean was 2.35 (SD = 0.967). The mean result indicates that the respondents' feelings towards this statement indicate moderate agreement. It shows that the respondent was not in full agreement, but more than a little on the reward and compensation of the organization. These show the reward and compensation are relatively adequate, but they aren't as good as expected. This means the organization did not reward and recognize the employee for good achievement. This means if there is a moderate level, there are no strong criteria for the reward and compensation of the organization and also no strong criteria for reward and compensation for the employee who has a good achievement in the organization. This shows that recruitment and selection are determinant factors for them.

4.3 Result of Inferential Statistics

4.3.1 Correlation Analysis

Correlation refers to a synonym for association or the relationship between variables. It measures the degree to which two sets of data are related. A higher correlation value indicates a stronger relationship between both sets of data. (Coetzee, 2003) Correlation simply indicates the presence of a relationship between two variables but does not imply one is a cause of another variable (Robert & Richard , 2008). When the correlation is 1 or -1, a perfectly linear positive or negative relationship exists; when the correlation is 0, there is no relationship between the two sets of data. Coetzee (2003) noted that when considering the correlation between the independent variable and the dependent variables, the larger the magnitude of the correlation, the stronger the linear association. The standard correlation coefficient is Pearson's r , which applies primarily to variables distributed more or less along interval or ratio scales of measurement. According to Nandini (2005), the strength can be assessed by these general guidelines: values of ± 0.1 represent a small effect, ± 0.3 represent a medium effect, and ± 0.5 represent a large effect. To interpret the direction and strengths of relationships between variables, the guidelines suggested by Alwadaei (2010) (2010) were followed. His classification of the correlation coefficient (r) is: 0.1–0.29 is weak; 0.3–0.49 is moderate; and > 0.5 is strong.

4.3.2 The Relationship between HRMPP and employee performance.

Table 4-4 Correlations between HRM Practice and employees' performance

		E/in achieve gals	Recruitment &Selection	Training & development	Performanc e appraisal	Reward and Compensatio	Employee's performanc
Effectiveness in achieving goals.	Pearson Correlation	1					
	Sig. (2-tailed)						
Recruitment and Selection	Pearson Correlation	.690**	1				
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000					
Training and development.	Pearson Correlation	.534**	.788**	1			
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000				
Performance appraisal	Pearson Correlation	.544**	.727**	.814**	1		
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000			
Reward and Compensatio	Pearson Correlation	.331**	.285**	.469**	.435**	1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000		
Employee's performance	Pearson Correlation	.421**	.547**	.703**	.777**	.320**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	

	N	291	291	291	291	291	291
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** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: Survey Result 2023

The results in Table 4.3 indicate the result of a statistical test for the correlation of independent (i.e., evaluation criteria, recruitment and selection, training and development, performance appraisal, and reward and compensation with employees' performance) and dependent variables. Employees' performance had a positive and significant relationship since the r values are 0.421 at p 0.01, 0.547 at p 0.01, 0.703 at p 0.01, 0.777 at p 0.01, and 0.320 at p 0.01, respectively. The results show that HRM practices have a significant positive relationship with employee performance. The researcher found that all of the levels of employee performance and HRM practices, such as evaluation criteria, recruitment and selection, training and development, performance appraisal, and reward and compensation, are indicated as high. The researcher also found that HRM practices such as training and development, compensation and benefits, performance appraisals, and work-life policies are positively related to employee performance. Thus, the findings of the study have achieved the research objectives, which are to determine the level of employee performance, the level of HRM practices, and the relationship between HRM practices and employee performance. Current data provides sufficient evidence for employers or human resources departments to help them plan the most appropriate solutions to improve employee performance.

The results also show that recruitment policy has a significant positive relationship with training and development ($r=0.788^{**}$) with a significant level of 0.000. This correlation

coefficient value is high. Because of this, recruitment policy and training and development have a strong relationship and are positively correlated. Therefore, recruitment policies have a positive relationship with training and development. This study confirms the results found in previous studies about the positive correlation between these practices and employees' performance. For example, the study by Akhtar et al. (2014) showed a positive relationship between training practices, other HRM practices, and organisational performance. Moreover, recruitment, selection, and training practices were found to be positively correlated with the EP in the study by Tessema & Soeters (2006). Other studies also gave the same impression about the importance of the practices mentioned in the study. However, it is important to conduct such research at different times, especially in the GCC countries, where the effects of external factors can be devastating and affect the results. Many employees lost their jobs in the region in the last two years, and others suffered salary reductions. Such problems affect the performance of the employees badly. A recent study by Hamza et al. (2021) in another Arabic region investigated the relationship between recruitment and selection and organisational performance. They emphasised the importance of selection methods. Another recent study by Alajlani and Yesufu (2022) examined the relationship between HR practices and employee retention as one of the performance dimensions in higher education institutions in the UAE. They found that HR practices can improve employee retention. Our study, however, is more general about the nature of organisations and the dimensions of employee performance.

Table 4:3 shows that the correlation coefficient (r) between performance appraisal with reward, and commission management is 0.435** with a significant level of 0.000. This correlation coefficient value is positive and moderate relationship. Managing the

performance of the employee is important to distinguish the strong workers from weak to provide reward and compensation for strong workers. Therefore, performance appraisal has a positive relationship with reward commission management.

This study is consistent with the study by Sattar et al. (2015), which suggests that training has a positive and significant impact on employee performance. Moreover, this result is consistent with Tanveer et al. (2011), who found that training effectiveness is positively related to employee performance. Besides, the findings of this study are also supported by a previous study conducted by Falola et al. (2014), which stated that training and development are a much-needed strategic tool to improve employee performance. Organizations increase their training budgets each year and believe that this will enable them to gain a competitive advantage. The results show that there is a close relationship between training and development and employee performance. Furthermore, past research conducted by Tahir et al. (2014) also indicated that training and development have a significant relationship with employee performance. Moreover, there is a moderately positive correlation between compensation and benefits and employee performance. This result is consistent with Tessema and Soeters (2016) report of a positive relationship between compensation practices and employee performance. Besides, this study was also consistent with previous studies conducted by Hassan (2016), which indicated that a compensation system based on excellence is the most effective HRM practice as it encourages high employee performance. Furthermore, the finding of this study is supported by a previous study conducted by Hameed et al. (2014), which observed that compensation has a positive impact on employee performance and, if well managed, will result in organizational performance.

The results of training and development have a significant positive relationship with performance management $r = 0.814^{**}$ with a significant level of 0.000. This correlation coefficient value represents a positive and strong relationship. Employee performance must be managed in order to provide training to those who perform poorly and to promote those who perform well. Therefore, performance appraisal has a positive and strong relationship with training and development in the Addis Ababa Police Commission. One of the implications for managers in this context of conducting performance appraisal and training and development programmers is that the managers should stay attentive to the fact that only those employees who perceive these HRM practices as fair and beneficial tend to commit and, in turn, have lower turnover tensions. This supports the study of Abdullah et al. (2011). Where it is proven that performance appraisal motivates and contributes to the turnover intentions of an employee. On the other hand, in the aspect of training, the study of Tannenbaum, Mathieu, Salas, and Cannon-Bowers in 1991 also supports the findings that the level of commitment escalates when they are exposed to training as they feel more confident about themselves. The more committed the employees were, the more they desired training. Thus, the performance appraisal and training and development programmers should be tailored in a way to attain the maximum possible confidence of the employees. According to Li and Butler (2004), the confidence of employees in the performance appraisal can be gained by getting them involved in the process of making choices relevant to their tasks. In this way, employees would be able to autonomously participate (self-reported performance) in the overall performance appraisal process and would feel satisfied with the performance appraisal procedure (Cawley, Keeping, & Levy, 1998).

The findings also suggest that organizations may deploy HRM practices among employees by providing training courses and other career development programmes to enhance their skills and abilities. To gain the confidence of the employees in the performance appraisal system, their involvement in the performance management process should be encouraged, and they should be well educated about how to monitor and evaluate their own performance. Moreover, provision and reception of feedback regarding performance appraisal should take place at all the superior-subordinate tiers and not only at the top. Foon, Leong, and Osman (2010) explain further by reinstating employees' low commitment and its detrimental effect if proper strategies and practices are not practiced, which subsequently increases turnover intention in the organization. In addition, the findings of this study on organizational commitment and turnover are justified by several past studies where there is a negative relationship between organizational commitment and turnover intention (Salleh, Nair, & Harun, 2012). This means that the turnover rate can be lowered through the development of a committed workforce. The findings of this study explore and contribute to the understanding of the effects of the HRM practices of performance appraisal, training, and development on individual employees in terms of organizational commitment and turnover intention, as well as the factors that may affect the perceptions of employees about the extent of fairness and justice in the policies deployed. One of the implications for managers is that they should incorporate satisfaction factors into the processes of performance appraisal, training, and development.

4.4 Diagnosis Test

Before applying regression analysis, some tests were conducted in order to ensure the appropriateness of data to assumptions regression analysis.

4.4.1 Linearity Test

Linearity refers to the degree to which the change in the dependent variable is related to the change in the independent variables. To determine whether the relationship between the independent variable human resource policy and practice (Effectiveness in achieving goals, Recruitment and Selection, Training and development, Performance appraisal and Reward and Compensation) and the dependent variable i.e. Employee's performance linear; plots of the regression residual through SPSS software had been used.

Figure 4-1 Normal Point Plot Standardized Residual

Source: Fieldwork ;(2023)

The scatter plot of residuals shows no larger difference in the spread of the residual as you look from left to right on figure 4.1. This result suggests the relationship we are trying to predict is linear. Similarly, the above figure shows the normal distribution of residuals around its mean of zero. Hence the normality assumption is fulfilled as required based on the above figure, it is possible to conclude that the inference that the researcher made about the population is somewhat valid.

4.4.2 Normality Test

Figure 4:2 shows the frequency distribution of the standardized residuals compared to a normal distribution. Although, there are some residuals (those occurring around 0) that are relatively far away from the curve, many of the residuals are fairly close. Moreover, the histogram is bell shaped which lead to infer that the residuals are normally distributed.

Figure 4-2 Frequency Distribution of Standardized Residual

Source: Fieldwork ;(2023)

4.4.3 Multicollinearity Test

After the normality of the data in the regression model was met, the next step to determine whether there is similarity between the independent variables in a model, it is necessary to multicollinearity test. Similarities between the independent variable will result in a very strong correlation. In addition, multicollinearity tests done to avoid habits in decision making process regarding the partial effect of independent variables on the dependent variable. Test multicollinearity as a basis the VIF values of multicollinearity test results using SPSS.

This assumption assumes that the independent variables are not highly correlated with each other. The collinearity of two variables means that a strong correlation exists between them, making it difficult or impossible to estimate their individual regression coefficients reliably. A VIF above 4 or a tolerance below 0.25 indicates that multicollinearity might exist, and further investigation is required. When VIF is higher than 10 or tolerance is lower than 0.1, there is significant multicollinearity that needs to be corrected. This assumption is tested by the variance inflation factor (VIF) statistic as follows:

Table 4-5 Collinearity Statistics

Items	Tolerance	VIF
Effectiveness in achieving goals.	0.494	2.024

Recruitment and Selection	0.252	3.963
Training and development.	0.231	4.335
Performance appraisal	0.309	3.234
Reward and Compensation	.712	1.405

Source: Survey Result 2023

Based on the coefficient output- Collinearity statistics, obtained VIF value of independent variable i.e. Human resource policy Effect in achieving goals (2.024), Recruitment and Selection (3.963), Training and development (4.335), Performance appraisal (3.234) and Reward and Compensation (1.405). The values obtained from collinearity statistics (VIF) was between 1 and 10. Therefore, it can be concluded that there are no multicollinearity symptoms between the components of the independent variables. Thus, from an examination of the information presented in all the three tests the researcher concluded that there are no significant data problems that would lead to say the assumptions of classical linear regression have been seriously violated

4.4.4 Regression Analysis

Linear regression is used when we want to predict the value of a variable based on the value of another variable. According to Marczyk (2005), linear regression is a method of estimating or predicting a value for some dependent variable given the values of one or more independent variables. In simple regression, we have only two variables; one variable defined as independent is the cause of the behaviour of another, defined as a dependent variable. Since the result provides only the direction and significance of the

relationship between variables, multiple regression analysis was employed to examine the effect of training dimensions on employee performance.

4.4.5 The combination of HRMPP & Employee performance for the Development

4.4.5.1 Multiple Linear Regressions

The concepts and principles developed in dealing with simple linear regression (i.e., one explanatory variable) may be extended to dealing with several explanatory variables.

Table 4-6 Model Summaries

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	0.796a	0.634	0.628	0.52102

- a. Predictors: (Constant), Reward and Compensation, Recruitment and Selection, Effectiveness in achieving goals (evaluation criteria), Performance appraisal, Training and development.
- b. Dependent variable Employee's performance

Source: Survey Result 2023

From the above table, 4:3 R (0.796 or 79.6 percent) simply shows the Pearson correlation among variables, which means there is a strong correlation between dependent variables and independent variables. R squared = 0.634 means almost 63.4 percent of the variation in employee performance can be predicted by the independent variables (human resource practice). The remaining 36.6 percent can be explained by

other factors that are not in the model. The larger R² is better (Pallant, 2010). And the value of the adjusted R square is 0.628, which represents 62.8% of the significant contribution of the five independent variables towards the dependent variable. Adjusted R square is always less than R² because it takes degree of freedom into consideration, and the larger the adjusted R square, the better. And the smaller the mean standard error (SME), the better (0.52102).

Generally, R² is the percentage of variation in employee performance explained by the variable human resource management practice effectiveness. Approximately 63.4 percent of the variation in employee performance can be explained by variable human resource management practice effectiveness.

From Table 4.5 above, the correlation between training design and employee performance is 0.796a. Additionally, the R square and adjusted R square values of the simple linear regression are 0.634 and 0.628, respectively. This is interpreted as 63.4% of variance in employee performance being explained by training design, while 36.6 % of variation in employee performance can be attributed to other variables that are not considered in this study. If another factor is presented, it would further explain 62.8%, as shown by the adjusted R square.

4.4.5.2 ANOVAa

Table 4-7 ANOVAa Model Summary

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	134.169	5	26.834	98.850	.000b
	Residual	77.366	285	.271		

	Total	211.536	290			
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a. Dependent Variable: Employee's performance

b. Predictors: (Constant), Reward and Compensation, Recruitment and Selection, Effectiveness in achieving goals (evaluation criteria), Performance appraisal, Training and development.

Source: Survey Result 2023

In a regression model, the ANOVA F statistic tests whether the model as a whole is significant or not. The F-statistic of 98.850 at 5 and 285 degrees of freedom is statistically significant at a 99% confidence level. The table determines a satisfactory result as the significance level of the model is not over or smaller than 0.05. Thus, the model used in this dissertation is statistically significant.

4.4.5.3 Multiple Regression Analysis

Table 4-8 Coefficientsa

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.	Result
		B	Std. Error	Beta			
		1	(Constant)	1.320			
	Evaluation criteria.	.052	.045	.059	1.150	.251	Rejected
	Recruitment and Selection	-.226	.070	-.231	-3.236	.001	Accepted

	Training and development.	.312	.065	.360	4.826	.000	Accepted
	Performance appraisal	.555	.054	.658	10.215	.000	Accepted
	Reward and Compensation	-.078	.038	-.089	-2.086	.038	Accepted

a. Dependent Variable: Employee's performance

Source: Survey Result 2023

Multiple Regression Equations:

$$Y = C + \beta X_1 + \beta X_2 + \beta X_3 + \dots + \beta X_n$$

Y = prediction relationship of types of variables towards performance.

C is the constant value.

β is the unstandardized coefficient.

X = independent variable (effectiveness in achieving goals, recruitment and selection, training and development, performance appraisal, reward, and compensation).

Based on the above table, we were able to derive the following equation:

$$Y = 1.320 + 0.052X_1 + -0.226X_2 + 0.312X_3 + 0.555X_4 + -0.078X_5$$

This can be interpreted as indicating that an increase of 1 unit in effectiveness in achieving goals may result in a rise of 5.2% units in employee performance. However, for the independent variable of training and development, every 1 unit increase will incur a raise of 3.12% units in the dependent variable, employee performance. On the other hand, a 1 unit increase in performance appraisal may cause 55.5% units of employee performance to increase.

Finally, recruitment and selection and reward and compensation variables have a negative relationship with employee performance retention in this module test.

4.4.5.4 The effect of Recruitment policies on training & development

Table 4-9 Model Summaries

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted Square	RStd. Error of the Estimate
1	.788a	.622	.620	.60707

a. Predictors: (Constant), Recruitment and Selection

b. Dependent variable: training and development

Source: Developed from the research 2023

According to the model summary above, the R square value had gain 0.622, which are 62.2 percent. These mean that 62.2% of dependent variable of training and development can be explained by independent variable Recruitment and Selection. It will conclude that 37.8% (100% -62.2%) of dependent variable of training and development is explained by other potential factors. The value of adjusted R square with value of 0.620 which 62% represented the significant contribution of the independent variable toward dependent variable.

Table 4-10 Coefficientsa of recruitment on training and development

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients	Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
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		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.469	.121		3.883	.000
	Recruitment and Selection	.889	.041	.788	21.785	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Training and development.

Source: Developed from the research 2023

This can be interpreted that the increase of 1 unit of Recruitment and Selection may incur the raise of 0.889 units in Training and development. The highest beta indicates the independent variable is the most significant variable toward its dependent variable.

4.4.5.5 The effect of performance appraisal on reward, and compensation management

Table 4-11 Model Summary of PA on reward & compensation management

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted Square	R Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.435a	.189	.186	.87241

a. Predictors: (Constant), Performance appraisal

Source: Developed from the research 2023

According to the model summary above, the R square value had gain 0.186, which are 18.9 percent. These mean that 18.9% of dependent variable of reward, and compensation management can be explained by independent variable Performance

appraisal. It will conclude that 81.1% (100% - 18.9%) of dependent variable of reward, and compensation management is explained by other potential factors. The value of adjusted R square with value of 0.186 which 18.6% represented the significant contribution of the independent variable toward dependent variable.

Table 4-12 the Coefficientsa of performance appraisal on reward, and compensation management

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.014	.170		5.948	.000
	Performance appraisal	.415	.051	.435	8.209	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Reward and Compensation

Source: Developed from the research 2023

This can be interpreted that the increase of 1 unit of Performance appraisal may incur the raise of 0.051 units in Reward and Compensation. The highest beta indicates the independent variable is the most significant variable toward it dependent variable.

4.4.5.6 The effect of Performance management on Training and development

Table 4-13 Model Summary effect of Performance management on Training and development

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted Square	RStd. Error of the Estimate
1	.814a	.662	.661	.57371

a. Predictors: (Constant), Performance appraisal

Source: Developed from the research 2023

According to the model summary above, the R square value had gain 0.662, which are 66.2 percent. These mean that 66.2% of dependent variable of Training and development can be explained by independent variable Performance appraisal. It will conclude that 33.8% of dependent variable of Training and development is explained by other potential factors. The value of adjusted R square with value of 0.661 which 66.1% represented the significant contribution of the independent variable toward dependent variable.

Table 4-14 Coefficientsa

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.440	.112		3.924	.000

	Performance appraisal	.791	.033	.814	23.790	.000
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a. Dependent Variable: Training and development.

Source: Developed from the research 2023

This can be interpreted that the increase of 1 unit of Performance appraisal may incur the raise of 0.791 units in Training and development. The highest beta indicates the independent variable is the most significant variable toward its dependent variable.

4.5 Discussions of Major Findings

Table 4-15 Summaries of Results

Hypothesis	Predictors	Correlation				Regression		
		r-value	p-Value	Degree of correlation	Status	B-value	P-value	hypothesis Status
H1	HRPP & EP	0.796	0.000	Strong relation	Accepted	0.052	0.000	Accepted
H2	RPO & TD	0.792	0.000	Strong relation	Accepted	0.889	0.000	Accepted
H3	PA & RCM	0.435	0.000	Moderate relation	Accepted	0.415	0.000	Accepted
H4	TD & PM	0.814	0.000	Strong relation	Accepted	0.791	0.000	Accepted

Source: Survey Result 2023

H1: Human resource policy have a positive relationship with the effect of the performance of human capital in the Addis Ababa police commission. From the hypothesis testing, it shows that there is a significantly positive relationship between the independent variable human resource policy and the dependent variable employee performance. The value of 0.807 indicates that human resource policy are positively correlated with employee performance. However, $p = 0.000$ ($p > 0.05$). Hence, H1 is supported.

According to Lim & Nurazwa (2021), the results showed that the level of employee performance and the level of HRM practices were high, and there was a positive relationship between HRM practices and employee performance. The managers determine the best combination of HRM practices, which include training and development, compensation and benefits, performance appraisals, and work-life policies, and help improve employee performance by developing effective strategies for these practices.

According to Chumpon et al. (2020), the findings of the study show that all the human resource management practices have a significant and positive relationship with employee performance, and job satisfaction mediates the relationship among variables. According to the results, all the hypotheses are accepted and provide a significant and positive relationship among variables, including reward and compensation, and employee performance. Although training and development and performance appraisal are more closely related, employee performance and job satisfaction also increase more as compared to other developing countries.

H2: There is a positive and significant relationship between recruitment policy and training and development at the Addis Ababa Police Commission. From the hypothesis

testing, it shows that there is a significantly positive relationship between independent variable recruitment and selection and independent variable training and development. The value of 0.792 indicates that recurrence and selection are positively correlated to training and development, and its p-value is 0.000 ($p < 0.05$). Hence, H2 is supported.

According to Novita (2019), the results of the coefficient of determination (R^2) indicate that recruitment and job training affect employee performance by about 35.7%. The results also show that recruitment and job training have a positive and significant effect on employee performance. According to Rashed, Khalfan, and Ahmad (2022), the recruitment and selection of employees have a significant impact on the performance of organizations and are of great importance if the organization hopes to succeed. Consequently, recruitment practices determine the quality of the new recruits, and the selection process is inherently determined by the quality of the candidates it attracts. And training and development are considered to be the most common human resources practices (Tzafrir, 2006). It is any effort to improve future employees' skills, abilities, and knowledge (Ashwathappa, 2006). Training and development constitute an ongoing process in any organization. "Training is the formal and systematic modification of behavior through learning that occurs as a result of education, development, and planned experience (Armstrong, M, 2001).

H3: Human resource policy and practice have a positive and significant relationship with training and development and employee performance. From the hypothesis testing, it shows that there is a significantly positive relationship between independent variable training and dependent variable employee performance. The value of 0.708 indicates that training is positively correlated with employee performance, and its p-value is 0.000 ($p < 0.05$). Hence, H3 is supported.

According to Meseret (2022), training and development are methods of updating the mentality of the workers and motivating them to stay in the organization. The absence of training and development may cause the demotivation of the workers. When they are confident and motivated to perform a task, they are more likely to be committed to their job, which reduces the turnover rate. Alemayehu (2017) shows that the trainers didn't deliver the training as expected by the trainee, and the employees' performance level was average since they were not comfortable with the present design and delivery of the training program. The trainees will reach the desired level of performance if the training is well designed and delivered. The other finding of the study shows that delivery style also has a positive and significant relationship with employee performance. Mohammed (2022) also revealed that training design, training needs assessment, training delivery style, and training evaluation have a significant positive effect on employees' performance. And Abeba's (2015) study also shows that training and development have a positively correlated and statistically significant relationship with employee performance and effectiveness. According to the 2009 American Public Transportation Association, organizations should provide sufficient training programmers for employee development to upgrade their employees. Hence, it can show that employee training is important for employee performance in any industry.

H4: There is a significant and positive relationship between reward management and employee performance. From the hypothesis testing, it shows that there is a significantly positive relationship between the independent variables reward and compensation and the dependent variable employee performance. The value of 0.328 indicates that reward and compensation are positively correlated with retention, and its p-value is 0.00 ($p < 0.01$). Hence, H4 is supported.

Reward and competitiveness to attract competent employees and individual equity to upgrade employee performance and retain top talent can be created by a fair reward compensation system. Employees may feel that they are appreciated by the organization for their performance and contributions if they get a good salary (Lai, 2011). Hence, they are motivated to contribute more or perform better for the organization. Indirectly, they tend to remain in the organization since they are valued.

Reward and compensation are not only the return and benefits for the work done, but they also reflect their accomplishments (Ali, 2009). Therefore, an effective reward compensation system should be designed to compensate employees. The compensation system is particularly important for intelligence-intensive industries like educational institutions because competent employees are the core capabilities or resources of the enterprises (Lai, 2011).

4.6 Discussions of Interview Results

The post-questionnaire interview result was obtained with 32 participants, including human resource managers and other managers related to the human resource policy and practice impact on employee performance. While the interviewees were interviewed, notes were taken individually, and the outcomes are discussed in this section for exploratory purposes.

The work performance of the members in the office is very good, but the benefits given to the employees by the office are not commensurate with their work. But one job criteria that should be fulfilled is that he should have stood up in his work as a human being. Work performance is evaluated every six months and three months of the year. There is no additional benefit given to the employee beyond the military salary, which is not proportional to the shortcomings of the work in terms of living conditions. Lack

of salary in the workplace means no reward is given, and recognition is given through acquaintance and presentation.

The salary and benefits system is being implemented according to the commission's guidelines and regulations, among other systems. The benefits provided by the organisation are not the same as those of other sub-district police departments. Salary and benefits are low, especially since the institution is zero in terms of recognition. Those benefits provided by the commission, like milk, transportation, house rent, and telephone, are not enough according to work conditions.

The salary, benefits, recognition, and promotion are not equivalent to the working conditions of police officers; the salary payment of officers is low when compared to other civil servants. The service of the police is to provide peace and security for the city; there is not any organisation providing their service. There is no equivalent benefit for an officer's accordance with their work.

Effective recruitment and selection by the organisation are not significant and appropriate contributions to the office if they are done with attention.

There is no effective recruitment and selection for officers. If a policeman is properly recruited, selected, and trained, he will be fired. But leadership and members who go to recruitment will not be recruited as per the office's requirements. This makes the morale of employees very low because they are not recruited through studies but as temporary work. If recruitment is done in a good way, the problems related to ethics and discipline will be solved, and if training is provided sufficiently, regular job training is also good.

The organisation leaders attract, select, and filter during the training, hiring the right talent for the organisation, but the work environment and condition of the salary and reward system make officers rude criminals to the organisation.

In order to solve the overall process of the reward and compensation system in the organisation, the Commission shall study and submit it to the Ministry for approval.

The government's reward and compensation are in accordance with the city administration's reputation and the service of police officers. In a salary context, the police organisation is a low-payer when compared to other civil servants. The service of the police is to provide for the peace and security of the city; there is not any organisation providing their service. But their salary is so low that the officers leave the organisation to get the best benefit for their survival. To retain the police officers in the organisation, it is important for the police commission to study and submit to the Ministry the salary scale applicable to police officers and implement the same upon approval by the government.

In particular, if on-the-job training is given to encourage people who are working properly, they should also talk honestly. If organisation leaders see all employees as equals and solve them honestly when they encounter different problems. Give priority to educated people; if only all things were measured by results.

There should be educational opportunities for the employees to increase their capacity so that they can undergo long and intensive training. The organisation should provide different training every season on capacity building for employees to do better work and make them learn about education for further development.

If the organisation has a consultant, good performance will be created. The rules and guidelines set by the organisation will be implemented, and there will be good performance.

To increase work motivation, there should be appropriate awards for growth, education, and other enlightenment, among others.

The problems encountered in the work of the office are many. Those are: protecting the employee's rights by informing those concerned about the organisation's rights and obligations will reduce obstacles; otherwise, it will increase obstacles.

Lack of capacity, lack of education, and lack of employment are due to a lack of employment with the leader and not treating all people equally.

The non-recognition and non-permanence of the work done by the institution is an obstacle to work, as it is done only in the eyes of the people and in an uncomfortable work environment. There is pressure from the boss, and there is no communication with the employee.

2.6 Summary

CHAPTER FIVE

5. SUMMARY OF MAJOR FINDINGS, CONCLUSIONS, AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Summary of the Major Findings

This sub-section presents the key results of the study. The prescription of the findings followed the pattern of both the research objective and the sequence of the data presentation and analysis as follows:

The human resource management policy and practices of the Addis Ababa Police Commission, With regard to the sex of the respondents, the majority were males. This clearly points out that, sexually, the members of the police force were dominated by males, and the responses given for the current study might be subjected to the perception of the male respondents. This shows that human resource management policy and practice do not well implement affirmative action during requirements and selection. The majority of respondents' ages fell between the age groups of 18 and 30, which is a higher number of young people. This shows that human resource management practices are not well implemented among all HR practices, and because of that, there are high numbers of police officer turnovers in the organization. With reference to the experience of the respondents, almost all were under 20 years of age and served in the organisation, but when we see the reward of the organisation according to Regulation No. 268, 2012, the police commission rewarded medals, ribbons, and certificates to be awarded to police officers on the basis of outstanding accomplishments of missions and meritorious services, which shall be determined by federal police administration regulation for those above 15 years. This shows that on

one side, because of the high turnover, they need to attract employees to retain them in the organisation to wait for the reward.

The effect of human resource management policies at the Addis Ababa Police

Commission: The overall average agreement of the respondents with regard to the evaluation criteria of effectiveness in achieving the organisational goals of the human resource management policy of the Addis Ababa Police Commission head office was moderate. This result indicates the feelings of respondents towards statements. It shows that the respondent was not in full agreement but more than a little on the evaluation criteria of effectiveness in achieving organisation goals, which means if there is a moderate level, there are no strong evaluation criteria for effectiveness in achieving organisation goals and employee performance. These show the effectiveness of achieving goals (evaluation criteria) is relatively adequate, but it isn't as good as expected, and the administration focus more on evaluation criteria to address assessment issues.

The extent to which human resource management policies affect the Employee's

performance: The overall average agreement of the respondents with regard to recruitment and selection, training and development, performance appraisal, reward, and compensation was moderate. It shows that the respondent was not in full agreement and was relatively adequate, but they weren't as good as expected.

The relationship between human resource management policy and practice and employee performance and the correlation found that all of the levels of employee performance and HRM practices, such as evaluation criteria, recruitment and selection, training and development, performance appraisal, and reward and compensation, are indicated as high. The researcher also found that HRM practices such as training and

development, compensation and benefits, performance appraisals, and work-life policies are positively related to employee performance. Thus, the findings of the study have achieved the research objectives, which are to determine the level of employee performance, the level of HRM practices, and the relationship between HRM practices and employee performance. Current data provides sufficient evidence for employers or human resources departments to help them plan the most appropriate solutions to improve employee performance.

The combination of human resource policies on employee performance for development: The Pearson correlation among variables means there is a strong correlation between dependent variables and independent variables. R squared = 0.634, which means almost 63.4 percent of the variation in employee performance can be predicted by the independent variables (human resource practice). The remaining 36.6 percent can be explained by other factors that are not in the model. The larger R² is better (Pallant, 2010). And the value of the adjusted R square is 0.628, which represents 62.8% of the significant contribution of the five independent variables towards the dependent variable. Adjusted R square is always less than R² because it takes degree of freedom into consideration, and the larger the adjusted R square, the better. And the smaller the mean standard error (SME), the better (0.52102). Generally, R² is the percentage of variation in employee performance explained by the variable human resource management practice effect. Approximately 63.4 percent of the variation in employee performance can be explained by variable human resource management practice effect.

5.2 Conclusions

The objective of this study was to investigate the effect of human resource management policies and practices on employee performance.

Accordingly,

The HRMP do not well implement affirmative action during requirements and selection

There is a high turnover of police officers in the organisation,

The organization does not attract employees to retention in the organisation to wait for the reward.

There is a problem on evaluation criteria for effectiveness in achieving organisation goals and employee performance

The HRMP was moderate affect the Employee's performance:

The relationship between HRMP with employee performance indicated as high. The combinations of human resource policies and employee performance for development, The Pearson correlation among variables means there is a strong correlation between dependent variables and independent variables. The R squared of almost 63.4 percent of the variation in employee performance can be predicted by the independent variables (human resource practice). The remaining 36.6 percent can be explained by other factors that are not in the model. The adjusted R square shows 62.8% of the significant contribution of the five independent variables to the dependent variable.

5.3 Recommendations

On the basis of the findings and conclusions reached, the following recommendations are forwarded in order to improve the human resource management policy and practice of the Addis Ababa Police Commission.

- The Addis Ababa Police Commission should prioritize the implementation of gender diversity initiatives to address the male-dominated composition of the police force. This could involve targeted recruitment strategies and the creation of a more inclusive work environment to attract and retain female employees.
- To improve communication and reduce workplace pressure, the commission should foster open channels of communication between supervisors and employees. Regular feedback sessions, team meetings, and training programs on effective communication can contribute to a more cohesive and supportive work environment.
- Leadership development within the HR function should be a key focus for the commission. Providing training and resources for HR professionals to lead organizational transformation and change initiatives effectively is essential for driving positive employee performance.
- Regular evaluations of human resource management policies and practices should be conducted to ensure alignment with best practices and the evolving needs of the workforce. This will enable the commission to adapt and refine its HR strategies to meet the changing demands of the organization.
- The commission should prioritize continuous learning and development opportunities for employees. Offering training programs, mentorship

opportunities, and career advancement pathways can contribute to improved employee performance and job satisfaction.

- The implementation of performance management systems that align individual and team goals with organizational objectives is crucial. Clear performance expectations, regular feedback, and recognition and rewards for high performance can motivate employees and enhance overall performance.
- Establishing a supportive and confidential feedback mechanism for employees to raise concerns and provide suggestions for improving HR policies and practices is essential. This will enable the commission to address employee needs and make informed decisions to enhance the effect of its human resource management policies and practices.
- The Addis Ababa Police Commission should consider establishing a dedicated team or committee to oversee the implementation and monitoring of the recommended HR management practices and policies. Finally, the commission should prioritize the creation of a supportive and confidential feedback mechanism for employees to raise concerns and provide suggestions for improving HR policies and practices.

5.4 Recommendations for Further Research

This study limited itself to only one organisation, the Addis Ababa Police Commission head office; recommendations are therefore made for further research in the different organisations and other duty stations in order to broaden research by incorporating alternative factors and variables in explaining the effect of human resource management policy in improving employee performance. This study was conducted at

the Addis Ababa Police Commission head office; therefore, the results of this study also compared with studies in alternative industries, such as the service sector, in different contexts. Future studies should investigate these limitations to produce more insights into the effect of human resource management policy and practice at the Addis Ababa Police Commission head office.

REFERENCE

- Disciplining social media. (2012). *An analysis of social media policies in 26 Swedish municipalities*".
- "Building a compliance department". (2022). *Thomson Reuters*. Retrieved 20 January 2022.
- Abdullah, A., Bilau, A., Ajagbe, A., Ali, K. N, K., & Enegbuma, W. (2011). *Evaluation of Job Satisfaction and Performance of Employees in Small and Medium Sized Construction Firms in Nigeria. 2 nd International Conference on Construction and Project*.
- Abeba, M. A. (2015). *The Impact of Training and Development on Employee Performance and Effectiveness: A Case Study of District Five Administration Office, Bole Sub-City, Addis Ababa, Ethiopia*.
- Abeha, B., & Bariha, B. (2012). *Effect of employees training on the organizational competitive advantage in private sector of. Far East Journal of Psychology and Business*, 6 (1), 59–72.
- Abetie, T. (2010). *The Assessment of Recruitment and Selection Practice: The Case of Federal Police*.
- ACC. (2016). *"Top Ten Tips for Developing an Effective Code of Conduct"*. Association of Corporate Counsel. Archived from the original on 7 September 2018. Retrieved 10 February 2016.
- Adam, M. (2018). *The role of human resource management (HRM) for the implementation of sustainable product-service systems (PSS)—an analysis of fashion retailers. Sustainability*. 2018;10(7):2518. doi:10.3390/su10072518.
- Adebaby , A. (1998). *Checklist of common personnel/Human Resource Management Problems in the Ethiopian Civil Service*’, *Merit: Ethiopian Federal Civil Service Quarterly Bulletin*, Addis Ababa, 3, no.4:27.

- Aggarwal, , e. (2020). *Gen Z entering the workforce: Restructuring HR policies and practices for fostering the task performance and organizational commitment. Journal of Public Affairs, hlm. 1–18.*
- AIHR. (2022). "A Practitioner's Guide to Organizational Effectiveness". AIHR. 2020-12-07. Retrieved 2022-03-27. .
- Aizza , A. A., Shakeel, K., & Hassan. ((2018).). *Impact of intrinsic and extrinsic motivation on Employee's retention: A case from call center. International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences, 8(6), 652-666.*
- Akhtar, N., Azeem, S., & Mustafa , M. (2014). *Impact of HRM practices on perceived organizational performance. International Journal of Academic Research, 6(5). doi:10.7813/2075-4124.2014/6-5/B.3.*
- Akram, A., Ungku, N., & Khalid, A. (2016). *The Impact of Human Resource Management Practices (HRMPs) on Employee's Performance at Islamic University of Gaza, (IUG) in Palestine. International Review of Management and Marketing, 2016, 6(4), 1080-1088.*
- Aktar, S., Sachu, M. K., & Ali, M. (2012). *The impact of rewards on employee performance in commercial banks of Bangladesh: An empirical study. IOSR Journal of Business and Management, 6(2), 9–15. https://doi.org/ 10.9790/487X-0620915.*
- Alajlani, S., & Yesufu, L. (2022). *The impact of human resource practices on employee retention: A study of three private higher educational institutions in the United Arab Emirates. SA Journal of Human Resource Management, 20, 10. doi:10.4102/sajhrm.v.*
- Alemayehu , M. S. (2017). *Effects of Training on Employee Performance in Ethiopia Revenue and Customs Authority at Customs procedure Sector.*
- Alemayehu, M. S. (2017). *Effects of Training on Employee Performance in Ethiopia Revenue and Customs Authority at Customs procedure Sector. Addis Ababa.*

- Alwadaei, S. (2010). *Employee's perception of, and satisfaction with, performance Appraisal*.
- Armstrong , Michael ; Murlis, Helen. (2004). *Reward Management. 5th ed. London: Kogan Page Limited*.
- Armstrong, G. L., & Gerber, S. (2016). *Human metapneumovirus circulation in the United States, 2008 to 2014. Pediatrics, 137(5)*.
- Armstrong, M. (2001). *A Hand book of Human Resource Management Practice', London: Kogen Page*.
- Armstrong, M. (2001). *A Hand book of Human Resource Management Practice', London: Kogen Page*.
- Armstrong, M. (2014). *Handbook of human resource management practice (13 ed.)*. Kogan Page Limited.
- Armstrong, M. (2001). *Human Resource Management Practice. London: Kogan Page. p. 290. ISBN 0749433930*.
- Armstrong, M. (2009). *Human Resource Management Practice. (11th edition), Kogan Page ltd, London and Philadelphia*.
- Armstrong, M. (2020). *Handbook of human resource management practice. Kogan Page*.
- Armstrong, M; Brown, D. (2001). *New dimensions in pay management. CIPD Publishing*.
- Armstrong, M; Murlis, H. (2007). *Reward management: A handbook of remuneration strategy and practice. Kogan Page Publishers*.
- Armstrong, M; Stephens, T. (2005). *Employee reward management and practise: first edition. Great Britain and United States: Kogan page Limited*.
- Armstrong, M; Taylor, S. (2014). *Armstrong's Handbook Of Human Resource Management Practice. 13th edn. London: Kogan Page*.

- Arul , K. S. (2017, SEPTEMBER). A conceptual framework of human resources practices and policies in private sector. *ZENITH International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, Vol.7 (9)(ISSN 2231-5780), 1-9.
- Asfaw, A., Argaw, M., & Bayissa, L. (2015). *The Impact of Training and Development on Employee Performance and Effectiveness: A Case Study of District Five Administration Office, Bole Sub-City, Addis Ababa, Ethiopia*. *Journal of Human Resource and Sustainability Studies*, 3, 188-202.
- Ashenafi, A. (2018). *A Comparative Study of Factors Affecting Teachers' Motivation between Selected Government And Private Secondary Schools In Addis Ababa City*(master thesis, Addis Ababa University).
- Ashwathappa, K. (2006). *Human Resource Management (3rd Ed.)*: Tata McGraw Hills, New.
- Assefa , D. (2019). *Assessment of Human Resource Management Practice in Ethiopian Broadcasting Corporation*. ADDIS ABABA Ethiopia.
- Aydogan, E., & Arslan, O. (2021). *HRM practices and organizational commitment link: Maritime scope*", *International Journal of Organizational Analysis*, Vol. 29 No. 1, pp. 260-276.
- Barman, T., & White, S. (2016). *"Implementing an effective corporate ethics policy"*. *Chartered Global Management Accountant (CGMA) Magazine*. Retrieved 10 February 2016.
- Barton, A., & Skiba, D. (2012). *Creating social media policies for education and practice*". *NI 2012: 11th International Congress on Nursing Informatics, June 23–27, 2012, Montreal, Canada*. *International Congress in Nursing Informatics (11th: 2012: Montreal*.

- Bataineh, K. A. (2017). *The Impact of Electronic Management on the Employees' Performance. Journal of Management and Strategy*, 8(5), 86-100. <https://doi.org/10.5430/jms.v8n5p86>.
- Batarlienė, N., Čižiūnienė, K., Vaičiūtė, K., & Šapa. (2017). *The Impact of Human Resource Management on the Competitiveness of Transport Companies. Procedia Engineering*, 87, 110-116. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.proeng.2017.04.356>.
- Bazezew, M. (2017). *The Effect of Nonfinancial Reward on Employee Retention: The case of United Bank S.C.*
- Beer, M., Spector, B., Lawrence, P., Mills, D., & Walton, R. (2005). *A conceptual view of HRM in managing human assets. Free Press, New York.*
- Begashaw, T. (2017). *The Role of Effective Compensation and Reward System on Employee Performance in the Case of Commercial Bank of Ethiopia.* Addis Ababa, Ethiopia.
- Begashaw, T. (2017). *The Role of Effective Compensation and Reward System on Employee Performance in the Case of Commercial Bank of Ethiopia.*
- Bhatt, P., & Reddy, C. (2011). *HRM practices and its impact on performance – exploratory literature review in the context of indian smes. NJRIM*, 1(2), 73-87.
- Biruk, H. (2019). *Impact of Training on Employee Performance: In Case of Ethiopian Police University College.*
- Boxall, P., & Purcell, J. (2011). *Strategy and Human Resource Management. Macmillan International Higher Education; 2011.*
- Boxall, P; Purcell, J; Wright, P. (2007). *The Oxford Handbook of Human Resource Management, Oxford University Press.*
- Bratton, J., & Gold, J. (2017). *Human Resource Management: Theory and Practice: Palgrave; 2017.*

- Bratton, J; Gold, J. (2001). *Human resource management theory and practice*. Hound Mills.
- Bratton, J; J., Gold. (2007). *Human Resource Management Theory and Practice*, New York: Palgrave.
- Bruktawit , M. A. (2006). *The effect of compensation and reward on employee performance: the case of management sciences for health – Ethiopia*.
- Burma, Z. (2014). *Human resource management and its importance for today's organizations*. *International Journal of Education and Social Science*, 1(2), 85-92.
- Cawley, B., Keeping, L., & Levy, P. (1998). *Participation in the performance appraisal process and employee reactions: a meta-analytic review offield investigations*. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 83, 615-631. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1037/0021-9010>.
- Chemeda, D. (2012). *A Comparative Study of Employees Performance Appraisal Practices and Problems in Ethiopian Higher Education Institutions: The Case of Addis Ababa University and St. Mary University College*.
- Chen, C.-J., & Huang, J.-W. (2009). *Strategic human resource practices and innovation performance—the mediating role of knowledge management capacity*. *J Bus Res*. 2009;62(1):104–114. doi:10.1016/j.jbusres.2007.11.016.
- Chumpon, , R., Anunya , T., Tawatchai, S., & Pawintana , C. (2020). *Effect of Human Resource Management Practices on Employee Performance Mediating by Employee Job Satisfaction*.
- Coetzee, O. (2003). *The Relationship between Personality Variables and Work Performance of Credit Controllers in a Bank*. Pretoria.
- Collings, D. G., & Wood, G. (2009). *Human resource management: A critical approach*. In D. G. Colligs & G. Wood (Eds.), *Human resource management: A critical approach* (pp. 1-16). London: Routledge.

- Cooper, D. J., & Ezzamel, M. (2013). *Globalization discourses and performance measurement systems in a multinational firm. Accounting, Organizations and Society, 38, 288-313.*
- Costante, E., Sun, Y., Petković, M., & den, 2. H. (2012). *A machine learning solution to assess privacy policy completeness". Proceedings of the 2012 ACM Workshop on Privacy in the Electronic Society - WPES '12: 91. doi:10.114.*
- Council, F. H. (2017). *Why Your Business Needs A Social Media Policy And Eight Things It Should Cover". Forbes.*
- Daft, R. (2015). *Organization theory and design. Boston: Cengage Learning.*
- Daniel , Tadesse Tulu. (2020). *Human Resource Management Practices and Reflective Organizational Performance-A Focus on Public Offices of Ambo Town, Oromia, Ethiopia (ደዘኛ. Vol.68, 2020).*
- Daniel, T. T. (2020). *The study to examine human resource management practices vis-a-vis organization performance in the case of public organizations in Ambo town.*
- Daud, N. (2006). *Human resource management practices and firm performance: the moderating roles of strategies and environmental uncertainties. Universiti Sains Malaysia.*
- Dawit, T. A. (2019). *Assessment of Human Resource Management Practices and Challenges in Selected Construction Projects: A Study in Jimma Town.*
- Dawson, C. (2007). *A practical guide to research methods: A users friendly manual for mastering research techniques and projects. How To Books.*
- de Menezes, L. M., & Escrig, A. B. (2019). *Managing performance in quality management A two-level study of employee perceptions and workplace performance. International Journal of Operations & Production Management, 39(11), 1226-1259. https://doi.org/10.1.*

- De Miranda Castro, M. V., de Araujo, M. L., Ribeiro, A. M., Demo, G., & Meneses, P. M. (2020). *Implementation of strategic human resource management practices: A review of the national scientific production and new research paths. Rev. Gestão 2020, 27, 229–246.*
- Decenzo, D., & Robbins, S. (2010). *Fundamentals of Human Resource Management. Canada: Jhon wiley & Sons, Inc.*
- Degu, M. Z. (2010). *Evaluation of personnel management capabilities of the federal police of Ethiopia in Addis Ababa.*
- Dessler, G. (2005). *A Framework for Human Resources Management. Prentice-Hall.*
- Dessler, G. (2007). *Human resource management (10th Ed.): Pearson prentice Hall- united state of America.*
- Dessler, G. (2008). *Human Resource Management (11th edition), Prentice Hall, of India Private Ltd, New Delhi. (Unpublished master"s thesis). Indira Gandhi National Open University, - 110 068, Maidan G arh New- Delhi.*
- Devender, S. (2014). *HR Practices and Job Performance Journal Of Humanities And Social Science . Volume 19, Issue 4, Ver. I PP 55-6.*
- Dictionary.com, L. (2011). *"Effectiveness | Define Effectiveness Dictionary.com." Dictionary.com | Find the Meanings and Definitions of Words at Dictionary.com. 2011. Web. 28 Sept. 2011. <<http://dictionary.reference.com/browse/effectiveness>>.*
- Dirk , J. van Wasbeek. (2004). *Human Resource Management Practices in Selected Ethiopian Private Companies: A Study to Increase Employee Productivity in Ethiopia. Addis Ababa Ethiopia.*
- Dirk, J. W. (2004). *Human Resource Management Practices in Selected Ethiopian Private Companies: A Study to Increase Employee Productivity in Ethiopia.*

- Doig, A., & Wilson, J. (1998). "Business Ethics: A European Review Volume 7, Issue 3, July 1998". *Business Ethics: A European Review*. 7 (3): 140–149. doi:10.1111/1467-8608.00100.
- Drucker, P. (2012). *The practice of management*. Routledge.
- Edward, E., & John , B. (2012). *Effective Human Resource Management, Paperback ISBN: 9780804776875 Ebook ISBN: 9780804782685*.
- Edwards, M. (2009). 'HR, Perceived Organizational Support and Organizational Identification: An Analysis After Organizational Formation,' *Human Resource Management Journal*, 19, 1,91 – 115.
- Ekwoaba, J., Ikeije, U., & Ufoma, N. (2015). *The Impact of Recruitment and Selection Criteria on Organizational Performance Global Journal of Human Resource Management. March 2015 Published by European Centre for Research Training and Development UK*. 3(.
- Elnaga, A., & Imran, A. (2013). *The Effect of Training on Employee Performance. European Journal of Business and Management*, 5, 137.
- Elnaga, A; Imran, A. (2013). *The effect of training on employee performance. European Journal of Business and Management*, 5(4), 137–147 <https://www.iiste.org/Journals/index.php/EJBM/article/view/4475>.
- Esayas , Y. (2019). *The effect of selected human resource management practices on employees' turnover intention: the case of civil employees of Ethiopian federal police commission*. Addis Ababa, Ethiopia.
- Esayas, Y. (2019). *The effect of selected human resource management practices on employees' turnover intention: the case of civil employees of Ethiopian federal police commission*.
- Esete , M. (2019). *Effect of reward practices on employees' performance: a case study on Zemen bank S.C*.

- Etzioni, A. (1964). *Modern Organizations*. Englewood Cliffs, NJ: Prentice-Hall.
- Evans, S., & Tourish, D. (2017). *Agency theory and performance appraisal: How bad theory damages learning and contributes to bad management practice*. *Management Learning*, 48(3), 271-291.
- Fikru, W. (2022). *The effect of police job stress on their performance: in the case of the Ethiopian federal police commission*.
- Fisseha , G. (2019). *Ethiopia Human resource management practice and challenges: the case of organization for social services health and development*. Addis Ababa,.
- Foon, Y., Leong, L., & Osman, S. (2010). *An exploratory on turnover intention among private sector employees*. *International Journal of Business and Management*, 5, 57-64. <http://dx.doi.org/10.5539/ijbm.v5n8p57>.
- Forbes, D. P. (1998). "Measuring the Unmeasurable: Empirical Studies of Nonprofit Organization Effectiveness from 1977 to 1997". *Nonprofit and Voluntary Sector Quarterly*. 27 (2): 183–202. doi:10.1177/0899764098272005. S2CID 145657794.
- Gamage, A. (2014). *Recruitment and Selection Practices in Manufacturing SMEs In Japan”: An Analysis Of The Link With Business Performance”*. *Ruhuna Journal of Management and Finance*, 1(1), 37-52.
- Garavan, T. (1997). *Training, Development, Education and Learning: Different or the Same?* *Journal of European Industrial Training*, 21, 39-50. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1108/03090599710161711>.
- Garavan, T., McCarthy, A., & Carbery, R. (2020). *Training and organisational performance: A meta-analysis of temporal, institutional and organisational context moderators*. *Human Resource Management Journal*, 31 (1), 93–119. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1748-8583.12284>.

- Getachew, E. (2016). *Practices and Challenges of Human Resource Management in Major General Muluget Buli Technical College*.
- Getachew, Z., & Abebe, T. (2019). *Work motivation and its effects on organizational performance: the case of nurses in Hawassa public and private hospitals:(master thesis, Hawassa University)*.
- Gold, J., & Bratton, J. (2003). *The Dynamics of Professionalization: Whither the HRM Profession*. In *Critical Management Studies Conference (Vol. 2, No. 3, pp. 17-22)*.
- Goldstein, I., & Ford, J. (2002). *Training in organizations: Needs assessment, development and evaluation (4th Ed.)*, Belmont, CA: Wadsworth.
- Habtamnesh , G. (2019). *Effect of Recruitment and Selection Practices on Organizational Performance in the Case of United Bank S.C*.
- Hadji, S. (2022). *Diagnosing of human resource performance management based on lack of ambidextrous learning themes: a case study of public Iranian banking system*. *International Journal of Ethics and Systems, ahead-of-p(ahead-of-print)*.
- Hamza, P., Othman, B., Gardi, B., Sorguli, S., Aziz, H., Ahmed, S., ወ.ዘ.ተ. (2021). *Recruitment and Selection: The Relationship between Recruitment and Selection with Organizational Performance*.
- Hodson, R. (2002). *Management Citizenship Behavior and its Consequences,* *Work and Occupations*, 29, 1, 64 – 96.
- Holmes, E. (2005). *Anti-Discrimination Rights Without Equality". Modern Law Review*. 68 (2): 175–194. doi:10.1111/j.1468-2230.2005.00534.x. ISSN 0026-7961.
- Hughes, A., Zajac, S., Woods, A., & Salas, E. (2019). *The role of work environment in training sustainment: A meta-analysis*. *Human Factors*, 62(1), 166–183. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0018720819845988>.

- Huq, A. Z. (2017). "*Judging Discriminatory Intent*". Rochester, NY. SSRN 3033169. .
- Hussain, M., & Ahmad, M. (2012). *Mostly discussed research areas in human resource management (HRM) – a literature review. International Journal of Economics and Management Sciences, 2(3), 10-17.*
- Isaac, O., Abdullah, Z., Ramayah, T., & Mutahar, A. (2017). *Internet usage, user satisfaction, task-technology fit, and performance impact among public sector employees in Yemen. The International Journal of Information and Learning Technology, 34, 210-.*
- Islami, Mulolli, & Mustafa. (2018). *Using Management by Objectives as a performance appraisal tool for employee satisfaction. Future Business Journal, 4(1), 94-108.*
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fbj.2018.01.001>.
- Ivancevich, J. (2004). *Human Resource Management”, 9th Edition, in the McGraw-Hill Irwin, Companies, New York.*
- Jamrog, J. (2005). *Measuring Organizational Effectiveness: Canadian Management Centre Special Report.* (online)
<http://www.cmctraining.org/reg/wp/MeasuringOrganizationalEffectiveness.pd>.
- Jiang, K., Lepak, D., Baer, J., & Hu, J. (2012). *How does human resource management influence organizational outcomes? A meta-analytic investigation of mediating mechanisms. Acad Managet J. 2012;55 (6):1264–1294. doi:10.5465/amj.2011.0088.*
- Jiménez, J., & Valle , R. (2005). *Innovation and human resource management fit: An empirical study. International Journal of Manpower, 26(4), 364-381. https://doi.org/10.1108/01437720510609555.*
- Johnason, P. (2009). *HRM in changing organizational contexts. In D. G.Collings & G. Wood (Eds.), Human resource management: A critical approach (pp. 19-37). London: Routledge.*

- Kaplan, I., & Denno, R. (2007). *Interspecific interactions in phytophagous insects revisited: a quantitative assessment of competition theory*. *Ecology letters*, 10(10), 977-994.
- Khan, A., Abbasi, S., Waseem, R., Ayaz, M., & Ijaz, M. (2016). *Impact of training and development of employees on employee performance through job satisfaction: A study of telecom sector of Pakistan*. *Business Management and Strategy*, 7(1), 29. .
- Khan, M. (2010). *Effects of human resource management practices on organizational performance: An empirical study of the oil and gas industry in Pakistan*. *European Journal of Economics, Finance and Administrative Sciences*, 24(6), 157–174.
- Khan, R. G., Khan, F. A., & Khan, M. A. (2011). *Impact of training and development on organizational performance*. *Global Journal of Management and Business Research*, 11(7), 63–68. <https://journalofbusiness.org/index.php/GJMBR/issue/view/55>.
- Kothari, C. (1984). *Quantitative Techniques, 2nd ed.*, New Delhi: Vikas Publishing House Pvt. Ltd.
- Lajara, B. M., Lillo, F. G., & Sempere, V. S. (2003). *Human resources management: A success and failure factor in strategic alliances*. *Employee Relations: Management Research News*, 31(9), 683 – 696.
- Levit, N. (2012). *Changing Workforce Demographics and the Future of The Protected Class Approach*". Rochester, NY. SSRN 2033792. .
- Li, A., & Butler, A. (2004). *The effects of participation in goal setting and goal rationales on goal commitment: An exploration of justice mediators*. *Journal of Business and Psychology*, 19, 37-51. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1023/B:JOBU.0000040271.74443.22>.
- Lim, C. T., & Nurazwa , A. (2021). *The Relationship between Human Resource Management Practices and Employee Performance*.
- Lotta, L. (2012). *Case Study: The Impact of Financial and Non Financial Rewards on Employee Motivation*. Turku University of Applied Sciences.

- Malik, M., Ghafoor, M., & Naseer, S. (2011). *Organizational Effectiveness: A Case Study of Telecommunication and Banking Sector of Pakistan*. *East Journal of Psychology and Business*, 2, 37-49.
- McConnell, John. (2005). *How to develop Essential HR Policies and procedures*. USA: American Management Association. pp. 5. ISBN 0814408273.
- McCormick, M. (2011). *New Privacy Legislation.*" *Beyond Numbers* 427 (2003): 10-. *ProQuest*. Web. 27 Oct. 2011 .
- McMillan, M. (2016). "Codes of Ethics: If You Adopt One, Will They Behave?". *Enterprising Investor: Practical analysis for investment professionals*. Retrieved 10 February 2016.
- Mensah, J. K. (2018). *Talent Management and Employee Outcomes: A Psychological Contract Fulfilment Perspective*. *Springer Science+Business Media*, 19, 325-344. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11115-018-0407-9>.
- Mergel, I., & Bretschneider, S. I. (2013). *A Three-Stage Adoption Process for Social Media Use in Government*" (PDF). *Public Administration Review*. 73 (3): 390–400. doi:10.1111/puar.12021.
- Meseret, A. A. (2022). *The effect of non-monitory rewards on employee retention, the case of Lideta sub-city land development and management*.
- Michael, A. (2001). *A Handbook of Human Resource Management Practice*. London: Kogan Page. p. 289. ISBN 0749433930.
- Michael, A. (2010). *Performance Management*. 3rd ed. London and Philadelphia: Kogan Page Limited.
- Mohammadi, S. F. (2017). *Designing a performance management model with a human resources development approach in the public sector*", *Quarterly Journal of Human Resources Training and Development*, Vol. 15 No. 4, pp. 133-153.

- Mohammed, H. Y. (2022). *Impact of training on employees performance: A case study of Bahir Dar university, Ethiopia.*
- Morris, N., & Jane, M. (2017). *The Influence of Performance Management System on Employee Performance in Commercial Banks in Kitui Town, Kitui County, Kenya. International Journal of Humanities and Social Science Vol. 7, No. 6.*
- MSH. (2013). *Human Resource Management Assessments in Ethiopia: Synthesis Report.* Addis Ababa: Management Sciences for Health, September 10, 2013.
- Muchinsky, P. (2012). *Psychology Applied to Work (10th ed.). Summerfield, NC: Hypergraphic Press.*
- Nandini, D., & Caroline, R. (2005). Correlation and Regression. *American journal of Roentgenology*, vol. 185: pp. 3-18.
- Negash, R., Zewude, S., & Megersa, R. (2014). *The effect of compensation on employees motivation in Jimma University academic staff. Basic Research Journal of Business Management and Accounts, Volume 3(2), pp. 17-27.*
- Nguyen, D., Ha, V., & Dang, T. (2020). *The impact of human resource management activities on compatibility and work results. Journal of Asian Finance, Economics, and Business, 7(9), 621–629. <https://doi.org/10.13106/jafeb.2020.vol7.no9.62>.*
- Niati, D. R., Siregar, Z., & Prayoga, Y. (2021). *The Effect of Training on Work Performance and Career Development: The Role of Motivation as Intervening Variable. Budapest International Research and Critics Institute (BIRCI-Journal): Humanities and and Social Sciences, 4(2), 2385–2393.*
- Noe, B. A., & Hollenbeck, J. (2019). *Fundamentals of human. Fundamentals of human resource management (8th ed.). McGraw-Hill Education..*
- Novita , W. S., Dyah , A. S., & Udin. (2019). *The Effect Of Recruitment And Training On Employee Performance.*

- O'Dea, Thomas. (2017). *How to Write a Culture-First Employee Handbook" (PDF)*. Blissbook.
- Oladejo, M., & Yinus, O. (2014). *An Assessment of the impact of Compensation Plan on workers Performance of selected Quoted Food and Beverages Manufacturing Companies in Nigeria. Journal of Business and Management. Volume 16, Issue 7. Ver. I, PP 05-12.*
- Ombui, K., Elegwa, M., & Gichuhi, A. (2014). *The Influence of Recruitment and Selection on the Performance of Employees in Research Institutes in Kenya Nairobi. International Journal of Science and Research, Volume 3, Issue 5.*
- Pain, R. A. (2014). *Reasonable Accommodations Are A Pain, But Litigation Is A Bigger Pain, HR Advisors, 2007, retrieved February 1, 2014 .*
- Pallant, J. (2010). *SPSS Survival Manual. 4th edition, McGraw Hill.*
- Paul Jackson, R. S. (2004). *e-Business and Workplace Redesign (2004), p. 37.*
- Pawirosumarto, s., Sarjana, P. K., & Gunawan, R. (2017). *The effect of work environment, leadership style, and organizational culture towards job satisfaction and its implication towards employee performance in Parador Hotels and Resorts, Indonesia. Intern.*
- Peters, T., & Waterman, R. (1982). *In Search of Excellence, Harper & Row, New York.*
- Pravin, D. (2010). *Human Resource Management. India: Dorling Kindersley (India) Pvt. p. 133. ISBN 9788131724842.*
- Proclamation No. 720. (2011). *Ethiopian Federal Police Commission Establishment Proclamation.... Page 6203. 8th Year No.2 ADDIS ABABA 28th November, 2011.*
- Propper, C., & Wilson, D. (2003). *The use and usefulness of performance measures in the public sector. Oxford review of economic policy, 19(2), 250-267.*

- Quresh, T., Akbar, A., Khan, M., Sheikh, R., & Hijazi, S. (2010). *Do human resource management practices have an impact on the financial performance of banks? African Journal of Business Management*, 4(7), 1281–1288. <https://academicjournals.o>.
- Qureshi, M., Tahir, R., Mohammad, M., & Zubair, A. (2007). *Impact of Human Resource Management (HRM) Practices on Employees Performance*, Muhammad Ali Jinnah University, Islamabad.
- Raja, A., Furqan, A., & Muhammad, A. (2011). *Impact of Training and Development on Organizational Performance*. Global Journals Inc. USA: Volume 11 Issue 7 Version 1.0 .
- Rashmi, R., & Umesh, M. (2017). *Impact of Rewards on Employee Performance: A Case of Indian Oil Corporation, Patna Region*. *Journal of Business and Management*. Volume 19, Issue 6. Ver. II, PP 22-30.
- Reasons Employees Get Fired. (2013). *BeingFired.com*. Archived from the original on 2013-08-18. Retrieved 2013-11-29. .
- Reed, R., & Vakola, M. (2006). *What roles can train needs analysis play in organizational change? Journal of Organizational Change Management*, 19, 393–407.
- Regulation No. 268. (2012). *Federal Police Officers Administration Council of ministers Regulation, 19" Year No .1 ADDIS ABABA 19th November. 2012. Page 6599. Annex Page 6637. .*
- Resource, D. o. (2014.). *Definition of Human Resource investopedia.com*. Investopedia. Retrieved 1 February 2014.
- Richard, O. C., & Johnson, N. B. (2001). *Strategic human resource management effectiveness and firm performance*. *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 12(2), 299 – 310.

- Rizwan, Q., & Ali, U. (2010). *Impact of Reward and Recognition on Job Satisfaction and Motivation. An Empirical Study from Pakistan. International journal of business and management.*
- Robert, B., & Richard, A. (2008). *Business Research Methods and Statistics Using SPSS. Sage Publications Ltd, London EC1Y 1SP.*
- Ruttledge, & Cathcart. (2019). *An evaluation of sensory processing training on the competence, confidence and practice of teachers working with children with autism. Irish Journal of Occupational Therapy, 47(1), 2–17. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJOT-01-2019-0001>.*
- Salas, E., Wilson, K., Priest, H., & Guthrie, J. (2006). *Training in organizations: The design, delivery and evaluation of training systems. In G. Salvendy (Ed.), Handbook of human factors and ergonomics (3rd ed., pp. 472–512). Hoboken, NJ: John Wil.*
- Salleh, R., Nair, M., & Harun, H. (2012). *Job Satisfaction, Organizational Commitment, and Turnover Intention: A Case Study on Employees of Retail Company in Malaysia. International Journal of Social, Education, Economics and Management Engineering, 6(.*
- Sanderson, J. (2011). *To Tweet or Not to Tweet: Exploring Division I Athletic Departments' Social-Media Policies". International Journal of Sport Communication. 4 (4): 492–513. doi:10.1123/ijsc.4.4.492.*
- Sarma, A. (2008). *Personnel and Human Resource Management. Himalaya Publishing House.*
- Schuler, R. S., & Jackson, S. E. (2020). *Linking competitive strategies with human resource management practices. Acad. Manag. Perspect. 2020, 1, 207–219.*
- Seicshnaydre, S. E. (2007). *Is the Road to Disparate Impact Paved With Good Intentions? -- Stuck on State of Mind in Antidiscrimination Law". Rochester, NY. SSRN 1015317. .*
- Selamawit, A. (2016). *The Effect of Performance Appraisal on Employee's Performance in Commercial Bank of Ethiopia Jimma District.*

- Selznick, P. (1957). *Leadership and Administration*, Row, Evanston, Ill.
- Shah, M. M. (2020). *The Development Impact of PT. Medco E & P Malaka on Economic Aspects in East Aceh Regency. Budapest International Research and Critics Institute- Journal (BIRCI-Journal) Volume 3, No 1, Page: 276-286.*
- Shah, N., Irani, Z., & Sharif, A. M. (2017). *Big data in an HR context: Exploring organizational change readiness. Journal of Business Research, 70, 366-378. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2016.08.010>.*
- Shiferaw, D. F. (2013). *A Thesis on Assessment of the Human Resource Management Practices in Ethiopian Public Health Association (EPHA).*
- Shipton, H., Fay, D., West, M., Patterson, M., & Birdi, K. (2005). *Managing people to promote innovation. Creativity and Innovative Management, 14(2), 118-128. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-8691.2005.00332.x>.*
- Shoaib, M., Noor, A., Tirmizi, S., & Bashir, S. (2009). *Determinants of employee retention in telecom sector of Pakistan. Proceedings of the 2nd CBRC, Lahore, Pakistan, 14(1), 1-18.*
- Sianoja, M., Kinnunen, U., De Bloom, J., Korpela, K., & Geurts, S. (2016). *Recovery during Lunch Breaks: Testing Long-Term Relations with Energy Levels at Work". Scandinavian Journal of Work and Organizational Psychology. 1. doi:10.169.*
- Smith, M., & Bititci, U. S. (2017). *Interplay between performance measurement and management, employee engagement and performance. International Journal of Operations, 37(9), 1207-1228. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJOPM-06-2015-0313>.*
- Springer. (2018). *Comparative Perspectives on the Enforcement and Effectiveness of Antidiscrimination Law - Challenges and Innovative Tools | Marie Mercat-Bruns | Springer. Ius Comparatum - Global Studies in Comparative Law. Springer. 2018. ISBN 9783319900674. .*

- Stone, R. J. (2008). *Human Resource Management (6th edition)*. John Wiley & Sons, Australia.
- Sulich, A. (2016). "Mathematical models and non-mathematical methods in recruitment and selection processes". *Reviewed Papers from 17th International Conference. Mekon 2015. 1. ISBN 978-80-248-3684-3. .*
- Tannenbaum, S. I. (2002). *A strategic view of organizational training and learning*. In K. Kraiger (Ed.), *Creating, implementing, and maintaining effective training and development: State-of-the-art lessons for practice* (pp. 10–52). San Francisco, CA: Joss.
- Teclmichael , T. M., & Soeters, J. (2006). *Challenges and prospects of HRM in developing countries: testing the HRM–performance link in the Eritrean civil service*. *International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 17(1), 86–105. doi:10.1080/0958.
- Teece, D. (2007). *Explicating dynamic capabilities: the nature and micro- foundations of (sustainable) enterprise performance*. *Strategic Manage J.* 2007;28(13):1319–1350. doi:10.1002/(ISSN)1097-0266.
- Tehitna, M. (2021). *The Role of Employee Recruitment and Selection on the Organization Performance, the Case of Wegagen Bank,.*
- Tehitna, Melkamu. (2021). *The Role of Employee Recruitment and Selection on the Organization Performance, the Case of Wegagen Bank, St. Mary's University.*
- Thomas, H. (2020). *Employee Recruitment and Selection Practices in Oromia Region. (The case of EEPCO of Adama Branch).*
- Tigist, S. (2022). *Impact of Human Resource Management Practices on Employee Performance: The Case of Bule Hora University, Ethiopia, Africa.*

- Travail Legal Database: . (2014). *Working Time in the Africa Region*". *Travail: Conditions of Work and Employment Programme. International Labour Organization. Retrieved 1 October 2014.*
- Trsit , G. (2018). *The effect of performance appraisal practice on employee performance: the case of goal Ethiopia.*
- Tyskbo, D. (2020). *Line management involvement in performance appraisal work: Toward a practice-based understanding. Employee Relations: The International Journal.*
- Wage Indicator" (PDF). (2016). *Archived from the original on 22 February 2016. Retrieved 17 January 2019.*
- Web finance, I. (2011). *"Privacy Policy". Archived from the original on 22 August 2013. Retrieved 23 October 2011. .*
- Wei, L. Q., & Lau, C. M. (2005). *Market Orientation, HRM Importance and Competency: Determinants of strategic HRM.. The International Journal of HRM.*
- Werdhiastutie, A. (2020). *Achievement Motivation as Antecedents of Quality Improvement of Organizational Human Resources. Budapest International Research and Critics Institute-Journal (BIRCI-Journal) Volume 3, No 2, Page: 747-752.*
- WorldatWork. (2007). *The WorldatWork Handbook of Compensation, Benefits & Total Rewards. New Jersey : John Wiley & Sons, Inc..*
- Yang, H. (2008). *'Efficiency Wages and Subjective Performance Pay'*, *Economic Inquiry*, 46(2), pp. 179–196.
- Yeshihareg , A. (2019). *The Effect of Human Resource Management Practice on Perceived Employee Performance: The Case of Ministry of Trade and Industry, Ethiopia.*

Zahari, G. (2019). Human resources management in the police system. *International Journal of Economics, Commerce and Management*, Vol. VII(Issue 2, February 2019 Licensed under Creative Common), 188.

Zehara , K. (2021). *The effect of compensation and reward on employee performance: the case of wegagen bank, Addis Ababa city branches.*

Zhang, Y. (2012). *The Impact of Performance Management System on Employee Performance -Analysis with WERS 2004 (Master's thesis, University of Twente).*

APPENDIX

GELILA INTERNATIONAL SEMINARY

DEPARTMENT MANAGEMENT AND LEADERSHIP

QUESTIONNAIRE TO BE FILLED BY EMPLOYEES OF ADDIS ABABA POLICE COMMISSION HEAD OFFICE

Dear respondents,

The main purpose of this questionnaire is to collect data for the study on the effectiveness of human resource management policy and practice on employees' performance in the case of the Addis Ababa Police Commission head office. It will be used to prepare a dissertation as a partial fulfilment of the requirement for the degree of doctor of philosophy in management and leadership. You (the respondent) are kindly requested to read the questions thoroughly and respond accordingly. The result of this assessment will be treated with the utmost confidentiality and will be strictly used for academic purposes only.

Thank you in advance for your cooperation!

Part I: Respondents' Background Information

Directions: Please put (√) mark in the appropriate box.

1. Gender; Male Female
2. Age, 18-25 26-30 31-40
3. Current position; Commissioner Directorate Division
Coordinator Team Team Leader Officer

4. Educational Background; MA/MS and above BA/BS Diploma/
Level 1 to 4 Grade 10/12 Complete Below Grade 10/12
5. Work Experience; Below 5 years from 6-10 years From 11-
15years From 16-20 years From 16-20 years From 26 and
above years.

Part II: Human Resource Management policy and Practices

Directions: Read the following statements and express your degree of agreement/
disagreement with human resource management practices by ticking (√) the appropriate
column.

Note that Strongly Agree (5), Agree (4), Moderately Agree (3), Disagree (2), And
Strongly Disagree (1).

No	Items	Answer				
		1	2	3	4	5
1.	Effectiveness in achieving goals (evaluation criteria)					
1.1	HR shows change leadership by initiating transformation first within the HR function					
1.2	HR demonstrates understanding of the theory and tools of change (Provides a model of change that can be used throughout the organization)					
1.3	HR plays a leading role in the communication of change (any type of					

	change) in the organization.					
1.4	HR ensure the effective evaluation (measurement) of employee's readiness to deal with organizational change					
1.5	HR timeously / proactively takes the lead in change projects					
1.6	HR serves as a facilitator in change projects					
1.7	HR provides continuous support to employees during change projects					
2.	Recruitment and Selection					
2.1	The organization has a formal written policy to guide the overall recruitment and selection functions					
2.2	Jobs and vacancies are always made open to general public in the organization					
2..3	Adequate and relevant information about the organization and job is provided to the candidate at the time of recruitment.					
2.4	The organization considers existing employees first for filling vacant positions.					
2.5	The requirement mentioned in the job announcement match with what is actually required.					
2.6	I am satisfied with the actions I observe at recruitment time.					

2.7	The organization places the right person in the right job.					
2.8	The organization provides equal employment opportunity for all regardless of gender, race, ethnic group, religion.					
2.9	The recruitment and selection practice leads to the employment of competent staff.					
3.	Training and development.					
3.1	Good opportunities are available to take job related trainings which adequately address the skill gaps and ensure job effectiveness.					
3.2	Incompetent employees are identified and provided with the necessary training.					
3.3	The training that I take meets the objective of the company.					
3.4	The methods of delivering the training are clear.					
3.5	The content was organized and easy to follow.					
3.6	The training program designed based on the requirements of the job.					
3.7	The training increases our motivation to the job we do.					
3.8	The training improves our skills, knowledge, attitude change, new capability.					
3.9	We satisfied with the overall aspect of the training programs in the					

	organization.					
4.	Performance appraisal					
4.1	I satisfied with the evaluation results that I get.					
4.2	Performance appraisal evaluate employee properly.					
4.3	Information generated through performance evaluation in is used as a basis to warn subordinates about unsatisfactory performance and helps supervisors make discharge or retention decision.					
4.4	I always get the expected results of the performance evaluation whatever I expecting.					
4.5	The evaluation results impact on my behavior, attitudes and morale.					
4.6	When your performance has not met minimum standards, your manager discusses with you the reasons.					
4.7	The performance criteria/instruments used to measure my performance are clearly defined and objective.					
4.8	Performance of the employee may be increased by promoting them.					
4.9	Performance appraisal is used as a decision making tool for the increasing the performance and set promotion standards.					
4.10	The performance evaluation form used to evaluate my performance is customized based on the characteristics of my job.					

5.	Reward and Compensation					
5.1	My Salary in this institution is enough for me.					
5.2	My organization gives competence or skill based pay increment.					
5.3	My organization gives cash bonus based on the surplus made per each period.					
5.4	The organization usually organizes small non-cash awards to staff.					
5.5	Staff to participate in decision making process in relation to reward.					
5.6	My organization Job performance is an important factor in determining the incentive compensation of employees.					
5.7	Our organization, salary and other benefits are comparable to the market.					
5.8	Compensation for all employees is directly linked to his/her performance.					
5.9	There is a reward system based on performance.					
6.	Employee's performance					
6.1	I enjoy my tasks and the division of work approach.					
6.2	I am always committed to the mission and vision of my organization.					
6.3	I love my work and I am motivated to complete the tasks that are					

	assigned to me always.					
6.4	I cooperate well with my colleagues in office.					
6.5	My performance level has direct effect on my salary level.					
6.6	I am given an opportunity to improve my performance through learning more skills.					
6.7	In my organization employees with higher educational qualifications perform better than those with lower qualification.					
6.8	I feel my performance contributes for the growth of my organization.					
6.9	I effectively use resources including time and materials.					
6.10	I serve as many customers as possible and develop logical and creative solution to problems.					

Part III: Interview Questions

1. How do you rate your working performance in the organization? (Low, good, or excellent)

Is it equivalent or not to what you rewarded and composition? Please explain.

2. What do you suggest for the overall process of the reward and compensation system in the Addis Ababa Police Commission head office? (Base pay/salary, benefits, recognition, promotion, overtime payment, and working conditions)

3. Do you think effective recruitment and selection of employees contribute to the Addis Ababa Police Commission head office? Explain

4. In your opinion, how do organisations correct the problems seen in the remuneration, reward, and recognition systems?

5. What do you think your organisation should do to further enhance employee performance?

6. What are some of the factors that affect your performance at work? Explain

7. Are you satisfied with the kind of benefits the organisation provides you?

8. Please explain the benefits provided by the organisation; how important are they to you in terms of your performance at work?

መጠይቅ

መግቢያ፡- «በሠራተኞች ስራ አፈጻጸም ላይ የሰው ኃይል አስተዳደር ፖሊሲና አሠራር ውጤታማነት በሚል ርዕስ በአዲስ አበባ ፖሊስ ኮሚሽን ዋና መ/ቤት የይክተሬት ዲግሪዬን እየሰራሁ ስለሆንኩኝ መጠየቁን በአግባቡ እንድትሞሉ በአክብሮት እጠይቃለሁኝ። ጥናቱ የበለጠ ፍሬያማ ለማድረግ፣ ለተሰጠው ጥያቄዎች ያለዎት ምላሽ መስጠት እንድትባበሩኝ እየጠየቁኝ ለጥያቄ የተሰጡት ሁሉም ምላሽዎ ለምርምር ስራው ብቻ ስለሚውሉ በሚስጥር ይጠበቃል። ጥያቄዎችን በመሙላት ላደረጋችሁት ያልተቆጠበ ትብብር ጥልቅ ምስጋናዬን ማቅረብ እፈልጋለሁ።

ክፍል አንድ፡ የመላሾች ዳራ መረጃ አቅጣጫዎች፡

መመሪያ አንድ

እባክትን ከሚከተሉት አማራጮች ውስጥ ለእያንዳንዳቸው ለርስዎ በጣም ተገቢ ከሆኑ መልሶች ቁጥር ፊትለፊት ባለው ሣጥን ውስጥ የ(✓) ይስጡት።

1. ጾታ፡ ወንድ
2. ዕድሜ 18-25 30
3. ማዕረግ፡ ከረ/ኮሚሽነር እስከ ኮሚሽነር ከም/ኮማንደር እስከ ኮማንደር
ከረ/ኢ/ር እስከ ዋ/ኢ/ር እስከ ዋ/ሣጅን ከንስታብል ሻል
4. ያሉበት ሀገር/ቀበሌ፡ ኮሚሽነር ዳ. ሬት ዲቪዥን ማስተባበሪያ
ቲም የሰው ኃይል ማረጋገጫ
5. የትምህርት ደረጃ፡ ዶክተሬት ሁለተኛ ድግር የመጀመሪያ ድግር
ዲፕሎማ/ደረጃ 1 እስከ 4 /12 ኛ ክፍል ያጠናቀቀ 10/12 ኛ ክፍልና በታች

6. የስራ ልምድ; ከ 5 አመትና በታች ከ [] መት ከ11-15 ከ [] ከ16-
 20 አመት [] ከ21 እስከ 26 ከ26 እ [] ከ31 እና ከዚያ [] []

ክፍል II: የሰው ሀብት አስተዳደር ፖሊሲ እና ተግባራት

ተ/ቁ	ጥያቄዎች	መልሶች				
		1	2	3	4	5
1.	የሰው ሀብት ግቦችን ለማሳካት ውጤታማነት (የግምገማ መስፈርቶች)					
1.2	የሰው ሀብት በሰው ሰራሽ ተግባር ውስጥ በመጀመሪያ ለውጥን በማስጀመር የለውጥ አመራርን ያሳያል።					
1.3	የሰው ሀብት የለውጥ ጽንሰ-ሀሳብን እና መሳሪያዎችን መረዳትን ያሳያል (በአጠቃላይ በድርጅቱ ውስጥ ጥቅም ላይ ሊውል የሚችል የለውጥ ሞዴል ያቀርባል)።					
1.4	የሰው ሀብት በድርጅቱ ውስጥ የለውጥ ግንኙነት (ማንኛውም አይነት ለውጥ) ግንባር ቀደም ሲኖር ይጨምራል።					

1.5	የሰው ሀብት የሰራተኛውን ድርጅታዊ ለውጥ ለመቋቋም ያለውን ዝግጁነት ውጤታማ ግምገማ (መለኪያ) ያረጋግጣል።					
1.6	የሰው ሃይል በጊዜ/በንቃት የለውጥ ፕሮጀክቶችን ይመራል።					
1.7	የሰው ሀብት በለውጥ ፕሮጀክቶች ውስጥ እንደ አስተባባሪ ሆኖ ያገለግላል።					
1.8	የሰው ሀብት በለውጥ ፕሮጀክቶች ወቅት ለሠራተኞች የማያቋርጥ ድጋፍ ይሰጣል።					
2.	ምልመላ እና መረጣ					
2.1	ድርጅቱ ማንኛውም የምልመላ ተግባራትን ለማከናወን የምጠቀምበት ግልጽ የሆነ የፅሁፍ መመሪያ አለው።					
2.2	ድርጅቱ ውስጥ ያሉት ክፍት የስራ መደቦች በየጊዜው ለአባሎች እና ለአመራሮች ክፍት ይሆናሉ።					
2.3	በምልመላ ወቅት ስለ ድርጅቱ እና ስለ ሥራው ሁኔታ በቂ እና ጠቃሚ መረጃ ሁሉ ለተመልሰው ይገለጻል።					
2.4	ድርጅቱ ክፍት የስራ መደቦችን ለመሙላት በቅድሚያ በቦታው ላይ ያሉት ነባር ሰራተኞችን ይመለከታል።					
2.5	በስራ ማስታወቂያ ላይ የተጠቀሰው መስፈርት ከስራው ሁኔታ ጋር ይዛመዳል።					

2.6	በምልመላ ወቅት በአመላመላቸው ግልፅ ድርጊቶች ረክቻለሁ።					
2.7	ድርጅቱ ትክክለኛውን ሰው በትክክለኛው ሥራ ላይ ያስቀምጣል።					
2.8	ድርጅቱ ጾታ፣ ዘር፣ ብሄር ወይም ሃይማኖት ሳይለይ ለሁሉም እኩል የስራ እድል ይሰጣል።					
2.9	የምልመላ እና የአመራረጥ አሰራር ብቃት ያላቸውን ሰራተኞች ወደ ስራ ያስማራል።					
3.	ስልጠና እና ልማት					
3.1	የክህሎት ክፍተቶችን ለመሙላት እና የስራ ውጤታማነትን ለማረጋገጥ ከስራ ጋር የሚያያዙ ስልጠናዎችን ለመውሰድ ጥሩ አጋጣሚዎች አሉ።					
3.2	ብቃት የሌላቸው ሰራተኞች ተለይተው አስፈላጊውን ስልጠና ይሰጣቸዋል።					
3.3	የምወስደው ስልጠና የድርጅቱን ዓላማ ያሳካል።					
3.4	ድርጅቱ ስልጠናውን የሚቀርቡበት ዘዴዎች ግልጽ ናቸው።					
3.5	የስልጠናዎቹ ይዘት የተደራጀ እና ለመከተል ቀላል ነበር።					
3.6	የስልጠና መርሃ ግብር በስራው መስፈርቶች መሰረት የተነደፉ ናቸው።					
3.7	ስልጠናው ለምንሰራው ስራ ያለንን ተነሳሽነት ይጨምራል።					
3.8	ስልጠናው ክህሎታችንን፣ እውቀታችንን፣ የአመለካከት ለውጥን፣ አዲስ					

	አቅማችንን ይቀይርልናል።					
3.9	በድርጅቱ ውስጥ ባለው የስልጠና መርሃ ግብሮች አጠቃላይ ገጽታ ረክተናል።					
4.	የአፈጻጸም ግምገማ					
4.1	በድርጅቱ ውስጥ የስራ አፈጻጸም ምዘና ዓላማ አውቃለሁ።					
4.2	በስራ በአፈጻጸም ምዘና የሚሰጠው ዉጤት ሰራተኞች የት እንዳሉ እንዲያውቁ ግብረ መልስ ለመስጠት ይጠቅማል።					
4.3	በስራ አፈጻጸም ግምገማ የሚሰጠው ዉጤት አጥጋቢ አፈጻጸም የለላቸውን ሰራተኞችን ለማስጠንቀቅ እና ለመሪዎቹ የማስጠንቀቅ ወይም የመቅጣት ውሳኔ ለመስጠት ይጠቅማል።					
4.4	በስራ አፈጻጸም ግምገማ የሚሰጠው ዉጤት ሰራተኞች ለመምከር እና ለማሰልጠን የሚያገለግል ሲሆን ይህም አፈጻጻማቸውን እንዲያሻሽሉ ነው።					
4.5	በስራ አፈጻጸም ምዘና የሚሰጠው ዉጤት የሰራተኞች ችሎታና ዕውቅና ለማነሳሳት ይጠቅማል።					
4.6	በአፈጻጸም ግምገማ የሚመነጨው መረጃ በአመራሮች እና አባሎች መካከል ያለውን ግንኙነት ለማጠናከር ነው።					
4.7	የስራ አፈጻጸም ለመለካት የሚያገለግሉት የአፈጻጸም መስፈርቶች በግልፅ የተቀመጡ እና ተጨባጭ ናቸው።					

4.8	በድርጅቱ የአፈፃፀም ግምገማ መስፈርት የእኔን እውነተኛ አፈፃፀም ለመለካት ይችላል።					
4.9	በእኔ እምነት የስራ አፈፃፀሜን ለመገምገም የሚያገለግለው የአፈፃፀም ግምገማ ፎርም ውጤታማ የሆኑትን ሰራተኞች ውጤታማ ካልሆኑ ለመለየት የሚያስችል ነው።					
4.10	የስራ አፈፃፀም ምዘና ቅፅ በስራዬ ባህሪ ጋር አብሮ የሚሄድ ነው።					
5.	ሽልማት እና ማካካሻ					
5.1	በዚህ ተቋም ውስጥ ያለኝ ደመወዝ ይበቃኛል።					
5.2	ድርጅቱ በብቃት ወይም በክህሎት ላይ የተመሰረተ የደመወዝ ጭማሪ ይሰጣል።					
5.3	የእኔ ድርጅት በእያንዳንዱ ትርፍ ሰዓት ስራ የገንዘብ ጉርሻ ይሰጣል።					
5.4	ድርጅቱ አብዛኛውን ጊዜ አነስተኛ የገንዘብ ያልሆኑ ሽልማቶችን ለሠራተኞች ያዘጋጃል።					
5.5	ሰራተኞች ከሽልማት ጋር በተያያዘ በውሳኔ አሰጣጥ ሂደት ውስጥ ይሳተፋል።					
5.6	የእኔ ድርጅት የሥራ ክንውን ለመወሰን ወሳኝ ነገር የሰራተኞች ማበረታቻ ካሳ ነው።					
5.7	ድርጅታችን፣ ደሞዝ እና ሌሎች ጥቅማጥቅሞች ከወቅቱ ጋር የሚነፃፀሩ ናቸው።					

5.8	የሁሉም ሰራተኞች ማካካሻ ከሥራ አፈፃፀሙ ጋር በቀጥታ የተያያዘ ነው።					
5.9	በድርጅቱ በስራ አፈፃፀም ላይ የተመሰረተ የሽልማት ስርዓት አለ።					
6.	የሰራተኛ ስራ አፈፃፀም					
6.1	በተግባሮቹ እና በስራው ክፍፍል ደስተኛ ነኝ።					
6.2	ሁልጊዜም ለድርጅቱ ተልዕኮ እና ራዕይ ቁርጠኛ ነኝ።					
6.3	ስራዬን እወዳለሁ እና ሁልጊዜም የተሰጡኝን ስራዎች ለማጠናቀቅ እነሳሳለሁ።					
6.4	ከስራ ባልደረቦቼ ጋር በመተባበር ስራዬን አከናውናለሁኝ።					
6.5	የደመወዜ እርከኔ በስራ አፈፃፀሜ ላይ ቀጥተኛ ተጽእኖ ያሳድራል።					
6.6	ተጨማሪ ክህሎቶችን በመማር የስራ አፈፃፀሜን ለማሻሻል እድል ተሰጥቶኛል።					
6.7	በድርጅቱ ውስጥ ከፍተኛ የትምህርት ደረጃ ያላቸው ሰራተኞች ዝቅተኛ ደረጃ ካላቸው ሰዎች በተሻለ ሁኔታ ይሰራሉ።					
6.8	የስራ አፈፃፀሜ ለድርጅቱ እድገት አስተዋፅኦ እንዳለው ይሰማኛል።					
6.9	የመንግስት ጊዜን እና ቁሳቁሶችን በአግባቡ እና በብቃት እጠቀማለሁ።					
6.10	በተቻለ መጠን ብዙ ደንበኞችን አገለግላለሁ እና ችግሮችን በማምከን እና ፈጠራዊ መፍትሄ አዘጋጃለሁ።					

መመሪያ፡- የሚከተሉትን ጥያቄዎችን በአግባቡ በማንበብ ፊትለፊት ባለው ምርጫ ላይ መልሶ በጣም እስማማለሁ ከሆነ (5)፣ እስማማለሁ ከሆነ (4)፣ በመጠኑ እስማማለሁ ከሆነ (3)፣ አልስማማም ከሆነ (2)፣ እና በጣም አልስማማም ከሆነ (1) ትይዩ ባለው የሰው ምልክት ውስጥ የ(X) ምልክት በማድረግ ከሰው ሀብት አስተዳደር አሰራር ጋር ያለህን ስምምነት/ መስማማት ይግለጹልን።

ክፍል III: የቃለ መጠይቅ ጥያቄዎች

1. በድርጅቱ ውስጥ የስራ አፈጻጸምዎን እንዴት ይገመግማሉ? (ዝቅተኛ ፣ ጥሩ ወይም በጣም ጥሩ) ከሽልማት እና ከስራዎች ጋር ተመጣጣኝ ነው ወይስ አይደለም? እባክዎን ያብራሩ።

2. በአዲስ አበባ ፖሊስ ኮሚሽን ዋና መ/ቤት ስላለው አጠቃላይ የሽልማትና የካሳ አሰራር ሂደት ምን ይጠቁማሉ? (መሰረታዊ ክፍያ/ደመወዝ፣ ጥቅማጥቅሞች፣ እውቅና፣ ማስተዋወቅ፣ በጊዜ ሂደት ክፍያ እና የስራ ሁኔታ)።

3. ውጤታማ ምልመላ እና የሰራተኛ ምርጫ ለአዲስ አበባ ፖሊስ ኮሚሽን ዋና መመሪያ ቤት አስተዋጽኦ ያደርጋል ብለው ያስባሉ? አብራሩ።

4. በእርስዎ አስተያየት ድርጅቶቹ በደመወዝ፣ በሽልማት እና በዕውቅና አሰጣጥ ስርዓት ላይ የሚታየውን ችግር እንዴት ያርሙታል?

5. ድርጅትዎ የሰራተኞችን አፈፃፀም የበለጠ ለማሳደግ ምን ማድረግ አለበት ብለው ያስባሉ?

6. በስራ ቦታዎ አፈፃፀምዎን የሚነኩ አንዳንድ ነገሮች ምንድን ናቸው? ያብራሩ?

7. ድርጅቱ በሚሰጥዎ አሰራር ረክተዋል?

8. እባክዎን በድርጅቱ የሚሰጡትን ጥቅሞች ያብራሩ, በስራዎ አፈፃፀም ረገድ ለእርስዎ ምን ያህል አስፈላጊ ናቸው?
